

ROZPRAWA DOKTORSKA

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Numerical Modeling of Deep Convection: Case Study of the 21 August 2007 Severe Convective System over the Masurian Lake District

Numeryczne modelowanie głębokiej konwekcji na przykładzie gwałtownego systemu konwekcyjnego z dnia 21 sierpnia 2007 z Pojezierza Mazurskiego

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Streszczenie

Letnim zjawiskom konwekcyjnym często towarzyszą groźne zjawiska pogodowe, jak wyładowania atmosferyczne, silny wiatr, ekstremalne opady i powodzie błyskawiczne. Z tego powodu dokładne prognozy pogody zwiększają bezpieczeństwo ludzi, mienia i różnych systemów transportu. Obecnie numeryczne prognozy pogody (NPP) pozwalają na prognozowanie gwałtownych zjawisk konwekcyjnych z kilkugodzinnym wyprzedzeniem. Przy braku silnego wymuszania synoptycznego czy orograficznego modele NPP są jednak podatne na błędy wynikające na przykład z trudności w reprezentacji mechanizmów inicjacji konwekcji. Przyczyną bywa rozdzielczość modeli niedostosowana do rozwiązywania procesów warstwy granicznej lub zbyt mała liczba obserwacji meteorologicznych dostępnych dla schematów asymilacji danych.

Niniejsza praca opisuje gwałtowny system konwekcyjny (burzę), który rozwinął się w dniu 21 sierpnia 2007 nad Pojezierzem Mazurskim (Poj. Mazurskim), a następnie dokumentuje badania nad możliwością odtworzenia burzy z pomocą dzisiejszych modeli konwekcyjno-skalowych. Opisana burza spowodowała powstanie porywów wiatru do 35 m s^{-1} oraz wysokich fal na jeziorach. Te zjawiska spowodowały rozległe zniszczenia i aż kilkanaście ofiar śmiertelnych. Ówczesne systemy NPP w Instytucie Meteorologii i Gospodarki Wodnej – Państwowym Instytucie Badawczym (IMGW-PIB) nie były wystarczająco zaawansowane, aby jawnie prognozować burze. Obecnie tamta burza okazuje się być wyzwaniem dla konwekcyjno-skalowych modeli NPP z uwagi na ograniczoną dostępność powierzchniowych i troposferycznych obserwacji meteorologicznych z terenu Europy Środkowo-Wschodniej, które mogłyby być wykorzystane do asymilacji w systemach NPP.

Ważnymi elementami pracy są zebranie i analiza dostępnych danych meteorologicznych z dnia 21 sierpnia 2007. W szczególności praca zawiera opis sytuacji synoptycznej oraz lokalne obserwacje mezoskalowe sprzed chwili rozwoju burzy. Analiza pokazuje, że burza rozwinęła się w podzwrotnikowej masie powietrza w sytuacji braku wymuszania synoptycznego, ale przy obecności mezoskalowego powierzchniowego odpływu zimnego powietrza pochodzącego od wcześniejszych rozproszonych burz. Po stronie zawiętrzonej tych burz zaobserwowano w warstwie powierzchniowej pas wilgotnego powietrza. Pas był wydłużony w kierunku północno-północno-zachodnim, a zarejestrowane temperatury punktu rosy przewyższały 20°C . Ponadto według symulacji

NPP południowo-południowo-wschodnie wiatry średnio-nisko troposferyczne nad Poj. Mazurskim były najprawdopodobniej zlokalizowane ponad tym pasem wilgotnego powietrza. Te czynniki wytworzyły warunki sprzyjające rozwojowi i szybkiemu przemieszczaniu się burzy, która mogła zorganizować się w burzę przybierającą kształt łuku (na obrazie radarowym).

Analizowana burza jest złożonym przypadkiem dla NPP, ponieważ rozwinęła się wskutek przejściowo sprzyjających warunków w warstwie powierzchniowej, wiatrów średnio-nisko troposferycznych i niewielkiej mechanicznej destabilizacji atmosfery. W celu konwekcyjno-skalowego modelowania tej burzy został wykorzystany model NPP COSMO. Dwa zestawy danych globalnych zostały zbadane pod kątem użyteczności generowanych z nich warunków początkowych i brzegowych dla symulacji w ograniczonej domenie nad Polską. Dane reanalizy ERA-5 oceniono jako lepsze i wykorzystano do wygenerowania danych początkowych i brzegowych symulacji konwekcyjno-skalowych. Pierwsze symulacje NPP wskazały, iż potrzeba wykonać szereg modyfikacji danych pochodzących z reanalizy, aby odtworzyć warunki środowiskowe adekwatne do warunków sprzed burzy nad Poj. Mazurskim. Te modyfikacje polegały na asymilacji obserwacji zebranych do południa dnia 21 sierpnia 2007 opisujących warunki gruntowe, powierzchniowe i górne sprzed burzy.

Niezbędne okazało się też wprowadzenie do symulacji jawnego mechanizmu inicjacji konwekcji. Przetestowano jego deterministyczną i stochastyczną wersję. Schemat stochastyczny okazał się być lepszym w przypadku około-kilometrowej konwekcyjno-skalowej symulacji NPP COSMO, ponieważ prowadził do realistycznie wyglądającego obrazu rozwoju burzy w kształcie łuku i generującego silne porywy wiatru. To też oznacza, że model NPP COSMO jest w stanie odtworzyć powstanie i rozwój burzy nad Poj. Mazurskiego o ile pracuje na wysoce realistycznych danych i jest rozszerzony o skuteczny mechanizm pobudzający start konwekcji. Konfiguracja z mechanizmem stochastycznym została użyta w dodatkowych testach dotyczących wrażliwości modelu w reprezentowaniu burzy w kształcie łuku w przypadku zwiększenia rozdzielczości siatki poziomej oraz zmiany schematu mikrofizyki chmurowej. Dyskusja symulacji NPP zawiera ocenę wpływu tych modyfikacji na dynamikę systemu burzowego i wynikające z niej zmiany w wielkości i strukturze symulowanych przypowierzchniowych porywów wiatru.

Podsumowując, analizy obserwacji meteorologicznych i wykonane symulacje numeryczne pokazują złożone środowisko oraz trudny do odtworzenia łańcuch zdarzeń prowadzący do rozwoju systemu burzowego w kształcie łuku z towarzyszącymi niebezpiecznymi zjawiskami meteorologicznymi. Niniejsza praca przedstawia badanie możli-

wości operacyjnego prognozowania tego systemu konwekcyjnego za pomocą współczesnego konwekcyjno-skalowego modelu NPP COSMO w ramach dyscypliny naukowej inżynieria środowiska.

Słowa kluczowe: głęboka konwekcja, modelowanie konwekcyjno-skalowe, burza w kształcie łuku, stochastyczne wzbudzenie konwekcji

Abstract

The warm-season moist deep convection is frequently accompanied by hazardous weather such as lightning, strong winds, heavy precipitation, and flash floods. It follows that accurate weather forecasts contribute to the safety of public, property, and transportation systems. Nowadays, numerical weather prediction (NWP) can forecast severe convective weather in a few-hours advance. In the absence of strong synoptic or topographic forcings, the NWP models are prone to errors because convection initiation may be missed due to unresolved boundary layer processes or insufficient weather observations for data assimilation.

This study initially focuses on the 21 August 2007 severe convective system (SCS) that developed over Masurian Lake District (Masurian LD) and brought high public attention in Poland. Then, the study investigates capabilities of a convection-permitting NWP model in hindcasting of that SCS. The discussed SCS induced surface wind gusts up to 35 m s^{-1} and significant waves on the lakes that caused extensive damage and loss of life. At that time, operational NWP systems at the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management – National Research Institute (IMGW-PIB) were not sufficiently advanced to explicitly forecast severe convective processes. Even today, the SCS represents a challenge for convection-permitting NWP because of a poor availability of surface and free-troposphere observations over the Central-Eastern Europe that can be assimilated into an NWP system.

Meteorological data available for the 21 August 2007 are collected and analyzed in this study, including the pre-storm synoptic and mesoscale conditions. This analysis shows that the SCS developed within a subtropical air mass, with no synoptic-scale forcing and in the presence of a mesoscale cold pool outflow from earlier scattered deep convection. Downwind from the scattered convection, a moist plume was observed in the surface layer. It was elongated in the NNW direction and featured dewpoint temperatures exceeding 20°C . The low-to-mid tropospheric SSE winds over Masurian LD likely overlapped the plume as suggested by model simulations. All those factors created favorable conditions for the development and fast propagation of deep convection that organized itself into a bow echo system.

The analyzed bow echo system represents a complex NWP case because it developed in response to transient favorable surface conditions, low-to-mid tropospheric winds, and a small-scale mechanical destabilization. The COSMO NWP model is used for the SCS convection-permitting modeling and two global datasets were tried to provide large-scale environment for limited-area simulations over Poland. The ERA-5 reanalysis was assessed superior and it was used as a source of initial and boundary conditions. Initial NWP simulations indicated that several modifications were necessary to obtain a reliable representation of the pre-storm conditions over Masurian LD. Those included assimilation of the pre-storm soil, surface, and upper-air weather observations collected up to the noon of 21 August 2007.

As the model misses to timely initiate a bow echo system, the setup was expanded to include either a deterministic or a stochastic idealized convection initiation scheme. The stochastic scheme was assessed as the superior for the kilometer-scale convection-permitting COSMO NWP simulations because its application led to the realistic representation of the bow echo system. That also denotes that the COSMO NWP model is capable to reconstruct the development of the bow echo system under the condition that the model data are realistic and the model is fitted with an effective convection initiation scheme. The setup with the stochastic scheme was subsequently used for additional model testing, focusing on the sensitivity of the bow echo representation to the refined horizontal resolution and cloud microphysics. The discussion of NWP simulations included an assessment of the influence of the modifications on the systems dynamics and consequent changes in the structure and magnitude of simulated surface wind gusts.

Overall, analyses of available observations and completed numerical simulations highlight a complex environment and difficult to predict chain of events that lead to the development of the bow-echo system. This dissertation documents the COSMO NWP model capabilities in modeling of that convective system. This research is classified within the discipline of environmental engineering.

Key words: deep convection, convection-permitting modeling, bow echo system, stochastic convection initiation

Contents

1	Introduction	17
1.1	Numerical weather forecasting	17
1.2	Motivation	18
1.3	Scientific objectives	19
1.4	The numerical modeling of atmospheric convection for the environmen- tal engineering and protection	20
1.5	Content	22
2	Theory of mid-latitude moist deep convection	25
2.1	Introduction	25
2.2	Principal modes of moist deep convection	29
2.2.1	Single-cell convection	30
2.2.2	Multicellular convection	30
2.2.3	Squall line	31
2.2.4	Bow echo	39
2.2.5	Supercellular convection	42
2.3	Convective parameters	46
2.3.1	Description of the dry and moist air	47
2.3.2	Equations of motion	49
2.3.3	The parcel theory	51
2.3.4	Convective parameters derived from the parcel theory	53
2.3.5	Vertical wind shear and the bulk Richardson number	54
3	Numerical modeling of moist deep convection	57
3.1	Introduction	57
3.2	The COSMO model	58
4	The 21 August 2007 severe convective system	61
4.1	Introduction	61
4.2	Weather situation preceding the severe convective system formation	63
4.2.1	Overview of synoptic situation	63

4.2.2	Upper-air characteristics	66
4.2.3	Analysis of convective activity preceding the severe convective system	71
4.2.4	Surface characteristics of the pre-storm environment	71
4.3	Initiation of the severe convective system from 21 August 2007 and system-related weather observations	75
4.3.1	Initiation of severe convection	75
4.3.2	Movement of the severe convective system	77
4.3.3	Surface observations related to the crossing of the severe convective system over Masurian LD	79
4.4	Evolution of the system structure	82
4.4.1	Morphological observations obtained by the weather radar in Gdańsk	82
4.4.2	The system propagation velocity	86
4.4.3	A comment on the convective mode of the system	86
4.5	Reconstruction of a likely sounding for Masurian LD	88
4.6	Summary	89
5	Setup of a modeling framework for studying the severe convective system from 21 August 2007	93
5.1	Introduction	93
5.2	General setup of simulations	95
5.2.1	The COSMO-7 setup	95
5.2.2	The COSMO-2 setup	96
5.3	Review of the coarse-scale COSMO-7 semi-operational simulations	96
5.3.1	The G-7 simulation	96
5.3.2	The E-7 simulation	97
5.4	Characterization of the weather evolution modelled in the E-7 simulation	104
5.5	Improvement of boundary layer and free tropospheric air characteristics	109
5.5.1	Adjustment of the soil model temperatures and the lakes surface temperatures	109
5.5.2	Switch to the convection-permitting setup	111
5.5.3	Nudging of surface observations	113
5.5.4	Modification of surface heat flux magnitude and the Bowen ratio	118
5.5.5	Direct adjustment of horizontal temperature gradients in the low-to-mid troposphere	125
6	Modeling of the severe convective system development	139
6.1	Introduction	139

6.2	Convective systems developing in simulations with additional convection triggering	140
6.2.1	Simulation with the deterministic scheme	140
6.2.2	Simulation with the stochastic scheme	147
6.2.3	Simulation with the concurrent stochastic and deterministic schemes	159
6.3	Impact of the low-tropospheric ambient wind on the system movement velocity	161
6.4	Impact of the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme on the model representation of the system	167
6.4.1	The REF+Stoch+2M simulation	167
6.4.2	Evolution of surface wind gusts compared to the REF+Stoch simulation	175
6.5	Impact of a refined horizontal grid length	179
6.5.1	The COSMO-05 setup	180
6.5.2	The high-resolution simulation with the 1-M cloud microphysical scheme	180
6.5.3	The high-resolution simulation with the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme	189
6.6	Summary	197
7	Summary	199
	Acronyms	203
	Bibliography	205

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Numerical weather forecasting

At one time weather forecasts were provided on the basis of a qualitative analysis of hand-drawn upper-air and surface synoptic maps. Since mid-1950s, these methods have been complemented by analyses of numerical weather forecasts calculated by numerical weather prediction (NWP) models (Persson, 2005). This was a direct result of the computer revolution, with the idea of NWP first considered at the beginning of the 20th century (Bjerknes, 1904), see also extended discussion in Lynch (2008) and Bauer et al. (2015). Nowadays, NWP models serve as well-established environmental engineering tools and have a nearly 70-year-long history of development and applications. With the help of those models, the national weather services around the world provide forecasts to the public on a daily basis. Availability of accurate weather forecasts contributes to the economic growth and public safety.

The earliest NWP models were based on the barotropic vorticity equation of Charney et al. (1950). Those models were not capable to in representing moist processes, moist shallow and deep convection in particular. With the advance in computer power and data assimilation methods, the models switched to solving simplified Navier-Stokes equations with the hydrostatic balance in the vertical direction, the so-called primitive equations, and they included a simplified representation of moist processes. In the operational NWP, effects of moist convection had to be represented indirectly, that is, by applying convection parameterizations (e.g., Arakawa and Schubert, 1974; Emanuel, 1991; Kain, 2004; Manabe et al., 1965; Tiedtke, 1989). Today's operational NWP models reach horizontal resolutions that allow explicit modeling of moist deep convection (i.e., convection-permitting models (CPMs); Baldauf et al., 2011; Done et al., 2004; Saito, 2012). This is a significant achievement of the NWP science as moist convection is ubiquitous in the Earth's atmosphere and it is responsible for a significant vertical mixing between the planetary boundary layer and the free atmosphere aloft. In particular, weather forecasts applying CPMs typically outperform forecasts obtained with

convection-parameterizing models in terms of, for example, convective rainfall forecasting (Clark et al., 2016). This is important because convection frequently creates hazardous conditions for people, property, and transportation systems. Representing convective processes and hazardous weather associated with them (e.g., lightning, severe winds, flash floods, hail) remains an important task of the contemporary weather forecasting (Yano et al., 2018).

The convection-permitting modelling was introduced to the operational NWP about two decades ago (Baldauf et al., 2011; Done et al., 2004; Saito, 2012). Recent years brought initial application of convection-permitting general circulation models (e.g., Satoh et al., 2008; Stevens et al., 2019) and applications of regional CPMs to the climate change science (e.g., Prein et al., 2015). In the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management – National Research Institute (IMGW-PIB), the first operational runs of the COSMO CPM (www.cosmo-model.org) date back to 2012.

This dissertation focuses on applied research regarding the improvement of numerical modeling of convective weather (Sections 1.2 and 1.3). Therefore, this dissertation is classified within the discipline of environmental engineering, as explained in Section 1.4.

1.2 Motivation

This dissertation is motivated by the necessity to understand and improve CPMs' capability in forecasting of rapidly developing high-impact convective weather events that develop in weakly-forced (e.g., thermally-forced internal air-mass) environments (Majumdar et al., 2021). In such situations, when strong synoptic-scale forcings are absent, convection initiation (CI) often results from local interactions of small-scale atmospheric flows (e.g., a sea-breeze, a cold pool) and/or poorly resolved physical processes (e.g., surface fluxes, turbulence, radiation, cloud processes; Pielke, 2001). These are frequently subgrid-scale and their representation in operational CPMs is rather imperfect (Clark et al., 2016; Hirt et al., 2019). The problem is important as CPMs are becoming well-established tools in forecasting of deep moist convection but they may also experience significant errors. Those errors are usually related to the high sensitivity of simulated convective processes (e.g., CI, exact location, morphology) to environmental conditions and model setup (Hohenegger and Schaer, 2007; Morrison et al., 2009). Therefore, major scientific efforts need to be undertaken to ensure realistic representation of the atmosphere down to the convective scales (i.e., convective-scale data analysis; e.g. Bachmann et al., 2020; Clark et al., 2016) and to represent sub-grid scale atmospheric processes with physically-based, scale-aware, and stochastic parameterizations (Brunet et al., 2015, Chapter 10). Moreover, soil and ocean models are developed and coupled with NWP models to provide realistic bottom boundary conditions for

temperature, humidity, and momentum equations (Brunet et al., 2015, Chapters 8 and 9).

With the complexity of the problem and despite of ongoing efforts, the NWP forecasts of high-impact convective weather are still not always successful. This limits practical performance of weather services in providing accurate model-driven forecasting. In particular, some high-impact weather warnings get issued only on the basis of observations and, thus, little time is left to propagate those warnings to the public (Majumdar et al., 2021). The advantages of shifting from observation-driven to model-driven forecasting of high-impact weather events are also appreciated by the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) that decided to launch a 10-year international research project HIWeather (www.hiweather.net). One of the aspects emphasized in the HIWeather project is the forecasting of severe deep convection.

Since many thunderstorms in Poland develop as internal air-mass systems (i.e., in absence of synoptic fronts; Kolendowicz, 2012), operational forecasts are prone to errors. Therefore, this dissertation aims to explore the ability of the state-of-the-art COSMO CPM used in IMGW-PIB to represent the development of a particular internal air-mass convective system that evolved into a high-impact weather event.

1.3 Scientific objectives

This study considers a severe convective system (SCS) that passed the Masurian Lake District (Masurian LD) in the early afternoon of 21 August 2007 causing a widespread damage and loss of life. One may expect that the representation of the system's development constitutes a challenge for the CPM as the system had a relatively small scale and developed rapidly within a relatively uniform air mass. The relevant observations-based severe weather warning was issued only minutes before occurrence of widespread damage.

This dissertation examines a research hypothesis that the COSMO CPM with horizontal grid size of around 2 km is capable to provide a realistic (i.e., featuring alike timing, location, convective organization, and surface wind gusts magnitude) hindcast of the severe convection from 21 August 2007. As initial attempts to verify that hypothesis encountered only forecast misses, it was found that the issue requires an in-depth investigation.

Three specific aspects of the general problem are considered within this dissertation. The first investigation aims to verify to what extent the model-inferred state of the environment, that is, the atmospheric and soil initial conditions, is responsible for the encountered model errors. It also aims at reconstructing realistic initial conditions using available observations and applying various techniques including trajectory analysis and nudging-based data assimilation.

As the study considers the internal air-mass convection development, the second investigation aims to develop and test idealized convection triggering schemes leading to a realistic representation of convection development. Evaluation of those schemes takes into account representation of the initial burst of scattered (unorganized) deep convection in the vicinity of Masurian LD and subsequent development of the mature organized mesoscale system. The analysis focuses on the spatio-temporal structure of the system (as documented in the observations) and on the presence of severe surface gusts responsible for the damages.

Currently used operational CPMs apply horizontal grids of the size ranging between 3 and 1 km, which is far too coarse to resolve deep convective currents (Bryan et al., 2003). Moreover, CPMs typically use one-moment microphysics parameterizations that neglect the spatial variability of liquid and frozen particle number concentrations (Adams-Selin et al., 2013; Morrison et al., 2009). Therefore, the final investigation considers simulations of the SCS applying increased horizontal resolution and double-moment microphysics. Those changes increase computational costs and, therefore, they are expected to enter the operational NWP in a few years time. Thus, the author investigates whether an additional expense provides any advantage in the model representation of the considered high-impact weather event as compared to the default setting.

The author has an appropriate experience in the area of numerical modeling to fulfill the listed objectives. That includes the optimization of numerical codes of CPMs (Rojek et al., 2015; Wójcik et al., 2012), development of the COSMO-EULAG CPM (Baldauf et al., 2013; Kurowski et al., 2016; Ziemiański et al., 2021), testing of the limited-area version of the ICON model (Baldauf et al., 2021), and numerical modeling of convective weather (Wójcik, 2017; Wójcik et al., 2019; Ziemiański et al., 2021).

1.4 The numerical modeling of atmospheric convection for the environmental engineering and protection

The scientific policy statement of the Committee of Environmental Engineering of Polish Academy of Sciences (Rosik-Dulewska, 2010) explicitly includes the methods of modeling of the environmental state within the scope of the scientific interests of the environmental engineering discipline. The statement notes that "In the environmental engineering and protection the attention is also paid on the methods of forecasting the state of the environment based on modeling, and management of data describing the environment, considering the valid quality standards for its elements."¹. There is also no doubt that the Environmental Protection Law (Dz.U. poz. 1219, 2020) in its Arti-

¹"W inżynierii i ochronie środowiska zwraca się także uwagę na metody prognozowania stanu środowiska w oparciu o modelowanie oraz zarządzanie danymi opisującymi środowisko, z uwzględnieniem obowiązujących standardów jakości poszczególnych jego elementów." (pol)

cle 3, point 39, includes the atmosphere into the scope of the meaning of the notion of "environment", stating that "environment - it is understood by the whole of nature elements, also transformed in a result of human actions, and particularly earth surface, minerals, waters, air, landscape, climate and other elements of biodiversity, and also the interactions between them"².

Following that general definition, the modeling of the environment's state is also practically explored as the objective of the scientific discipline of environmental engineering, mining, and energetics by Polish scientific groups working within this discipline. An example is the Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy we Wrocławiu defining one of the scientific objectives of the discipline of environmental engineering, mining and energetics as "mathematical modeling of environmental processes"³ (upwr.edu.pl/badania/wiodace-dyscypliny-naukowe/inzynieria-srodowiska-gornictwo-i-energetyka; Accessed November 10, 2021). More specifically, The Faculty of Building Services, Hydro and Environmental Engineering of the Warsaw University of Technology, while defining the basic scientific objectives in the discipline of environmental engineering, mining, and energetics, enumerates "numerical modeling of atmospheric processes and practical applications"⁴ (is.pw.edu.pl/koks/; Accessed November 10, 2021).

These general considerations and their practical implementation and scientific exploration within the Polish scientific community working in the area of environmental engineering confirm that the numerical modeling of atmospheric processes aimed at their practical applications falls into the category of scientific objectives of environmental engineering, and this dissertation falls within that scope.

It is worth mentioning that research regarding the CPMs performance (in particular, the research presented in this dissertation) contributes to the modeling quality of other environmental phenomena that are influenced or driven by convection in the sense of a cause-effect or a mutual relationship and are considered by the environmental engineering. Here, four exemplary relations are listed:

1. Operational hydrology: quasi-stationary convective systems (systems featuring approximate cancellation of the motion of individual cells with the system propagation, i.e., the apparent motion associated with the initiation of new cells) can drive the development of flash floods, that are the one of the most dangerous hazards induced by convection (Kundzewicz et al., 2013; Schumacher and Johnson, 2005).

²“środowisku – rozumie się przez to ogół elementów przyrodniczych, w tym także przekształconych w wyniku działalności człowieka, a w szczególności powierzchnię ziemi, kopaliny, wody, powietrze, krajobraz, klimat oraz pozostałe elementy różnorodności biologicznej, a także wzajemne oddziaływania pomiędzy tymi elementami” (pol.)

³“modelowanie matematyczne procesów środowiskowych” (pol.)

⁴“numeryczne modelowanie procesów atmosferycznych i zastosowań praktycznych” (pol.)

2. Air protection: modeling and tracing of pollutants, mineral dusts, volcanic ashes, and other may be more accurate with CPMs due to the more realistic representation of, for example, wind currents or precipitation (in case of water-reactive substances). Besides that, certain physical phenomena in the air protection modeling are only reasonably represented with CPMs. For example, Foroutan and Pleim (2017) report that dusts uplifting in arid areas by cold-pool induced surface wind gusts start to be reasonably represented with CPMs.
3. Urban modeling: the CPMs brings in a capability to better characterize weather and climatology of urbanized areas as those models describe more accurately the turbulent exchange processes than coarser-scale models. For example, spatial heterogeneity of surface fluxes in urbanized areas may lead to moisture convergence and deep convection initiation within urban heat islands (Baik et al., 2001; Barlow et al., 2017; Kusaka et al., 2014).
4. Climate modeling: usage of the CPMs has a potential to mitigate the statistical uncertainties related to the cumulus parameterization problem in global-scale climate models (Arakawa, 2004; Prein et al., 2015). This is important because negative impacts of climate warming includes an increasing number of heat waves during warm-seasons, emergence of disturbances in the environmental water cycle, and appearance of the more severe convective systems (e.g., Kirtman et al., 2013; Raymond et al., 2020). Moreover, as the Committee of Environmental Engineering of Polish Academy of Sciences aims to contribute to the Poland transformation into the climate-neutral country (Committee of Environmental Engineering, 2021), an accurate quantification of near-future temperature increase is of the interest of that scientific community.

1.5 Content

The dissertation is structured as follows. Chapter 2 describes the key points of the mid-latitude moist deep convection theory. That includes the historical background, principal convective modes, equations of motion, parcel theory, and common convective parameters.

An introduction to the contemporary NWP methods is provided in Chapter 3. In particular, that introduction includes a description of the COSMO NWP model that is used in the experimental part of this study.

The meteorological description of the SCS from Masurian LD is provided in Chapter 4. The description deals with meteorological data related to the pre-storm environment, the storm development, and the storm movement over Masurian LD. The discussion includes: (i) overview of the synoptic situation, (ii) upper-air observations,

(iii) satellite and radar observations, and (iv) surface-based observations obtained at the weather stations in Masurian LD. The discussion allows assessing the dominant class of convection, the bow echo, that explains severity of the system. That part of this dissertation may be also useful, to a moderate extent, in training of operational meteorologists. Most of that discussion was presented at two conferences, Wójcik (2017) and Wójcik et al. (2019), and those results are to be published in near future.

The modeling study is presented throughout the Chapters 5 and 6. The study follows the plan outlined by the scientific objectives (Section 1.3). Chapter 5 includes an assessment of the COSMO model forecasts and step-by-step analysis and correction of the COSMO model representation of convective mixed layer and free-tropospheric characteristics. In particular, that includes search for the optimum initial and boundary conditions and reduction of the main identified biases in the meteorological fields. The presented optimizations are more diligent than one from the initial study of Wójcik (2017), which paved the way for this study. The chapter ends with the assessment of the model performance when fitted with arguably the most realistic representations of the atmosphere and soil in north-eastern Poland.

Chapter 6 provides the model evaluation for the settings when the CI is explicitly provided by a deterministic or a stochastic triggering scheme developed in the course of this study. As the setup with the stochastic convection triggering scheme reconstructs a system that is more similar to the one from 21 August 2007, that setup is utilized to evaluate results' sensitivity to the employed microphysical parameterization scheme and the finer horizontal grid.

A summary of the obtained results is provided in Chapter 7.

Chapter 2

Theory of mid-latitude moist deep convection

2.1 Introduction

The theory of moist deep convection describes processes associated with lifting of near-surface moist air into the free troposphere that causes lowering of the lifted air temperature to the dewpoint temperature, subsequent water vapour condensation, and latent heat release. The heat release leads to significant horizontal air density differences that facilitate maintenance of ascending air currents (convective updrafts). The water vapour condensation leads ultimately to the formation of precipitation and precipitation-laden air descent (convective downdraft). Moist convection concerns several types of mid-latitude weather systems whose horizontal scales range from meso- γ (2 km to 20 km) to meso- α (200 km to 2000 km) of Orlanski (1975). The first in-depth study of moist convection was carried out in the Thunderstorm Project (Byers and Braham, 1948) in the second half of 1940s.

Most of the mid-latitude convective weather systems consist of one or more meso- γ scale convective cells that build-up into large spatio-temporal structures. Each cell undergoes a 30 to 60 minutes long life cycle that consists of three stages: growth, maturity, and dissipation (Figure 2.1). In the growth stage, the cell is composed of a vertically extended cloud (up to about 6 km altitude in mid-latitudes) that contains an updraft spanning the entire cloud depth. Typically, the towering cumulus cloud is recognized as an isolated growing convective cell. The updraft contains mostly moist air of near-surface origin. Lifting of air from the surface lowers the air temperature due to the adiabatic expansion. The water vapour condensation starts when the lowering air temperature reaches the dewpoint temperature (at the lifting condensation level, LCL). The condensation warms air due to the latent heat release. Decreasing density of the heated air contrasts with the environment and is responsible for development and main-

Figure 2.1: The life cycle of an isolated convective cell: the towering cumulus cloud (left), the mature cumulonimbus cloud (middle), and the dissipating cumulonimbus cloud (right). Arrows depict the cell-relative wind direction and magnitude within the cloud and in the precipitating downdraft. The reference wind magnitude and the horizontal spatial scale are shown in the bottom-left corner of each picture. Source: Byers and Braham (1948).

tenance of the convective updraft. The rising and condensing air undergoes the moist adiabatic expansion.

Convective cells transition from the growth to the mature stage is associated with formation of precipitation that consists of rain drops or ice particles that fall towards the surface under the influence of the gravitational force. In a convective cell, the rain drops increase their mass primarily by collection (accretion) of cloud water (Houze, 1997). Weight of precipitation forces air to descend so that the downdraft current can develop. The precipitation-driven downdraft is negatively buoyant compared to the environment due to (i) the weight of water droplets and (ii) the evaporative cooling of downdraft air that increases its negative thermal buoyancy (Srivastava, 1985). When reaching the surface, the downdraft current forms a cold pool under the mature cell. The cold pool spread may cause convection organization, dissipation or redevelopment, depending on a particular weather situation. An isolated mature cell takes the shape of the cumulonimbus cloud. The stronger ones are capable to spread its anvil cloud into the lower stratosphere.

In the dissipation stage the convective updraft weakens as the spreading cold pool cuts the cell from near-surface moist air. As a result, precipitation in that cell gradually declines causing its downdraft current to deteriorate as well.

The spreading cold pools are considered a key element influencing organization of deep convection (Fujita, 1957; Moncrieff and Miller, 1976; Rotunno et al., 1988). The largest ones grow up to the meso- α scale and reach up to 4 km thickness in a few hours only (Bryan and Parker, 2010). For that reason, understanding and modeling of spreading cold pools increases operational capabilities in forecasting of the movement

Figure 2.2: The air flow model of the mature thunderstorm outflow. Source: Droegemeier and Wilhelmson (1987).

of entire convective systems and in assessing probability of the mechanical convection triggering. The principal airflow model of a spreading cold pool comes from the theory of gravity currents (Figure 2.2; Charba, 1972; Droegemeier and Wilhelmson, 1987; von Kármán, 1940) that describes dynamics associated with the horizontal spreading of a denser fluid in a less-dense fluid environment. Such flow is driven primarily by the horizontal pressure gradient force because the denser fluid exerts the higher hydrostatic pressure.

An initial local development of moist convection is referred as the convection initiation (CI). CI is associated with a forced ascent of moist air, originating from the planetary boundary layer, to the level of free convection (LFC), that is, to the level where the further ascent of air is ensured by its positive buoyancy due to the latent heat release. CI can happen as a result of the mechanical lifting done by an external force or as a result of the thermal (solar) forcing. In case of the mechanical forcing, the external work may be associated with a larger meso- α scale weather system (e.g., advection of temperature or orographically-forced ascent of an air mass) or a smaller meso- β /meso- γ scale weather phenomenon (e.g., at a cold pool or a sea breeze boundary, due to local orographically-driven air circulations, or due to internal gravity wave activity). In case of the thermal forcing, CI results from the insolation-driven growth of the boundary layer and shallow convective clouds (i.e., the shallow-to-deep convection transition). Finally, CI does not have to result from one factor only, but it might originate from mutual contributions of the mechanical and thermal forcings.

Forecasting of the moist deep convection is important because convective weather brings hazards to the safety of people and property. Dangerous convective events are commonly named as the severe convective systems (SCS). The hazards include lightning, tornadoes, severe wind gusts, flash flood rainfall, and hail. The lightning comes from in-cloud charge separation resulting from collisions between ice crystals and ice pellets. Ice crystals tend to become positively charged and gather up at cloud tops. Ice

pellets tend to become negatively charged and tend to fall towards the surface. The tornado represents an extreme form of a rotating updraft driven by the dynamically-induced vertical pressure gradient force that extends to the surface. The other hazards are predominantly associated with precipitation and precipitation-driven downdrafts. The severe wind gusts are formed as a result of violent negatively buoyant downdrafts (possessing their own kinetic energy) spreading over surface and transferring horizontal momentum from the troposphere (downbursts and microbursts, Section 2.2.3). The flash flood rainfall forms in situations when growth of precipitating cells approximately balances cells advection by environmental winds. As a result, a quasi-stationary precipitating system forms (Chappell, 1986, Chapter 13). The hail represents an extreme form of ice precipitation that forms when convective updrafts are sufficiently strong to lift large water drops and ice particles, extending their in-cloud lifetime and growth via collision-coalescence. In order to reduce damage major efforts are undertaken to identify weather conditions that support development of SCS, to collect meteorological and climatological data related to SCS, and to improve NWP model capabilities in forecasting development and evolution of SCS.

A two-way coupling exists between synoptic-scale flows and mid-latitude convective systems. On the one hand, synoptic-scale processes provide a setting in which convection develops (for example, Morris, 1986, describes the Spanish Plume setting, see also Section 2.2.4). On the other hand, convective flows redistribute atmospheric heat and moisture and, thus, decrease large-scale imbalances resulting from differential surface insolation and cause disturbances in synoptic-scale flows (Palmén and Newton, 1969). Moreover, in the climate context, common convective clouds influence noticeably the global energy budget (Boucher et al., 2013).

Deep moist convection research developed significantly after 1945 as a result of the Thunderstorm Project field campaign that collected and analyzed numerous measurements of thunderstorm conditions (see Byers and Braham, 1948, and references therein), and allowed researchers to go beyond theoretical studies and surface-based observations (for a review see Doswell, 2007). More recently, in 1985, the PRE-STORM (Preliminary Regional Experiment for STORM-Central) project collected observations of mesoscale convective systems (MCS) leading to the discovery of the rear-inflow jet (RIJ) in squall lines (Houze, 1989; Houze et al., 1989; Smull and Houze, 1987) and to the formulation of the long-lived squall lines theory (Rotunno et al., 1988; Weisman and Rotunno, 2003). Also, several projects were launched to increase knowledge about the continental mid-latitude convection and to improve weather forecasting techniques. For example, the IHOP (International H₂O Project; 2002) project studied the 3-dimensional water vapour distribution in pre-storm environments, and the BAMEX (Bow Echo and MCV Experiment; 2003) project studied the life cycle of MCS and bow echoes (Davis et al., 2004). The supercells and tornadoes were studied in the VOR-

TEX (Verification of the Origins of Rotation in Tornadoes Experiment; 1994-1995) and VORTEX2 (Verification of the Origins of Rotation in Tornadoes Experiment 2; 2009-2010; www.vortex2.org) projects. Four fundamental meteorological measurement techniques were applied in each of these projects, that is, surface-based or dropsonde soundings, radar reflectivity measurements (since 1970s with Doppler radars and since 2010s with dual-polarization Doppler radars), airborne measurements, and surface synoptic station measurements.

In Poland, contemporary convective weather research includes the calculation of decadal climatologies (e.g., Nieckarz and Zięba, 2013), analyses of synoptic patterns associated with thunderstorms in Poland (e.g., Kolendowicz, 2006, 2012), identification of extreme meteorological conditions associated with deep convection (e.g., Ustrnul and Czekierda, 2009), development of nonhydrostatic models (e.g., Baldauf et al., 2013; Kurowski et al., 2016; Wójcik et al., 2017; Ziemiański et al., 2021) and their optimization and testing (e.g., Baldauf et al., 2021; Rojek et al., 2015; Wójcik et al., 2012; Wójcik et al., 2015), and observations and modeling of SCS (e.g., Taszarek and Kolendowicz, 2013).

The following sections of this chapter present the key elements of mid-latitude moist convection theory to allow understanding of the subsequent chapters of this dissertation. Section 2.2 describes the fundamental convective modes including those frequently associated with severe convection. Section 2.3 introduces the parcel theory and presents the most frequently used convective indices. For the topics not included in this study, the reader is referred to the contemporary textbooks, for example, Markowski and Richardson (2010) or Trapp (2013).

2.2 Principal modes of moist deep convection

One can distinguish two fundamental building blocks of convective systems: *ordinary cells* and *supercells*. The ordinary cells were investigated during the Thunderstorm Project (Byers and Braham, 1948). The supercells were described over a decade later by Browning (1964) who presented a comprehensive kinematic airflow model on the basis of atypical storms recorded by early radar systems over the US. The fundamental difference between the ordinary cells and the supercells is the force that drives the updraft. While updrafts of ordinary cells are driven only by the buoyant force, the updrafts of supercells are driven by both buoyant and dynamically-induced vertical pressure gradient force (Marwitz, 1973; Schlesinger, 1978; Wilhelmson, 1974). That is, in supercells the vertical vortex (mesocyclone) causes a local pressure depression and leads to the localized dynamic upward acceleration of an inflowing convectively unstable air. As opposed to the ordinary cells, the supercells are long-lasting (up to around a few hours) and they usually occur as a single entity.

The ordinary cells are the building blocks for both single-cell and multicellular convection (Sections 2.2.1 and 2.2.2, respectively). Two specific subtypes are frequently distinguished within the multicellular convection, that is, the squall line and the bow echo (Sections 2.2.3 and 2.2.4, respectively). Discussion of those types of convection is limited to the warm-season conditions.

2.2.1 Single-cell convection

The single-cell convection is usually observed in weak forcing environments having a small 0-6 km vertical wind shear $SH_{06} \leq 10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (weak-shear environment) and the convection available potential energy (CAPE) ranging between a few hundreds and 2000 J kg^{-1} (convective indices are described in Section 2.3). The single-cell convection is primarily driven by the boundary layer diurnal cycle and it occurs usually between the local noon and sunset. The life cycle of a single cell follows the cycle discussed in the introduction. This type of convection is rarely responsible for severe weather.

For a single-cell, precipitation usually falls through the updraft, potentially causing its weakening. As a result, the cold pool can form directly beneath the cell. If more than one single-cell are present in an area, collisions of gust fronts may trigger the secondary generation of cells (even some time after dissipation of a parent cell; Droegemeier and Wilhelmson, 1985).

2.2.2 Multicellular convection

The multicellular convection develops when the low-level flow promotes an organized development of new cells along the gust front. The multicellular convection may last for several hours, depending on the actual weather conditions and despite the fact that such systems consist of the ordinary short-lived cells. The spatial scale of multicellular convection may range from meso- β to meso- α (from 20 to 2000 km). Rather smaller meso- β scale structures are observed in environments where convection development results from the thermal forcing or a small-scale mechanical forcing. Larger meso- β and meso- α scale convective structures often develop in environments with the large-scale mechanical forcing. The multicellular convection frequently occurs in environments having SH_{06} shear between 10 and 20 m s^{-1} and CAPE between a few hundreds and a few thousands J kg^{-1} (Markowski and Richardson, 2010). The lower CAPE values are sufficient for environments featuring a significant source of mechanical forcing (e.g., orography).

In contrast to the single-cell convection, growth of new cells in the multicellular systems is organized and quasi-periodic during their lifetime. That characteristic originates from the continuous interaction between the environmental vertical wind shear in

Figure 2.3: Schematics showing interactions of the spreading cold outflow circulations with the environmental wind shear in the storm-relative reference frame (wind profile shown in the right of both chart). When a negligible environmental wind shear is present the development of new cells is hindered (left). When a noticeable environmental wind shear is present the new cells develop on the downshear side of the convective system (right). Closed circles depict horizontal vorticity associated with either the environmental wind shear or the cold outflow circulations. White (black) arrows denote convective updrafts (downdrafts). Source: Rotunno et al. (1988).

the lower troposphere and the gust front of the system, and ensures the system longevity in steady-sheared environments. That is, the cold outflow trying to spread downshear has its circulation opposed by that of the shear (Rotunno et al., 1988, see also Section 2.2.3). As a consequence, the interaction of the environmental wind shear and the gust front promotes the deeper lifting of atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) air increasing the chance for a successful CI at the gust front (Figure 2.3).

Movement of a multicellular convective system is a superposition of two components: (i) the advection of individual cells with the mean environmental wind (advective component), and (ii) the new cells development at the leading edge of a convective system (propagation component). Since the propagation of multicellular systems is strongly correlated with forced ABL air lifting, the development of new cells in the environments with uni-directional vertical wind shear (like in Figure 2.3, right) is strongly favored at the downshear edge of the outflow (the upshear and downshear edges are shown in Figure 2.3). Thus, multicellular systems movement typically differs from the mean environmental flow.

A MCS is a multicellular system having the spatial size exceeding 100 km. It is usually assumed that flow in such a system is influenced by the Coriolis force.

2.2.3 Squall line

The squall line represents a line-oriented multicellular convection that lasts several hours. Many mid-latitude squall lines are classified as MCS and their flow fields indeed show the influence of the Coriolis force (Fujita, 1978; Houze, 2004). Squall lines consist of the ordinary cells in majority of meteorological situations, but supercellular squall lines may exist as well (Bluestein and Jain, 1985; Lilly, 1979). Here, the first

type, the non-supercellular squall line, is described.

The first systematical analysis of squall line observations comes probably from Newton (1950) who analyzed the Thunderstorm Project data. He found that a squall line may appear ahead of a cold front and then move, at a faster rate, into the warm sector (*prefrontal* squall line). As an example, Newton (1950) shows a case study of a prefrontal squall line that lasted around 30 hours while moving from the Minnesota to Kentucky in the US. Newton was convinced that the longevity of that squall line was linked to the vertical transfer of horizontal momentum from the troposphere towards the surface and argued that this process would support the low-level convergence necessary for convection maintenance.

Field campaigns carried out in 1970s and 1980s, for example, GATE (Global Atlantic Tropical Experiment; Frank, 1978; Houze and Betts, 1981; Zipser, 1977) and PRE-STORM (Bluestein and Jain, 1985), gathered observational data regarding structure and environments of squall lines. Those campaigns documented that squall lines frequently occur in environments with a significant low-level vertical wind shear and that they tend to be aligned perpendicular to that shear. As a result, main theoretical considerations focused on interactions between the environmental low-level vertical wind shear and the cold pool-induced circulations. An early comprehensive model was given by Rotunno et al. (1988) (RKW theory), who used the vorticity argument to explain how short-lived cells undergoing growth and decay cycles can build a squall line. That vorticity analysis was subsequently extended by Weisman (1992) who described the role of RIJs in the relative cold pool and wind shear balance.

Early numerical studies of squall lines treated them as approximately two-dimensional, that is, uniform in the along-the-line direction and variable in the across-the-line direction (Moncrieff and Green, 1972; Schlesinger, 1973). Such an approach simplified modeling of major air currents and was adequate to model the RIJ development (e.g., Lafore and Moncreff, 1989). The early three-dimensional (3D) squall line modeling was initiated by Moncrieff and Miller (1976) who analyzed the squall line movement velocity. Growth of computational resources accelerated the 3D modeling, allowing modeling the interaction of squall lines with the Coriolis force (Skamarock et al., 1994; Weisman and Davis, 1998) or the upscale growth and organization of convection (Grabowski and Moncrieff, 2001).

Early synoptic forecasts of a squall line movement were based on the environmental wind field at the *steering level* height, that is, the height where environmental flow is equal to the movement velocity of the squall line. For squall lines over the US, Bluestein and Jain (1985) found that the steering level is typically located between 6 and 7 km above the surface. More recent modeling studies suggest that squall lines movement velocity is rather a result of convective momentum transport from mid-levels to the cold pool (Mahoney et al., 2009). Therefore, a precise forecast of a squall line movement

Figure 2.4: Cross section through an idealized mature trailing stratiform squall line showing its major morphological features. The thin contour denotes the cloud border, the thick contour denotes the squall line radar echo boundary, the shaded/black areas denote the moderate/high reflectivity zones, the arrows denote the major currents, and the letters H_i and L_i denote the pressure meso-highs and meso-lows. Source: Houze et al. (1989).

Figure 2.5: Idealized cross section through an idealized mature trailing stratiform squall line listing the principal cloud microphysical processes occurring in the convective and stratiform regions. Adopted from Houze (1989).

has to consider, for example, the velocity of RIJ and the momentum transfer from the RIJ to the cold pool. For such applications, the NWP modeling seems to be an essential and indispensable tool.

The vertical cross sections of a classical two-dimensional mature squall line are shown in Figures 2.4 (morphology) and 2.5 (cloud microphysical processes). The convective region (usually up to 40 km wide) and the stratiform region (capable to reach even 200 km width) are separated by a narrow transition zone (an area of relatively low radar reflectivity). Convective cells grow at the front of the squall line, above the gust front. During their life cycle, cells gradually move into the middle of the convective region and finally dissipate in the rear.

At the surface, passage of the convective region is distinguished by heavy convec-

tive showers, temperature and dewpoint temperature reduction, and by pressure increase associated with the precipitation-cooled air (meso-high H_1 in Figure 2.4, primarily hydrostatic; Haertel and Johnson, 2000). Approach of the convective region may actually be preceded by a weak surface meso-low (L_2 in Figure 2.4) that is associated with adiabatic heating of the air aloft caused by a pre-storm mesoscale compensating subsidence (Houze et al., 1989). In mid-levels of the convective updraft and above the surface meso-high (H_1), a hydrostatically-induced low pressure area is observed (mid-level meso-low L_3 in Figure 2.4) since the warmer updraft air has significantly larger buoyancy than surrounding environmental air (see also Equation 2.2). The positively buoyant updraft air is capable to reach the upper-troposphere and, occasionally, the lower stratosphere (overshooting top). At those heights the updraft air becomes negatively buoyant, significantly decelerates, and ultimately diverges horizontally (with a directional bias resulting from local environmental winds). That negatively buoyant air aloft may partially contribute to the formation of the upper-air meso-high (H_2 in Figure 2.4; see Fritsch and Maddox, 1981, for discussion of other factors).

In the convective region, precipitation particles grow primarily via coalescence and riming and experience the size sorting (Figure 2.5). The lighter water particles reach with the updraft the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere (temperature below -40°C , i.e., colder than the temperature of homogeneous freezing of droplets), freeze, and are advected into the stratiform region. Therefore, the anvil cloud consist of ice particles only. Many mid-sized water particles leave the updraft and are advected through the transition zone into the stratiform region (Houze, 1997). The heaviest water particles (i.e., with a high fall velocity such as rain drops, hail and graupel) fall to the ground inside of the convective region. If the descending RIJ (beginning in the stratiform region) remains aloft up to the convective area, this heavy precipitation ultimately brings it to the surface (see also Figure 2.4).

The stratiform region is formed by the lifted ABL air and smaller water and ice particles from the convective region. Depending on the environmental winds, the stratiform region may be located behind the squall line (trailing stratiform region; Figures 2.4 and 2.5), on one side of the squall line (parallel stratiform region) or at the front of the squall line (leading stratiform region; for a topical review see Parker and Johnson, 2000). The following description focuses on the squall line with the trailing stratiform region.

A typical trailing stratiform region extends between 50 and 200 km in the across-the-line direction of a mature system (Smull and Houze, 1987), behind the convective region. Three principal flows can be distinguished in that region: (i) the ascending front-to-rear flow, (ii) the precipitation-driven air descent, and (iii) the descending RIJ (Figure 2.4). The front-to-rear flow contains moist ascending air from the convective region having a relatively low vertical velocity (10s of cm s^{-1}). Since the horizontal

velocity component of that air is approximately preserved, it moves to the rear of the squall line. In that flow, the particles advected from the convective region experience a further growth by water vapour deposition and particle aggregation. The aggregation is the strongest around the melting level.

When an ice particle fall velocity within the stratiform region exceeds the mesoscale ascent rate, that ice particle falls out (sediments) from the ascending front-to-rear flow into the significantly drier descending RIJ. Ice particles that reach the melting layer increase their radar reflectivity due to the difference in the dielectric constant for liquid water and solid ice (the bright band effect). A typical radar reflectivity of the melting layer is of around 40 dBZ (Leary and Houze, 1979). Melting of ice particles and evaporative cooling within RIJ decrease the air temperature and cause formation of the precipitation-driven air descent that can bring a significant fraction of the descending RIJ to the surface (Figure 2.4) and contribute to the cold pool growth. The maximum surface precipitation rates observed in the stratiform region are around one order of magnitude smaller than in the convective region (Leary and Houze, 1979).

The RIJ can be defined as an intrusion of mid-tropospheric environmental air into the storm across the trailing stratiform precipitation boundary that extends up to the convective region (Figures 2.4 and 2.6). The RIJ is a common feature of both observed and modelled trailing stratiform squall lines (Lafore and Moncreff, 1989; Smull and Houze, 1987; Weisman, 1992). The RIJ development starts with the build-up of the mid-level meso-lows in the convective and stratiform (if present) regions (L_3 and L_4 in Figure 2.4, respectively). These lows build a horizontal pressure gradient field that extends up to the rear of the stratiform region and drives the mid-level horizontal momentum generation (Figure 2.6; Lafore and Moncreff, 1989; Mahoney et al., 2009). To the rear of the stratiform region, the RIJ descends gradually since the amount of ice particles is limited so that the evaporative cooling is less intensive. In that area, a wake low may develop as a gravity-wave-driven response to the low-level cooling associated with stratiform precipitation (L_1 in Figure 2.4; see Haertel and Johnson, 2000, and references therein).

The descent of RIJ accelerates around the melting layer in the stratiform region because there is a noticeably higher availability of ice particles and the cooling is driven by both evaporation and melting (Leary and Houze, 1979). The descent of RIJ usually features an intensive downward momentum transfer (Figures 2.4 and 2.6).

An important insight into the squall line development and structure comes from the RKW theory (Rotunno et al., 1988). The theory postulates that the approximate balance between the cold pool circulation (*system-generated* horizontal vorticity) and the line-normal low-level vertical wind shear (*environmental* horizontal vorticity; Δu) is responsible for the periodic and efficient development of new convective cells and, thus, for the squall line longevity (Figure 2.3). In particular, the theory introduces the

Figure 2.6: Schematic of the major budget terms related to the trajectory of RIJ. The term PGA denotes acceleration due to the pressure gradient force, $VA\bar{u}$ denotes the vertical advection of the environmental winds, and VAu'/v' denotes the vertical advection of the perturbation wind. Source: Mahoney et al. (2009).

Figure 2.7: The horizontal vorticity balance in a squall line between the low-level vertical wind shear and the cold pool circulation (left). The rearward (upshear) tilted updraft develops in response to the overwhelming cold pool circulation (right). The vortex circulations at the trailing stratiform precipitation boundary contribute to the RIJ development (right). Source: Weisman (1992).

cold pool intensity parameter C to measure the cold pool strength:

$$C^2 = 2 \int_0^h (-B) dz, \quad (2.1)$$

where the upper integral limit (h) denotes the minimum height above the surface where the buoyancy (B) first becomes non-negative. The buoyancy B is defined (in terms of the potential temperature θ , water vapour mixing ratio q_v , and liquid/solid water mixing ratio q_l) as:

$$B = g \left((\theta - \bar{\theta}) / \bar{\theta} + 0.608(q_v - \bar{q}_v) - q_l \right), \quad (2.2)$$

where the overbars denote the environmental state. When the balance is observed ($\Delta u = C$), the updraft is expected to be upright (Figure 2.7, left panel). The theory states that under this condition: (i) lifting at the leading edge of the cold front is the strongest, (ii) entrainment of the updraft is minimized, and (iii) the volume of air that is pushed out of the updraft way is the smallest. In that situation, the updraft air can better realize its CAPE and the squall line has a higher chance to be long-lived and severe.

Weisman (1992) extended the RKW theory by considering the role of horizontal temperature gradients on RIJs development and mature convection maintenance. In his

Figure 2.8: Horizontal vorticity balance in a squall line with a developed elevated RIJ. Source: Weisman (1993).

modeling study, Weisman observed that for the large and upshear-tilted updraft (Figure 2.7, right) the development of RIJ is explained in terms of the two-dimensional horizontal vorticity analysis. That is, the horizontal buoyancy gradients ($\partial B/\partial x$) present at the rear edges of both upshear-tilted updraft and surface cold pool build two significant sources of horizontal vorticity (η):

$$\frac{d\eta}{dt} = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial x}, \quad (2.3)$$

and the two developing rear-edge vortices drive the RIJ development as well (Figure 2.8).

By analyzing the horizontal vorticity balance at the rear of a convective system (between vorticity fields generated at the cold pool and the cloud rear edges), Weisman (1992) proposed to distinguish two classes of RIJs: the RIJs gradually descending to the surface (*descending* RIJ) and the RIJs that remain elevated up to the region of convective downdrafts (*elevated* RIJ). The descending RIJs are attributed to situations with the dominating cold pool vortex, and the elevated RIJs are attributed to the balanced situation (Figure 2.8). Weisman (1992) also pointed out that an elevated RIJ is capable to reestablish the horizontal vorticity balance near the front of an upshear-tilted squall line by counteracting the dominating cold pool circulation. As a result, a deep updraft can regenerate and the realization of CAPE within the convective region can be improved.

It should be mentioned that the RKW theory, although possibly the most widespread in textbooks, remains a subject of the scientific debate since the very beginning (Lafore and Moncreff, 1989). Doubts concern, for example, differences between the observed shear profiles of long-lived squall lines and the shear profiles promoted by the RKW theory as the most supportive for the long-lived severe convection (Coniglio et al., 2012).

Squall lines may feature *mesovortices*, that is, vertical vortices that develop near the leading edge of squall lines with the diameter of the order of several kilometers and the maximum vertical vorticity up to around 0.01 s^{-1} (Trapp and Weisman, 2003). Theirs growth mechanisms include the Helmholtz instability (shearing instability) at the

Figure 2.9: Mesovortex couplet growth (red and blue shaded volumes and solid circles at the surface) through the tilting of horizontal vorticity tubes (black solid lines). The vortex denoted in red is cyclonic and the one denoted in blue is anticyclonic. The impact of the planetary vorticity (orientation shown in the right) after some time on the vortex couplet is denoted via the dashed red and blue circles as a relative change with respect to the solid circles. The cloud (white area), precipitation (blue shading), downdraft winds (black arrows), and gust front location (green line) are shown as well. Source: Trapp and Weisman (2003).

border between the cold pool and the environment, and the precipitation-driven tilting of environmental horizontal vorticity (Figure 2.9). In the former case, many similarly-oriented vortices develop along the border and may subsequently merge into a larger mesovortex. In the latter case, the tilting builds two opposite-oriented mesovortices. Mesovortices are capable to enhance horizontal surface wind in two ways: by hosting a tornado (non-supercellular), and by inducing a superposition of the vortex rotational winds with the diverging cold pool-driven winds (Atkins et al., 2005; Trapp and Weisman, 2003; Wakimoto et al., 2006).

Squall lines are regarded as a potential source of hazardous surface winds. These winds can be divided, according to their origin, into the tornadic (rotating) and the non-tornadic (straight-line) winds. The rotating winds originate from the low-level non-supercellular tornadogenesis that occurs when a mesovortex is stretched into a tornado-scale vortex. The straight-line winds are associated with the evaporatively-cooled cold air descent in the form of a *downburst* (violent downdraft air current that strikes the ground and diverges horizontally causing damage), *microburst* (a downburst having the diameter up to 5 km), or with the spreading cold pool (Charba, 1972; Fujita, 1978). The straight-line winds frequently reflect the downward momentum transfer occurring along with the RIJ descend or in a strongly-sheared environment. Squall lines with the straight-line winds frequently take the bow echo shape (visible in the horizontal radar reflectivity cross sections; Section 2.2.4).

Figure 2.10: Horizontal cross section through the radar reflectivity pattern of the classical bow echo system (grey shading). Mid- and low-level system-relative winds are shown with thick and thin arrows, respectively. Source: Weisman (1993).

Figure 2.11: Horizontal cross section through the radar reflectivity contours showing time evolution of the classical bow echo (beginning with a strong wet downburst, DB). Source: Fujita (1978).

2.2.4 Bow echo

Bow echoes are defined as quasi-linear mature convective systems with the bow-shaped radar reflectivity image (Figures 2.10, 2.11, and 2.12) that indicates onset of severe surface outflow winds (straight-line winds; Fujita, 1978; Hamilton, 1970; Nolen, 1959). The typical bow echo width ranges between 20 and 200 km. The most severe bow echoes are the ones having up to 100 km width, that is, not necessarily the largest ones (Davis et al., 2004). The large scale bow echoes or series of bow echoes that affect a widespread area are called *derechos* (Johns and Hirt, 1987).

Bow echoes typically develop from weakly organized convective cells, out of supercell downbursts, or within squall lines. For bow echoes over the US (the country with the highest frequency of bow echo events), the first process is the most frequent one (around 45% of cases) and is known to generate bow echoes in even less than 30 minutes after merging of pre-existing convective cells (Klimowski et al., 2004). That pre-existing convection frequently lasts for several hours before the bow echo formation occurs (e.g., the case study in Mathias et al., 2017). Bow echoes developing out of pre-existing squall lines are very frequent as well (40% of cases over the US; Klimowski et al., 2004). In that case, the bow echo develops usually after 2-4 hours of the squall line lifetime. That timing compares well with experiences known from many squall line modeling studies, for example, Weisman (1993); Weisman and Davis (1998).

The first kinematic flow model, clear separation from other morphological types, and underlining of the initial downbursts importance in the bow echo genesis was proposed by Fujita (1978), as a result of the NIMROD (National Intensive Meteorological Research on Downburst) research project. Since then, a rich observational dataset was established and an observation-based classification of bow echoes was proposed (classical bow echo, bow echo complex, cell bow echo, and squall line bow echo; Klimowski et al., 2004). To come together with the observational study in Chapter 4 the subsequent paragraphs focus on the classical bow echo, that is, the bow echo that is larger than a single cell, not embedded into a squall line, and is isolated from other organized convection.

Development of the classical bow echo usually starts after a strong precipitation-laden downburst founding a thick cold pool (Stage A in Figure 2.11; Fujita, 1978). That diverging cold pool drives organization of new convective cells at its leading (downshear) edge. As a result, the horizontal reflectivity pattern becomes slightly bow-shaped (Stage B in Figure 2.11). If updrafts are sufficiently strong, a deep mid-level meso-low develops, followed by a RIJ development, and a further shaping of the system into the bow with the bulge (stage C in Figure 2.11). At that time, rear-inflow *notches* (currents of drier mid-level environmental air entraining the storm) may be observed in the trailing stratiform precipitation region.

A further enhancement of the mid-level RIJ may result from the development of book-end vortices, that is, the system-scale vertical vortices that rotate at the bow echo lateral ends consistently with the RIJ (Figure 2.10, Stage C in Figure 2.11; Weisman, 1993). Flow in those vortices comes from two interwinding currents: a rising warm air at the outer side of the bow echo and a sinking cold air at the inner side of the bow echo (Houze, 2004). If a pair of book-end vortices develops, the one oriented with the planetary vorticity vector (i.e. the cyclonic vortex in the Northern Hemisphere) ultimately starts to dominate over the other and the system symmetry becomes broken (Figure 2.9; Stage C in Figure 2.11). As a result, the bow echo may take the shape of a comma with the most severe convection occurring at the head (Stages D and E in Figure 2.11). While a couplet of book-end vortices is frequently detected in idealized studies, their presence is not a mandatory feature of observed mid-latitude bow echoes. For example, Mathias et al. (2017) and Davis et al. (2004) (Figure 2.12) document bow echoes with a one book-end vortex only. Bow echo may also dissipate before reaching the comma stage due to adverse environmental conditions, for example, after entering a large body of water having significantly different characteristics of ABL.

The dynamical model of the classical bow echo can be described by the 3D vorticity equation ($\boldsymbol{\omega}$; Weisman and Davis, 1998):

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\omega}}{dt} = (\boldsymbol{\omega} + f\mathbf{k}) \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} + \nabla \times (B\mathbf{k}), \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 2.12: Horizontal (left) and vertical (right) cross section of the 10 June 2003 bow echo recorded during the BAMEX field campaign in the US. Shown are the system-relative winds (arrows) and the radar reflectivity (coloured contours). White line in the left figure marks the location of the vertical cross section (right). Source: Davis et al. (2004).

where f is the Coriolis parameter, \mathbf{v} is the 3D velocity vector, \mathbf{k} is the unit vector in the vertical direction, and B is the buoyancy (e.g., given by Equation 2.2). The vorticity equation describes the creation of horizontal vorticity in the presence of horizontal buoyancy gradients (covered also by Equation 2.3), tilting and stretching of vorticity, and influence of the planetary vorticity as represented by the $f\mathbf{k}$ term. In particular, time evolution of the vertical component of the vorticity vector (ζ) is given by:

$$\frac{d\zeta}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\omega}_H \cdot \nabla_H \mathbf{w} + (\zeta + f) \frac{\partial w}{\partial z}, \quad (2.5)$$

where the symbols with subscript H denote the horizontal operators. The first term on the right-hand side of Equation 2.5 represents the vertical vorticity production by the tilting of horizontal vorticity (originating from the low-tropospheric sheared flow or system-generated horizontal vorticity; Weisman and Davis, 1998). The second term on the right-hand side represents stretching of the absolute vertical vorticity (i.e., $\zeta + f$). In particular, Equation 2.5 describes development of book-end vortices in result of the horizontal vorticity tilting (first term) and their subsequent differentiation under the influence of the planetary vorticity (second term).

There is a consensus that development of warm season mid-latitude bow echoes requires high moisture content in the surface layer (dewpoint temperatures exceeding 20°C), high CAPE, and relatively large amount of wind shear across the lower or low- and mid-troposphere (Johns and Hirt, 1987). The exact amount of wind shear needed to produce a well-organized classical bow echo depends on the thermodynamical compo-

sition of the atmosphere. For large bow echoes developing in weakly-forced conditions over the US, in the 50% of cases the ML_CAPE is between around 1600 and 2900 J kg^{-1} , the 0-2.0 km wind shear is between 7.0 and 12.0 m s^{-1} , and the 0-6.0 km wind shear is between 10.5 and 20.0 m s^{-1} (Evans and Doswell, 2001). In numerical simulations, however, Weisman (1993) identified that at least 20 m s^{-1} wind shear over the lowest 2.5 km layer is required for an environment with around 2500 J kg^{-1} of CAPE, or at least 30 m s^{-1} wind shear over the lowest 5.0 km layer is required for an environment with around 3000 J kg^{-1} of CAPE. That duality of required wind shear magnitudes is being raised as a flaw of the RKW theory (Coniglio et al., 2012).

The two main synoptic bow echo patterns over the US are the progressive and the serial ones (Figure 2.13, left and right, respectively; Johns and Hirt, 1987). The progressive bow echoes develop in vicinity of a quasi-stationary front in the cooler air mass and move along the front (and mean wind) to terminate in the warm sector. The serial bow echoes also start in vicinity of a quasi-stationary front and the individual bowing systems in the warm sector are followed by development of subsequent ones. In both cases the occurrences remain quite well correlated with the diurnal temperature cycle (79% of large bow echoes occur between 10:00 and 22:00 of local time; Johns and Hirt, 1987).

Although bow echoes are less frequently observed over Europe, the two recent decades brought an increasing number of publications describing the European bow echoes (Mathias et al., 2017; Schmid et al., 2000) and derechos (Gatzen, 2004; Punkka et al., 2006; Taszarek et al., 2019). The best known bow echo European weather pattern is the so-called *Spanish Plume*, that is, a warm season situation when dry sub-tropical (Spanish or Saharan) air is lifted in a thermal low over Spain and advected N or NE in front of an upper trough (initially offshore of the Spanish coast). Concurrently, a significant convective instability develops near the surface owing to the high insolation (dry air of the Spanish Plume aloft) and a higher availability of moisture to the N and NE from Spain. The release of that instability is initially inhibited by the plume aloft but it is ultimately facilitated by the approach of the cooler upper trough (Mathias et al., 2017; Morris, 1986)

2.2.5 Supercellular convection

The supercellular convection is different from the ordinary convection in a number of ways. That convection is built as a long-lived cell that propagates continuously (the mechanism of new cell triggering does not hold the primary role; Figure 2.14) and has the movement direction significantly different from the mid-tropospheric environmental winds. Also, it is far more frequently associated with severe hail and is capable to host supercellular tornadoes (the most severe ones on Earth). The classical supercells develop in environments with the deep vertical wind shear exceeding 20 m s^{-1} and

Figure 2.13: Schematics showing two typical synoptic bow echo patterns over the US: the progressive bow echo (left), and the family of serial bow echoes (right). The horizontal scale is included in each plot. Hatching represents areas endangered by severe surface winds. Source: Johns and Hirt (1987).

the moderate to high CAPE (around 1000 J kg^{-1} or more; Markowski and Richardson, 2010). This type of convection is rarely observed in Poland (Taszarek and Kolendowicz, 2013).

In the supercell, the updraft-downdraft couplet is usually physically separated, and both currents do not disrupt each other (Klemp, 1987). That occurs because supercells develop mostly in environments with the strong vertical wind shear that eases separation of the downdraft and hydrometeors from the updraft (Figure 2.15). The supercell updraft, also known as the main storm tower (Figure 2.14), is located above the intersection of the forward and rear-flank gust fronts (Figure 2.15), has a diameter of several kilometers, and rotates with the tangent wind velocity of several tens of meters per second around a large fraction of its height. That rotation originates from the tilting and stretching of the horizontal environmental vorticity when the ABL air enters the updraft. The concentration of vertical vorticity may exceed 0.01 s^{-1} and this vortex is named as the *mesocyclone*.

Supercell research started with the arrival of meteorological radars in late 1940s. This technology allowed researchers to observe the major morphological features of supercells (e.g., the hook echo shape and the bounded weak echo region (BWER)) and the major kinematic features (e.g., the tendency to travel to the right of the winds in the low- and mid- troposphere; Newton and Katz, 1958). Relative easiness of the radar-based distinction between the ordinary cells and the supercells allowed for the acquisition of early climatological data and facilitated development of the first kinematic model (Browning, 1964). Subsequently, Klemp (1987); Rotunno (1981); Rotunno and Klemp (1981, 1985) proposed theories for the mesocyclone dynamics.

The conceptual model of Browning (1964) links the internal supercellular flows to the veering environmental tropospheric winds¹ in case of the severe right-moving (SR) supercell. That model postulates that the updraft is maintained by the low-level inflow of potentially warm air approaching the SR supercell from the right forward

¹Veering wind means the clockwise wind direction change with the increasing height.

Figure 2.14: Schematic view of the major cloud structures of a supercell. Source: Doswell and Bosart (2001).

Figure 2.15: The contours of the classical supercell radar reflectivity at various heights (left). Source: Browning (1964). The horizontal cross section of the wind and precipitation fields near the surface for the classical supercell (right). Here, the arrows denote the horizontal low-level flow relative to the supercell, the thick contour denotes the 40 dBZ reflectivity contour, the front lines mark the environmental air inflow (warm front) and the extension of the cold pool (cold front). The light gray color denotes the heaviest precipitation zones, that is, the forward-flank downdraft (FFD) and the rear-flank downdraft (RFD). The dark gray color denotes the updraft zone (UP). The letter 'T' shows the most probable location for a tornado development. Source: Lemon and Doswell (1979).

Figure 2.16: Relation between the veering environmental wind (L, M, and H denote the low-, mid-, and the upper-troposphere) and the supercell movement velocity (open circle; left upper panels). Airflow at various heights in the right-moving classical supercell (left bottom panel). Three dimensional view of that airflow over the surface (right panel). The right panel includes typical precipitation trajectories (black dots), the precipitation region at the surface (shading), the potential tornado zone, and the surface gust front. Source: Browning (1964).

flank (Figure 2.15, left). Horizontal vorticity of the veering low-level inflow tilts to vertical and, thus, the updraft rotates. Ascending air parcels turn cyclonically by 270° (Figure 2.16, bottom left). As a result, a large anvil forms on the forward-flank side of the supercell (Figures 2.15 and 2.16, both right). Larger hydrometeors fall out of the updraft, enter and cool the drier mid-tropospheric air (evaporation), and are advected by mid-tropospheric horizontal wind out of the updraft neighbourhood (Figure 2.16, right). Therefore, the updraft features relatively low radar reflectivity within the BWER. The cooled and loaded with precipitation mid-tropospheric air starts to descent and forms downdraft currents. The wind-driven size sorting of hydrometeors results in not uniform precipitation rates at the surface (Figure 2.15, left; Dawson et al., 2015). The highest precipitation zones are named the forward-flank downdraft and the rear-flank downdraft. Hydrometeors that re-enter the updraft are transported upwards again and may acquire the large hail size.

Supercells host three types of hazardous weather, that is, damaging winds associated with either the dynamically induced surface low (located below the updraft core) or with the downbursts reaching the surface, large hail, and intense and long-lived tornadoes. The tornadoes develop either in regions where the environmental inflow and the storm outflow meet beneath the mesocyclone (Figure 2.15, right) or along the nose

of the gust front.

2.3 Convective parameters

Over 70 years of convective weather observations resulted in the development of convective parameters for operational weather forecasting. Calculation of parameters was based, at first, on rawinsonde air measurements. Later, after the onset of multi-level NWP models, the parameters became the standard tool aiding weather forecasters with NWP forecasts analysis. Several of the parameters are based on the theory of an ascending air parcel. A few others originate from the theory of supercell development and discriminate conditions favouring the supercellular convection. Research in the area of optimal convective parameters is progressing until today (e.g., Thompson et al., 2007).

Convective parameters are sensitive to the quality of rawinsonde data. One usually does not have a sounding coinciding in space and time with a weather event since the operational rawinsonde measurement network is coarse both in time (rawinsondes are released twice a day, around 11:15 and 23:15 UTC in Poland, and their ascent lasts around 2 hours) and in space (global rawinsonde network spacing ranges from meso- α to the synoptic scale). Furthermore, the rawinsonde drifts several kilometers from the launch site during the ascent. Therefore, the research community develops methods to adjust available soundings to the proximity of a weather event to obtain a more representative environmental conditions (Davies and Johns, 1993). In the most simple approach, during the warm season, the well-mixed layer (ML) part of the sounding is adjusted according to the surface measurements from the synoptic station nearest to the researched weather event.

Convective weather forecast is usually based on the convective parameters such as the convective available potential energy (CAPE), convective inhibition (CIN), lifting condensation level (LCL), level of free convection (LFC), equilibrium level (EL), and other ones. To identify the most likely convective mode one employs parameters associated with the theories of squall line and supercell development, that is, the vertical wind shear (SH) and the bulk Richardson number (BRN). Because these parameters can be calculated in a number of ways, the following subsections define the conventions employed throughout this study. For a more detailed parameter description the reader can refer, for example, to the review of Pielke (2001), the Trapp (2013) textbook, and the Markowski and Richardson (2010) textbook. The convective parameters are also combined to form the compound convective indices, for example, the storm-relative environmental helicity, energy-helicity index, and supercell composite parameter (not discussed in this study; Thompson et al., 2003).

The next two sections provide foundations of the parcel theory. Section 2.3.1 presents

the equation of state for the dry air and its extensions covering the water vapour and the hydrometeors. Section 2.3.2 introduces the 3D momentum equations and its main simplifications applicable for modeling of an ascending air parcel. Then, Section 2.3.3 introduces the parcel theory. The main convective parameters resulting from that theory are presented in Section 2.3.4. Finally, Section 2.3.5 introduces the vertical wind shear and the bulk Richardson number parameters.

2.3.1 Description of the dry and moist air

Air consists of several gaseous components from which three gases determine the main air characteristics in the context of the parcel theory. The oxygen (O_2 , molecular weight $M = 32$) and the nitrogen (N_2 , $M = 28$) constitute in average around 98% of dry air² and they determine the average molecular weight of the dry air, $M_{dry\ air} = 29$. These gases are present in Earth atmosphere only in the gaseous phase, and their distribution hardly varies in space and time. Molecules of the last leading component, the water vapour (H_2O , $M_{vapour} = 16$), are significantly lighter and their concentration across the ABL and free troposphere strongly varies in time and space, reaching locally up to a few percent of the total air mass. High variability of the water vapour concentration results, inter alia, from its capability to undergo phase transitions across the ABL and free troposphere³.

For the dry air, the principal relation between its pressure p_{dry} , density ρ_{dry} , and temperature T is given by the gas law:

$$p_{dry} = \frac{R^*}{M_{dry\ air}} \rho_{dry} T = R_d \rho_{dry} T, \quad (2.6)$$

where R^* is the universal gas constant equal $8314.5 J (kg \cdot K)^{-1}$, and R_d is the dry air gas constant equal $287 J (kg \cdot K)^{-1}$. The analogical law holds for the water vapour:

$$e = \frac{R^*}{M_{vapour}} \rho_{vapour} T = R_v \rho_{vapour} T, \quad (2.7)$$

where the water vapour constant $R_v = 461 J (kg \cdot K)^{-1}$ and e denotes the conventional abbreviation for the water vapour pressure.

The moist air can be treated as a mixture of the dry air and the water vapour. That is, the total air density (ρ) is a sum of the dry air density (ρ_{dry}) and the water vapour density (ρ_{vapour}). If the temperature T of the mixture components is the same, the Dalton's law describes the additive relation between the total pressure, p , and partial

²Air that is assumed to contain no water vapour.

³The critical temperature of water vapour, $374^\circ C$, is significantly higher than air temperatures observed in Earth troposphere (Tsonis, 2007, Chapter 6).

pressures, p_{dry} and e , of the mixture components:

$$p = p_{dry} + e = R_d \rho_{dry} T + R_v \rho_{vapour} T. \quad (2.8)$$

The virtual temperature, T_v , is a useful parameter equal the temperature which the dry air must have to have the same density ρ as the moist air at the same pressure. To define the virtual temperature two additional ratios have to be defined first. The water vapour mixing ratio, q_v , equals the mass fraction of water vapour with respect to the mass of dry air in the same volume:

$$q_v = \frac{\rho_{vapour}}{\rho_{dry}}.$$

Then, the ratio R_d to R_v is usually denoted as

$$\varepsilon = R_d/R_v \approx 0.6222.$$

Those ratios allow reformulating Equation 2.8:

$$\begin{aligned} p &= (R_d \rho_{dry} + R_v \rho_{vapour}) T = \left(R_d \rho_{dry} + \frac{R_d}{\varepsilon} q_v \rho_{dry} \right) T \\ &= R_d \rho_{dry} \left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right) T. \end{aligned}$$

The postulated definition of the virtual temperature states:

$$\begin{aligned} (\rho_{dry} + \rho_{vapour}) R_d T_v &= p = R_d \rho_{dry} \left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right) T, \\ T_v &= \frac{\rho_{dry}}{\rho_{dry} + \rho_{vapour}} \left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right) T = \frac{1}{1 + q_v} \left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right) T, \\ T_v &= \frac{\left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right)}{1 + q_v} T. \end{aligned} \quad (2.9)$$

The virtual temperature can be generalized to the density temperature that accounts for the *hydrometeors* (liquid and solid water particles sedimenting in the atmosphere). That is, the density temperature T_ρ is the temperature which the dry air must have to have the same density ρ as the moist air with hydrometeors having density ρ_{hydro} at the same pressure p (Emanuel, 1994):

$$\begin{aligned} (\rho_{dry} + \rho_{vapour} + \rho_{hydro}) R_d T_\rho &= p = R_d \rho_{dry} \left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right) T, \\ T_\rho &= \frac{\left(1 + \frac{q_v}{\varepsilon} \right)}{1 + q_v + q_h} T, \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where $q_h = \frac{\rho_{hydro}}{\rho_{dry}}$ denotes the total hydrometeors mixing ratio. Alike the density tem-

perature is the density potential temperature:

$$\Theta_\rho = \Theta \frac{1 + q_v/\varepsilon}{1 + q_v + q_h} \approx \Theta(1 + 0.61q_v - q_h), \quad (2.11)$$

which equals the density temperature of an air parcel after its adiabatic displacement to the reference pressure level (p_0). The above definition comes from a general relation between the potential temperature (Θ) and the temperature (T):

$$\Theta = T (p_0/p)^{R_d/c_p}, \quad (2.12)$$

where typically $p_0 = 1000 \text{ hPa}$ and $c_p = 1004.64 \text{ J}(\text{kg} \cdot \text{K})^{-1}$ is the specific heat capacity of the dry air at constant pressure. In terms of the density potential temperature, the gas law for the moist air reads:

$$p^{c_p/R_d} = (\rho_{\text{dry}} + \rho_{\text{vapour}} + \rho_{\text{hydro}}) \frac{R_d}{p_0^{R_d/c_p}} \Theta_\rho. \quad (2.13)$$

2.3.2 Equations of motion

A basic equation set for mesoscale flows modelling comes from the application of the second Newton's law of motion to the main dynamical forces present in the free atmosphere, such as the pressure gradient force, gravity, and the Coriolis force. The flux-form equation set reads:

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{V}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{V} \mathbf{V}) = -\nabla p - g \rho \mathbf{k} - f \rho \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{V}, \quad (2.14)$$

where the velocity vector $\mathbf{V} = [u, v, w]$, p denotes air pressure, ρ denotes air density, $g \mathbf{k}$ denotes the gravitational acceleration, $f \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{V}$ denotes the Coriolis force, and the advection term $\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{V} \mathbf{V})$ represents the transport of momentum observed in the Eulerian framework (Stuhl, 2017).

For the buoyancy driven flows⁴, the equation for vertical momentum can be simplified using the Boussinesq approximation for the buoyancy. That approximation assumes that horizontal differences in air density can be ignored except of the buoyancy term ($-g \rho \mathbf{k}$ in Equation 2.14). The implementation of that approximation assumes that one can extract a hydrostatically-balanced background density profile, $\rho_0(z)$, from the atmospheric density field:

$$\rho = \rho_0(z) + \rho',$$

$$p = p_0(z) + p',$$

⁴Flows in which the density differences following the fluid flow are small and negligible in comparison with the fluid density itself.

where

$$\partial p_0 / \partial z = -\rho_0 g.$$

That approximation is applied to the vertical momentum equation:

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_0 + \rho') w}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot ((\rho_0 + \rho') \mathbf{V} w) = -\frac{\partial p_0}{\partial z} - \rho_0 g - \frac{\partial p'}{\partial z} - \rho' g, \quad (2.15)$$

resulting in a cancellation of several terms:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_0 w}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{V} w) = -\frac{\partial p'}{\partial z} - \rho' g. \quad (2.16)$$

For the small-Mach number flows ($|\mathbf{V}| \ll c_s$; c_s - speed of sound), the density perturbation in the vertical momentum equation (2.16) can be substituted by a temperature perturbation:

$$\frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} \approx -\frac{T'}{T_0}, \quad (2.17)$$

where $T_0(z)$ is related to $\rho_0(z)$ and $p_0(z)$ by the equation of state (Equation 2.6). That further simplifies the vertical momentum equation:

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{\rho_0} \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{V} w) = -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial z} + \frac{T'}{T_0} g. \quad (2.18)$$

The buoyancy term can be also formulated in terms of the potential temperature (Equation 2.12):

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{\rho_0} \nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{V} w) = -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial z} + \frac{\Theta'}{\Theta_0} g, \quad (2.19)$$

because

$$\frac{T'}{T_0} \approx \frac{\Theta'}{\Theta_0}.$$

The convective acceleration term in Equation 2.19 can be reformulated for the anelastic flows. Such flows assume that the temporal density variations in the continuity equation are negligible:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_0 \mathbf{V}) = 0, \quad (2.20)$$

where $\rho_0 = \rho_0(z)$ represents the background (anelastic) density profile. Application of Equation 2.20 to 2.19 results in a further simplification of the vertical momentum equation:

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla w = -\frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial z} + \frac{\Theta'}{\Theta_0} g. \quad (2.21)$$

That form of the Euler vertical momentum equation is valid for the low-Mach buoyancy-driven anelastic flows.

2.3.3 The parcel theory

The parcel theory considers the vertical ascent (descent) of a warmer (cooler) air parcel in the surrounding constant-in-time environment. The theory provides an estimate for the updraft (downdraft) speed and for the change of an air parcel internal energy. Thus, the theory allows distinguishing a potentially extreme convective weather situation from other meteorological situations.

The parcel theory assumes the leading role of the buoyancy, B , in the vertical acceleration of an air parcel (Equation 2.21):

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + w \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = \frac{\Theta'}{\Theta_0} g = B. \quad (2.22)$$

The steady state of Equation 2.22 allows obtaining the upper limit for the ascent velocity of the air parcel (i.e., the *thermodynamical* speed limit):

$$\frac{dw^2}{dz} = 2B, \quad (2.23)$$

that is,

$$w^2 = 2 \int B dz \quad (2.24)$$

and

$$w_{max} = \sqrt{2 \int B dz}. \quad (2.25)$$

When the integrated buoyancy term is defined using the density potential temperature (Θ_ρ ; Equation 2.11) the condensing hydrometeors are accounted in the parcel ascent:

$$B = g \frac{\Theta_\rho - \Theta_{\rho,e}}{\Theta_{\rho,e}}, \quad (2.26)$$

where the $\Theta_{\rho,e} = \Theta_{\rho,e}(z)$ denotes the environmental density potential temperature profile. If the pseudo-adiabatic parcel is considered, the virtual potential temperature is used to define buoyancy, that is, the condensate loading is excluded.

The buoyancy integral taken between LFC and EL is known as the CAPE (LFC and EL are defined in Section 2.3.4):

$$\text{CAPE} = \int_{\text{LFC}}^{\text{EL}} B dz. \quad (2.27)$$

Typically,

$$\text{CAPE} = \frac{1}{2} w_{max}^2.$$

The parcel theory assumes that the ascending air parcel is immersed in the hydrostatic environment. Therefore, the parcel pressure p equals the environmental hydro-

static pressure p_e :

$$\frac{dp}{dz} = \frac{dp_e}{dz} = -\rho_e g, \quad (2.28)$$

where ρ_e denotes the environmental air density profile. The parcel pressure adjustment is immediate and realized by a compression or expansion.

Any evolution of the parcel thermodynamical state during the vertical ascent follows the law of thermodynamics:

$$dq = du + pdv \quad (2.29)$$

where dq is the heat exchange rate (equal zero for the adiabatic process), du is the increase of the internal energy, and pdv is the compressing work done by the surrounding environment on the parcel. Since the following thermodynamical relations hold:

$$\begin{aligned} du &= c_v dT, & pv &= RT, \\ v &= 1/\rho, & c_v + R &= c_p, \end{aligned} \quad (2.30)$$

Equation 2.29 can be rewritten to:

$$dq = c_p dT - \frac{1}{\rho} dp, \quad (2.31)$$

where the first term on the right-hand-side is known as the change of specific enthalpy. Differentiation of Equation 2.12 allows rewriting Equation 2.31 to the most compact form:

$$d\Theta = \frac{\Theta}{c_p T} dq \quad (2.32)$$

that states that during an adiabatic process ($dq = 0$) the potential temperature of an air parcel is conserved.

Evolution of a moist parcel thermodynamical state in result of a vertical displacement may induce the water phase transition and release of the latent heat of condensation. The heat exchange rate dq_{cond} is equal to:

$$dq_{cond} = L_h C_d, \quad (2.33)$$

where $L_h = 2.5 \times 10^6 J/kg$ denotes the latent heat of condensation and C_d is the condensation rate.

There exists a temperature-dependent limit of the maximum pressure (saturation pressure e_s) that water vapour can have in its subcritical temperatures. That is, condensation of water vapour occurs when that limit is exceeded. The change of water vapour

Figure 2.17: Graphical visualization of CAPE, CIN, LCL, LFC and EL on a skew-T diagram for the pseudo-adiabatic air parcel rising from the surface. The black and dark blue lines denote the environmental temperature and dewpoint temperature, respectively. The light blue and red lines denote the parcel's temperature evolution during its ascent from the surface.

saturation pressure with temperature is known as the Clausius-Clapeyron law:

$$\frac{de_s}{dT} = \frac{L_h e_s}{R_v T^2}. \quad (2.34)$$

The saturation water vapour mixing ratio (q_{sat}) is the amount of water vapour that the air can hold at the pressure p and temperature T

$$q_{sat} = \frac{\rho_{vapour\ sat}}{\rho_{dry}} = \frac{e_s / (R_v T)}{(p - e_s) / (R_d T)} = \epsilon \frac{e_s}{p - e_s}. \quad (2.35)$$

Since the water vapour constitutes only a fraction of the air mass, the condensing water takes shape of a suspension of minuscule water droplets in the air that is generally known as a cloud.

2.3.4 Convective parameters derived from the parcel theory

The physical interpretation of the basic convective parameters is depicted in the skew-T diagram in Figure 2.17. In the diagram, the solid black and blue lines represent the temperature and the dewpoint temperature soundings (environment), respectively. The X-axis represents the air temperature (i.e., internal energy) and the Y-axis represents the altitude. From that diagram two types of convective indices are deduced. The first type represents characteristic heights for an ascending pseudo-adiabatic parcel such as lifting condensation level (LCL), level of free convection (LFC), and equilibrium

level (EL). The second type represents the release or absorption of energy during the parcel vertical displacement and is denoted by the bounded areas in the diagram such as convective available potential energy (CAPE) and convection inhibition (CIN).

LCL is the altitude at which the air parcel rising from the surface reaches saturation. It is located at the intersection of the dry adiabat that extends from the parcel surface temperature and of the saturation mixing-ratio line (dashed green line in Figure 2.17) that extends from the parcel surface dewpoint temperature. LFC denotes the altitude at which the ascending air parcel becomes positively buoyant (compared to the environment) following the dry adiabat (between the surface and LCL) and the moist pseudo-adiabat (above LCL). EL marks the altitude above LFC where the ascending air parcel becomes again negatively buoyant (usually at or above the tropopause height in the environments supporting deep convection).

CAPE is the amount of energy released by the unit mass of the ascending air parcel between LFC and EL (Equation 2.27). It is proportional to the area bounded by the environmental temperature, moist pseudo-adiabat of the ascending air parcel, and heights of LFC and EL. Since the CAPE release may require an external mechanical work to let the parcel overcome CIN, the availability of CAPE is not the sole factor governing convection development.

CIN equals the amount of energy that needs to be provided to the unit mass of the ascending air parcel to lift it from the surface to LFC (Figure 2.17):

$$\text{CIN} = - \int_0^{\text{LFC}} B dz, \quad (2.36)$$

where buoyancy B is calculated from Equation 2.26 using either the density potential temperature (for adiabatic ascents) or the virtual potential temperature (for pseudo-adiabatic ascents). CIN is proportional to the area bounded by the environmental temperature and the dry adiabat (for altitudes between the surface and LCL) and moist pseudo-adiabat (for altitudes between LCL and LFC) of the ascending parcel.

When the initial parcel potential temperature is estimated from the surface measurement, the convective parameters are conventionally denoted with the prefix SB (i.e., the surface-based), e.g. SB_CAPE. When the potential temperature is estimated from averaging of measurements in the lowest 0.5 km of the environment, the convective parameters are denoted with the prefix ML (i.e., the mixed layer), e.g. ML_CAPE.

2.3.5 Vertical wind shear and the bulk Richardson number

The vertical wind shear (SH) and the bulk Richardson number (BRN) parameters let to distinguish the environments supporting multicell or ordinary cell convection from the environments supporting supercellular convection.

The vertical wind shear over the 0-1 km layer (SH_{01}) above the surface provides

a limited capability to distinguish the environments capable to build tornadic supercells from other environments (Thompson et al., 2003). The shear SH_{01} can be calculated, for example, as the magnitude of the vector difference between the mean wind in the lowest 0.1 km layer and in the 0.9-1.1 km layer:

$$SH_{01} = |\vec{SH}_{01}| = |\vec{V}_{0,0.1 \text{ km}} - \vec{V}_{0.9,1.1 \text{ km}}|. \quad (2.37)$$

Then, the vertical wind shear over the 0-6 km layer (SH_{06}) above the surface provides a capability to distinguish the environments supporting the supercellular convection development (Thompson et al., 2003). The SH_{06} parameter can be calculated, for example, as the magnitude of the vector difference between the mean wind in the lowest 0.5 km layer and in the 5.5-6.5 km layer (averaging usually improves the representativeness of calculated parameters):

$$SH_{06} = |\vec{SH}_{06}| = |\vec{V}_{0,0.5 \text{ km}} - \vec{V}_{5.5,6.5 \text{ km}}| \quad (2.38)$$

If a particular situation and sounding are considered the height limits may be shifted in accordance with the sounding structure.

The BRN parameter is a non-dimensional parameter that measures relation between the vertical wind shear and ML_CAPE. It is calculated following the Moncrieff and Green (1972) and Weisman and Klemp (1982) as:

$$BRN = \frac{ML_CAPE}{0.5\vec{V}_{BRN}^2} \quad (2.39)$$

where \vec{V}_{BRN} approximates the storm-relative wind inflow velocity. That latter parameter is frequently calculated as the vector difference between the density-weighted mean wind over the lowest 6 km layer of the atmosphere (an approximate for the storm motion vector) and the mean wind in the lowest 0.5 km layer (an approximate for the wind across of the convective well-mixed layer). Usually, environments with the BRN less than 45 support the supercellular convection and environments with the BRN above that value support the ordinary or multicellular convection (Thompson et al., 2003).

Chapter 3

Numerical modeling of moist deep convection

3.1 Introduction

Contemporary NWP is based on solving equations describing the natural atmosphere of Earth. These equations consist of: (i) equations of motion, (ii) the gas law, and (iii) the thermal energy equation/the first law of thermodynamics. Except for the gas law, the equations are usually formulated as the partial differential equations (PDE) and have the prognostic form. The equations of motion come from the Navier-Stokes PDEs and usually accommodate a few simplifying assumptions regarding the atmospheric flow characteristics (Thunis and Bornstein, 1996). The main simplifications are associated with the buoyancy (the Boussinesq approximation) and the hydrostaticity (see also Section 2.3.2).

The prognostic equations allow for calculation of the future evolution of the current weather. The accuracy of forecasts is limited, however, and it depends on several factors that include the mathematical properties of the equations and of the numerical solver, the capability of the model and its parameterizations to represent physical behaviour of Earth atmosphere, the quality of initial state and boundary data, and the availability of computational resources. For example, numerical solvers often carry out an approximate inversion of sparse matrices since the exact inversion exceeds available computational resources of the present-day supercomputers.

Several atmospheric processes that feature relatively small spatial scales in comparison to NWP model grid intervals have to be parameterized. Therefore, contemporary NWP models include parameterizations of several small-scale physical processes, including the cloud microphysics (e.g., formation of precipitation), radiative transfer across the atmosphere, turbulence, surface fluxes of energy and momentum, and moist convection. The models also include the soil and sea surface schemes to provide pos-

sibly realistic bottom boundary conditions for the temperature and moisture evolution. Consequently, the contemporary NWP models are the result of a joint effort of many scientists working on dynamical solvers, microphysics, parameterizations, grid generation, heterogeneous weather data assimilation, and efficient I/O subsystems.

Modeling of the moist deep convection began in the second half of 1970s in result of the development of the first 3D numerical cloud models (Clark, 1977, 1979; Klemp and Wilhelmson, 1978; Schlesinger, 1975). At the beginning, the idealized modeling was performed using computational grids with horizontal grid length of the order of 1 km and using rather simple microphysical parameterizations (i.e., excluding ice processes). Such configurations provide a sufficient tool to reproduce principal currents within a squall line or a bow echo (Weisman, 1993). Growth of computational resources allowed running first operational convection-permitting models in the early 21 century (Done et al., 2004). The present-day operational convection-permitting forecasts utilize horizontal grid lengths in the range between 1.0 km and 3.0 km. While for those grid lengths the basic convective currents are likely to be represented (e.g., relatively wide updrafts and downdrafts), the sub-cloud scale motions remain unresolved (Bryan et al., 2003). The convection-permitting resolutions are also far too coarse to resolve explicitly individual cloud and precipitation droplets and their interactions (e.g., autoconversion of cloud water into rain water or accretion of cloud water by rain water). The effects of such processes are calculated approximately by the present-day cloud microphysical schemes (Doms et al., 2011; Kessler, 1969).

Microphysical schemes are the key tool in representing the main cloud microphysical processes occurring in mixed-phase convective clouds and cloud systems (Figure 2.5). The two principal classes of bulk microphysical schemes are the single-moment (1-M) and the double-moment (2-M) schemes. The 1-M schemes assume the constant-in-time droplets concentrations while the 2-M schemes compute the concentrations by solving relevant evolutionary equations. As a result, the 2-M schemes provide a few improvements in representation of microphysical processes, for example, the homogeneous nucleation, size sorting, diffusive growth of ice crystals, aggregation and riming of snowflakes, and inclusion of turbulent effects in calculation of droplets collisions (Seifert and Beheng, 2006).

The rest of this chapter is intended to provide an introduction to the COSMO NWP model (Section 3.2) that is applied in the realistic NWP simulations in Chapters 5 and 6 of this dissertation.

3.2 The COSMO model

The Consortium for Small-scale Modeling (COSMO) model (www.cosmo-model.org; Baldauf et al., 2011) is widely used both for operational forecasting and applied re-

search. The COSMO model solves the fully compressible equations of atmospheric flows in the rotated geographical coordinate system¹:

1. Equations for the wind components:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{du}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial x} + f^v - f_c w + M_u, \\ \frac{dv}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial y} - f u + M_v, \\ \frac{dw}{dt} &= -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p'}{\partial z} + g \frac{\rho_0}{\rho(1+q^x)} \left(\frac{T'}{T} - \frac{T_0 p'}{T p_0} + q_x \right) + f_c w + M_w,\end{aligned}\tag{3.1}$$

where $q^x = \left(\frac{R_v}{R_d} - 1 \right) q^v - q^l - q^f$, $f = 2|\Omega| \sin \phi$, $f_c = 2|\Omega| \cos \phi$, and the M -terms denote the source terms due to the turbulent mixing. Perturbations (primed terms) denote deviations from the time-independent basic state (ρ_0, p_0, T_0) defined as a dry, vertically-stratified atmosphere at rest in the hydrostatic balance. The moist variables in the COSMO model have the sense of specific humidities, that is, the ratio of the mass of water vapour/liquid water/ice water to the total air mass ($q^v/q^l/q^f$).

2. Perturbation equations of energy ($T' = T - T_0$) and pressure ($p' = p - p_0$):

$$\frac{dp'}{dt} = g \rho_0 w - \left(\frac{c_{pd}}{c_{vd}} \right) p D,\tag{3.2}$$

$$\frac{dT'}{dt} = -w \frac{\partial T_0}{\partial z} - \frac{R}{c_{vd}} T D + Q_T,\tag{3.3}$$

where the D -term denotes the three-dimensional wind divergence, and the Q_T term represents the diabatic heating (for an explicit form of these terms see Equations 8.9 and 3.72 in Doms and Baldauf, 2015).

3. Specific humidity equation:

$$\frac{dq^v}{dt} = - \left(S^l + S^f \right) + M_{q^v},\tag{3.4}$$

where the S -terms denote sources of specific humidity related to the liquid or frozen water.

4. Equations for the evolution of various forms of liquid water or ice specific hu-

¹For simplicity the Cartesian version of model equations (Doms and Baldauf, 2015) is presented in this dissertation.

midities:

$$\frac{dq^{l,f}}{dt} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P^{l,f}}{\partial z} = S^l + S^f + M_{q^{l,f}}, \quad (3.5)$$

where $P^{l,f}$ denotes precipitation fluxes of liquid/frozen water.

In the COSMO model the air density ρ is diagnosed from the temperature and pressure via the equation of state:

$$\rho = p (R_d (1 + q^x) T)^{-1}. \quad (3.6)$$

The dynamical solver of the COSMO model is based on the Runge-Kutta split-explicit scheme of Wicker and Skamarock (2002) and utilizes the C-grid discretization of prognostic variables. The prognostic equations are first split into the slow (advection, Coriolis, forcings from the physical processes) and the fast (pressure gradient, buoyancy term, and the so-called working terms in temperature and pressure equations; Baldauf et al. (2011)) components. The slow-varying component of the equations is integrated with a large time step. The fast-varying component is solved with a number of small substeps for fast propagating sound and gravity waves.

The COSMO model features a large set of physical parameterizations (Doms et al., 2011), that is, the Ritter-Geleyn radiative transfer scheme (Ritter and Geleyn, 1992), two alternative turbulence schemes with the common surface flux scheme, the 1-M cloud microphysical scheme with a three-category ice (Reinhardt and Seifert, 2006), the land-surface model (Heise et al., 2003), and the convection parameterization (shallow, mid-level, and deep; Tiedtke, 1989). The Raschendorfer (2001) operational turbulence scheme is based on the 2nd order turbulence closure with the prognostic equation for the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE). It describes the vertical turbulent transport in the atmosphere, including the influence of subgrid-scale condensation. The fully three-dimensional Smagorinsky-Lilly turbulence scheme is available for research in the COSMO model as well (Langhans et al., 2013).

The operational 1-M microphysical scheme of Reinhardt and Seifert (2006) represents an extension of the Kessler warm-rain scheme (Kessler, 1969) to mixed-phase clouds with three forms of ice condensate (cloud ice, snow, and graupel). For research purposes, an accurate 2-M microphysical scheme of Seifert and Beheng (2006) is available in the COSMO model as well (see also Section 3.1, p. 58).

Throughout this dissertation, the realistic simulations employ the COSMO version 5.01.

Chapter 4

The 21 August 2007 severe convective system

4.1 Introduction

The 21 August 2007 severe convective system in the Masurian Lake District (Masurian LD) brought high public attention in Poland. It distinguished itself by severe surface wind gusts up to 35 m s^{-1} that caused extensive damage. In particular, over a dozen of sailing boats sunk and 12 fatalities were recorded in result of high waves induced by the wind on the lakes. Rescue operation covered several lakes between the Śniardwy Lake¹ in the south (S), and the Łabap Lake² in the north (N). The convective system passed over two synoptic weather stations (WST), that is, the Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs. The event prompted installation of a warning system that is now in place in the Lake District.

The first severe weather warning was issued by the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - National Research Institute (IMGW-PIB) at 11:59 UTC³ (IMGW-PIB, 2007). The warning was based on the data from the SAFIR lightning detection system and satellite data since the radar station in Legionowo did not provide weather data to forecasters at that time⁴. The warning concerned convective systems over the Podlaskie Voivodeship that were expected to enter the Warmian-Masurian Voivodeship. The warning stated that these systems may become severe, specified an expected precipitation rate (up to 30 mm hour^{-1}), wind gusts strength ($17\text{-}22 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), and provided

¹Figure 4.1 shows locations of essential geographical points that are used in description of the convective system.

²Around 45 km in latitudinal direction and up to 20 km in meridional direction.

³All hours in this chapter are given in the Universal Time Coordinated (UTC). The acronym UTC is generally omitted throughout this thesis. The local time is Central European Summer Time (CEST), CEST = UTC + 02:00.

⁴Due to transmission failure of an external network provider radar data from Legionowo were not available for forecasters and were lost.

Figure 4.1: Geographical map of NE Poland showing localization of geographical points used in the main text. The solid black line marks borders between the Warmian-Masurian Voivodeship in the N, the Podlaskie Voivodeship in the E, and the Mazowieckie Voivodeship in the center. Source of the background map: Aotearoa User at Polish Wikipedia (CC Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported License).

a hail warning. The warning was labeled as a first (the lowest) level warning in two level gradation. Then, this warning was raised to the highest level at 13:07 UTC, that is, 17 minutes after violent showers were first observed at the Mikołajki WST. The updated warning stated that the severe convective system moving towards north-west (NW) entered Warmian-Masurian Voivodeship from the south-east (SE). The updated warning informed also about the observed precipitation rate (30 mm hour^{-1}) and surface wind gusts magnitude (36 m s^{-1}).

The NWP system in the IMGW-PIB in 2007 was based on the COSMO model with 14.0 km horizontal grid length and on the ALADIN model with 13.5 km horizontal grid length. The effective resolution of these two models is six to seven times coarser, that is, around 80 km. Such a coarse resolution does not allow NWP models to simulate deep convective flows. In such a case convective phenomena are represented indirectly through a convection parameterization scheme. This approach typically performs poorly in highly localized convective precipitation events (Weusthoff et al., 2010). Therefore, the NWP system in the IMGW-PIB was not enough advanced in 2007 to predict development of the system.

This chapter summarizes meteorological observations related to the severe con-

vective system development and the weather conditions preceding the system initiation. The next section presents meteorological description of the weather situation up to the moment of the system formation. That section includes: an overview of synoptic situation (Section 4.2.1), upper-air characteristic of the subtropical air mass (Section 4.2.2), analysis of convective activity in the morning of 21 August (Section 4.2.3), and the surface data-based characteristics of the pre-storm environment (Section 4.2.4). The crossing of the severe convective system over Masurian LD is described in Section 4.3. Analysis of the convective system structure, including radar observations, is given in Section 4.4. Reconstruction and analysis of the most plausible pre-storm upper-air weather conditions over Masurian LD is provided in Section 4.5. The chapter is summarized in Section 4.6.

4.2 Weather situation preceding the severe convective system formation

4.2.1 Overview of synoptic situation

The 500 hPa and 700 hPa upper-air charts for 00:00 21 August 2007 are shown in Figures 4.2 and 4.3, respectively. The analyses depict a pronounced upper-level low located over the western (W) and central Europe and an upper-level ridge located over the central part of European Russia. The low developed from the trough that entered W Europe on the 19 August and spread over W and central Europe since then. The 500 hPa analysis shows that the lowest heights of this isobaric surface within the low were approximately 5560 m Above Mean Sea Level (AMSL; southern France). The 500 hPa height over Poland was between approximately 5660 m (Wrocław) and 5730 m AMSL (Legionowo) at that time. In contrast, the 500 hPa height over the W Russia was between 5840 m and 5880 m AMSL marking the upper-level ridge that was present over this part of Europe for several days before the 21 August. Within the ridge, a cut-off high was observed in the lower troposphere and ABL (700 hPa analysis is shown in Figure 4.3, 850 hPa analysis is not shown). As a result of the horizontal pressure gradient, a S to SE flow within the troposphere was present over Poland at 00:00, and it remained in place over the entire 21 August (Figure 4.5). Therefore, approximately SE winds were registered at 00:00 in Legionowo with speed of about 18 m s^{-1} (500 hPa; Figure 4.5). That upper-air flow promoted an inflow of subtropical air⁵ of Mediterranean origin to the E Poland. Compared to the Kolendowicz (2012) classification of convective conditions, this situation resembles the 7th pattern in that classification.

Surface weather analysis is shown in Figure 4.4. Three distinct mesoscale surface

⁵The naming convention applied in this study does not distinguish between subtropical and tropical air masses, that is, both are denoted as subtropical air masses.

4.2 Weather situation preceding the SCS formation

Figure 4.2: The 500 hPa analysis for Europe (21 August, 00:00). Source: IMGW-PIB.

Figure 4.3: The 700 hPa analysis for Europe (21 August, 00:00). Source: IMGW-PIB.

Figure 4.4: Surface weather analysis of Europe (21 August, 00:00). Source: IMGW-PIB.

lows, located below the upper low, were observed at 00:00 over W and central Europe. Close to the Poland was the low over the Czech Republic with the center located in the N part of that country (minimum mean sea level pressure is 1002 hPa). Two fronts were associated with the low and they marked a border between polar maritime air in the W and modified subtropical air in the E. The warm front extended north from the low center up to the NW Germany and the cold front extended south from the low center across the E Austria up to the Slovenia.

The surface high observed at 00:00 over N part of European Russia (Figure 4.4) was linked with the much larger upper-level ridge over the European Russia. During the 19 and 20 August, a strengthening of that surface high and the upper ridge was observed. The warm front to the S of the surface high marked the border between the polar continental air to the N and the subtropical continental air to the S.

The cold front, associated with the surface low over the Czech Republic, entered the SW Poland after midnight of 21 August (Figure 4.4). The front slowly progressed during that day over the SW Poland and at 12:00 maritime polar air covered the entire Lower Silesia. Simultaneously, in central and E Poland, inflow of the subtropical air from S to SE directions was observed.

Routine surface analysis from 21 August, 00:00 (Figure 4.4) suggests a presence of a frontal system related to a shallow low over Hungary. Additional analyses of surface maps from 20 August (not shown), satellite images (Figure 4.8), and Deutscher

Wetterdienst (DWD) surface maps⁶ show that the low should be considered a transient surface meso-low that developed within the subtropical air mass in an area of extended convective activity (Section 4.2.3). Also, presence of the two fronts is not confirmed by surface analysis maps from 20 August, DWD surface maps, and analysis of upper-air data (Section 4.2.2). The surface analysis suggests presence of different air masses over the N and central Poland, modified polar air and subtropical air, respectively. A comparison of the upper-air sounding from Legionowo (Figure 4.5) with the upper-air soundings from the S coast of the Baltic Sea, Łeba and Greifswald⁷, indicated that at 00:00 21 August both central and northern Poland was covered by the same subtropical air mass, as confirmed by the DWD surface analysis.

4.2.2 Upper-air characteristics

The nearest upper-air sounding station located approximately upwind from Masurian LD (for winds above ABL) was the sounding station in Legionowo, around 120 km to the SW from the area of the convection initiation (CI; Section 4.3.1). Between 12:00 20 August and 00:00 22 August, the station registered the subtropical air mass having the tropopause at around 11.0 to 11.5 km AMSL (Figure 4.5). A sequence of skew-T diagrams in Figure 4.5 shows evolution of the structure of that subtropical air mass over Poland. At 12:00 20 August, the subtropical air mass was already present over Legionowo and winds were weak across the most of ABL and the free troposphere, except near the tropopause (up to 26 m s^{-1} from SSW direction). Then, at 00:00 21 August a significant increase of wind magnitude was observed in the lower and middle troposphere (3 to 7 km AMSL) where SE wind was up to 18 m s^{-1} . Further strengthening of the wind was observed at 12:00 21 August, that is, the observed SE wind was between 18 and 26 m s^{-1} in the layer between 5.5 and 11.8 km AMSL. These changes of wind magnitude resulted from the increase of horizontal geopotential height gradient magnitude.

Several upper-air observations are available upwind (SSW to SE) from the Legionowo station. Figure 4.6 depicts a few of those soundings that were taken in Vienna (20 August, 12:00), Cluj-Napoca, Uzhhorod, and Poprad⁸ (21 August, 00:00). Each of these sounding detected subtropical air mass with the tropopause at around 11.0 km AMSL or higher. The ABL in each of the four soundings contained an elevated residual layer, and the moisture content in the lowest 1.0 km of ABL was quite high. That is, the average water vapour mixing ratio in that layer was between 8.5 g kg^{-1} for Poprad and 11.2 g kg^{-1} for Cluj-Napoca. The soundings indicated presence of a uniform air mass

⁶Available at www1.wetter3.de/Archiv/archiv_dwd.html

⁷Available at weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html

⁸The sounding from Lviv is not shown because its measurements ceased already at 6 km AMSL. That sounding depicts an air mass qualitatively similar to the sounding from Cluj-Napoca.

Figure 4.5: Skew-T diagrams (solid lines) acquired from radiosonde ascents in Legionowo: 12:00 20 August (upper left panel), 00:00 21 August (upper right panel), 12:00 21 August (bottom left panel), and 00:00 22 August bottom right) panel. Dashed light blue and light gray lines denote the reference skew-T diagram from 12:00 21 August (bottom left panel). The diagrams for 12:00 include values of several convective parameters. In those diagrams, dashed red lines denote ML_CAPE release during the moist pseudo-adiabatic parcel ascent.

in the area, without presence of atmospheric fronts, as already discussed.

Prime attention should be paid to the upper-air sounding from Legionowo at noon of 21 August, because the radiosonde ascent started at 11:16 (according to the WST record), that is, nearly at the moment of the CI (Section 4.3.1). That radiosonde reached the tropopause at about 11.5 km height AMSL around 12:00. That sounding provides the upper-air measurement that is the closest to the area of severe convection development.

The sounding from Legionowo shows that around 11:20 a well-mixed convective boundary layer (ML), in contact with radiatively heated ground, extended from the surface (96 m AMSL) to around 890 m height AMSL. Temperature stratification in this layer was almost neutral (25°C at 2-m height; Figure 4.7) and the highest humidity was observed near the surface (57% relative humidity (RH) corresponding to the dewpoint temperature of 15.9°C). The average water vapour mixing ratio in the lowest 1.0 km layer of the ABL was 10.2 g kg⁻¹ and it compared well with the values observed in other upper-air soundings of that subtropical air mass. The ML was capped by around 4°C strong inversion. Above the inversion, an elevated residual layer extended from 1250 m to around 3300 m height AMSL with almost neutral stratification (Figure 4.7). This layer was also quite well mixed for the water vapour content.

The around 3 km thick ABL observed in Legionowo at 12:00 21 August, with its thick elevated residual layer, was a phenomenon registered at several other upper-air sounding stations as well (Vienna at 12:00 20 August, Cluj-Napoca and Uzhhorod at 00:00 21 August; Figure 4.6). A similar thickness of ABL was also observed in Legionowo at 12:00 20 August and at 00:00 22 August (Figure 4.5). Thus, the presence of a 3 km thick and rather complex ABL at noon of 21 August in Legionowo should be considered a common feature of the subtropical air mass that was flowing across central and E Poland on the 20 and 21 August.

The 12:00 21 August Legionowo sounding showed the almost moist-neutral air in the layer between 3300 m and 5100 m height AMSL. High RH was reported in this layer (91-94 %), suggesting presence of altocumulus clouds that were observed at 12:00 at the Mława WST (to the N from Legionowo). Another peak in RH (86 %) was reported around 7400 m height AMSL, suggesting presence of cirrus/cirrostratus clouds also observed at the Mława WST at 12:00. The altocumulus and cirrus/cirrostratus clouds could mark the remnants of the MCS that dissipated earlier that morning over SE Poland (Section 4.2.3; Figure 4.11). The free troposphere observed by that sounding is characterized by a relatively high water vapour content in comparison to the earlier soundings from Legionowo (Figure 4.5). This could also be a result of the vertical moisture transport occurring earlier within the MCS.

The thermal structure of the middle and upper troposphere (500 to 300 hPa) in

Figure 4.6: Skew-T diagrams (solid lines) acquired from radiosonde ascents in: Vienna (20 August, 12:00; upper left panel), Cluj-Napoca (21 August, 00:00; upper right panel), Uzhhorod (21 August, 00:00; bottom left panel), and Poprad (21 August, 00:00; bottom right panel). Dashed red line denotes ML_CAPE release during the moist pseudo-adiabatic parcel ascent. The diagram for Vienna includes values of several convective parameters. In each diagram, the dashed light blue and light gray lines denote the reference skew-T diagram for Legionowo (21 August, 12:00; Figure 4.5, bottom left panel).

Figure 4.7: Potential temperature profile acquired from the sounding in Legionowo (21 August, 12:00).

Legionowo was similar⁹ to the previous day upper air observations from Legionowo (Figure 4.5, upper left) and from Vienna (Figure 4.6, upper left), and to the 00:00 21 August upper-air observations from Cluj-Napoca, Uzhhorod, and Poprad (Figure 4.6, the other panels). As already mentioned, the 500 to 200 hPa layer in Legionowo featured strong winds up to 26 m s^{-1} (around 230 hPa) that were noticeably stronger than winds located below 500 hPa. The tropopause altitude in Legionowo located at around 11.5 km compared well with the tropopause altitude at the other sounding stations, and remained there at approximately the same level over the entire 21 August (Figure 4.5).

Several convective indices (Section 2.3) are calculated for the 12:00 soundings from Legionowo (20 and 21 August; Figure 4.5), and from Vienna (20 August; Figure 4.6). These soundings do not show any extreme CAPE values. For example, in the 21 August Legionowo sounding case the SB_CAPE and ML_CAPE (727 and 447 J kg^{-1}) are moderate and the SB_CIN and ML_CIN (102 and 111 J kg^{-1}) indicate presence of a moderate-to-strong barrier for convective development. Quite similar values of CAPE and CIN were observed within this subtropical air mass on the previous day in Legionowo as well. In the Vienna sounding case, slightly lower CAPE values (508 and 366 J kg^{-1}) and moderate CIN values (42 and 59 J kg^{-1}) were observed at the noon of 20 August. Overall, such CAPE values are not typical for the warm season severe convection development.

On the other hand, the presence of elevated residual layers (ERL) is a factor that favours development of stronger updrafts and more severe convection once convection is initiated (Krikpatrick et al., 2011). That is, the nearly dry adiabatic temperature profile in ERL favours a significant CAPE release in the low- and mid-troposphere.

Analysis of the available upper-air measurements allows concluding that the severe convective system from Masurian LD developed within the subtropical air mass already present on site on 20 August. Available soundings document many similari-

⁹To ease comparisons the skew-T diagram of the Legionowo sounding from 12:00 21 August is outlined with dashed lines at the other skew-T diagrams.

ties in the structure of ABL and free troposphere within the subtropical air mass. In particular, several soundings revealed ABL thickness exceeding 3 km, moderate water vapour content in the ML, presence of ERLs, and the tropopause located at around 11 km height AMSL.

4.2.3 Analysis of convective activity preceding the severe convective system

A significant MCS developed over the N Serbia and E Hungary in the afternoon of 20 August (not shown). The MCS entered SE Poland after 02:00 21 August (Figure 4.8). While moving across the Beskid Niski and Bieszczady Mountains in the SE Poland, the MCS caused moderate precipitation with the intensity ranging between 15 mm hour⁻¹ for the convective cells and 3 mm hour⁻¹ for the surrounding stratiform precipitation areas (radar reflectivity-based estimates). The weather radar in Rzeszów observed MCS' maximum radar reflectivities of around 50 dBZ. Most of the MCS dissipated before 07:00 leaving a few isolated convective cells surrounded by mid- and upper-level clouds. Dissipating cells of the MCS at that time were present over SE Poland in the vicinity of Lublin and Zamość, and in the vicinity of Sandomierz and Kielce. These MCS residuals were observed by weather radars (Figure 4.9) and satellite images (Figures 4.8 and 4.11). The upper-air soundings from 00:00 21 August (Figure 4.6) failed to measure environment of the MCS directly (Figure 4.8, top left). This is because the most active part of the system was located within the gap between the sounding stations in Poprad, Uzhhorod, Cluj-Napoca, and Budapest.

In the morning of 21 August, both Masurian LD and upwind-located neighbourhoods were almost free of deep convection. Some convective activity was observed during that time to the E (e.g., near Suwałki) and to the SW (e.g., near Mława) from Masurian LD, but those systems have not entered Masurian LD (Figure 4.8, SYNOP messages). Consistently, clouds observed over Masurian LD were rather shallow and the cloud cover was ranging between 2 and 5 oktas (Figure 4.15, bottom right).

4.2.4 Surface characteristics of the pre-storm environment

Cooling of the ABL observed during the night in Masurian LD was mostly caused by longwave radiation. Consequently, shallow fogs were observed around 03:00 at the Mikołajki WST and around 06:00 at the Olsztyn WST (SYNOP messages). These fogs indicated a high moisture content in the surface layer over Masurian LD. At 06:00, 2-m dewpoint temperature at the Mikołajki WST was 19.3°C and 2-m temperature was 21.4°C (RH of 88%; Figure 4.15). Similar values were reported in the neighborhoods with the highest values reported at the Ostrołęka WST (20.0°C and 21.6°C, respectively; RH of 91%). Significantly dryer surface layer was observed to the W and E from

4.2 Weather situation preceding the SCS formation

Figure 4.8: Brightness temperature acquired by the MSG SEVIRI detector in $10.8 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength showing weather situation over Central Europe between 00:00 and 08:00 of 21 August. In the 00:00 panel the letters in red denote locations upper-air weather sounding stations: Poprad (P), Budapest (B), Uzhhorod (U), Cluj-Napoca (C), and Vienna (V).

Figure 4.9: Maps showing the maximum of radar reflectivity in a column at 07:00 (left) and 08:20 (right) of 21 August. Radar reflectivity scale is given in the right panel. Source: IMGW-PIB.

Masurian LD at 09:00 (Figure 4.10, upper right panel). It follows that the surface layer over Masurian LD in the early morning was relatively warm and humid. Those observations of very high dewpoint temperatures at the Ostrołęka, Mikołajki, and Kętrzyn WSTs suggest presence of a plume of very humid air in the surface layer over Masurian LD (dotted area in the upper right panel of Figure 4.10; 09:00), which likely extended into the ML as well.

Analyses presented in Sections 4.2.2, 4.2.3 and in this section allow concluding that Masurian LD featured weather conditions favouring development of a significant convective instability in the morning of 21 August that, in turn, could support development of severe convection. Four important factors supported development of the instability: (i) a likely presence of the elevated residual layer (similar to the one observed around Legionowo), (ii) warm and humid air in the ML ensuring release of a significant CAPE, (iii) meteorological conditions allowing for a significant surface insolation, and (iv) relatively warm temperatures of the topmost soil layers (see Figure 5.16, p. 111, in Chapter 5). Such conditions were not present, for example, in Legionowo where ML was significantly less humid and the CAPE values were relatively small, as discussed above.

4.3 Weather situation preceding the SCS formation

Figure 4.10: Temperature (coloured contours) and dewpoint temperature (shading) data obtained from the SYNOP reports (21 August). Dotted areas represent dewpoint temperature observations exceeding 20°C. Hatched areas represent dewpoint temperature observations remaining below 18°C. Figure for 06:00 provides acronyms and locations of WSTs: Bia (Białystok), Elb (Elbląg), Ket (Kętrzyn), Mik (Mikołajki), Min (Mińsk Mazowiecki), Mla (Mława), Olsz (Olsztyn), Ost (Ostrołęka), Sie (Siedlce), Suw (Suwałki), and Ter (Terespol). Figure for 12:00 shows locations of the secondary CI around 11:15 (red crosses).

4.3 Initiation of the severe convective system from 21 August 2007 and system-related weather observations

4.3.1 Initiation of severe convection

The development of severe convection from 21 August is shown in 10.8 μm satellite images in Figure 4.11 (coloured brightness temperature). The first new convective cell developed around 10:00 within the environment hosting the previous MCS residuals to the E of Siedlce¹⁰. At 11:00, two convective clouds having significant horizontal extent were already present within the area of the upcoming convective initiation, these are marked with A and B in Figure 4.11. The cloud A represents a mature deep convective cell with brightness temperature of the cloud top below 220 K. This is not clear in the cloud B case. The cold pool associated with the cloud A was registered at 11:00 at the Siedlce WST (Sie, Figure 4.10). The following convective system started to develop between 11:15 and 11:30. During that time, three new convective cells developed: two cells (marked with numbers 1 and 2 in Figure 4.11) developed to the NE from the convective cell A and one cell developed (marked with number 3 in Figure 4.11) in between of the convective cell A and the cloud B. Cells 1, 2, and 3 likely developed at the edges of cold pools from clouds A and B¹¹. These observations strongly suggest that the severe convective system developed as a result of a secondary convection initiation (secondary CI). In particular, the secondary CI could be related to the forced/mechanical lifting induced by the cold pool of the cell A and potentially B.

At the beginning, the convective system structure was rather unorganized. Unfortunately, because of a quick development of the anvil cloud that overshadowed the convective cells, little is known about the system morphology between 11:30 and 12:20. Due to technical difficulties, the secondary CI was not recorded by the weather radar in Legionowo. Fortunately, the maturing system (starting from around 12:00) was recorded by the weather radar in Gdańsk (Section 4.4.1).

According to the satellite images, the new convective cells grew at the windward (south) side of the local mesoregion uplands¹². The convective cell 3 started to grow at the windward side of Wysoczyzna Kolneńska (up to 90 m height difference). The convective cells 1 and 2 started to grow at the windward side of the NW part of Wysoczyzna Białostocka (up to 70 m height difference). On the basis of available observational data, an unequivocal determination of the role of the uplands dynamical forcing in the con-

¹⁰The convective cells/clouds developing between around 10:00 and 11:00 are in Chapter 6 referred to as the first generation of convective cells/clouds.

¹¹Those cells/clouds are in Chapter 6 referred to as the second generation of convective cells/clouds.

¹²Plains elevated by around 100 m above the lowlands along rivers and swamps.

Figure 4.11: Brightness temperature acquired by MSG SEVIRI detector in $10.8 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength (21 August). The letters A and B denote clouds and the numbers 1 to 3 denote convective cells that developed in result of CI. Source: IMGW-PIB / EUMETSAT.

Figure 4.12: Tropospheric wind hodograph acquired from the radiosonde ascent in Legionowo (21 August, 12:00; m s^{-1}).

vection triggering is not possible.

The region of deep convection development, between Łomża to the west and Białystok to the east, includes two rivers (Narew, Biebrza), swamp lowlands (in both river valleys) and uplands. Those could supported high evaporation rates resulting in a continuous moistening of the pre-storm ML.

4.3.2 Movement of the severe convective system

After initiation, convective cells moved approximately in the NNW direction: the convective cell 3 moved towards Masurian LD, and the other two cells moved towards Pojezierze Ełckie LD (Figure 4.11). At 12:00, the cloud top brightness temperature pattern suggests that the individual anvils merged and formed an extensive anvil cloud. The movement of the system was a consequence of the upper-air wind direction (Figure 4.12) that coincided with a favourably dewpoint temperature distribution in the surface layer (Figure 4.10, upper and middle right panels). In particular, the area of dewpoint temperatures exceeding 20°C (marking a significant latent energy concentration in the near-surface layer) was elongated in the NNW direction. The overlapping of the upper-air wind direction and the spatial distribution of high dewpoint temperatures in the surface layer could create favorable conditions for the development and propagation of the system.

A general overview of the system path and structure is provided by radar composite images. Figure 4.13 depicts movement of the system in approximately NNW direction. Initially the system remains within the SE edge of the radar range (11:30-12:00) but the subsequent images document its crossing over Masurian LD and heading towards the Baltic Sea.

Figure 4.13: Maps of maximum reflectivity value over columns measured by the weather radar in Gdańsk (21 August). The reflectivity scale is provided in the upper right panel. Source: IMGW-PIB.

Figure 4.14: Tropospheric wind hodograph from Figure 4.12 presented in the coordinates moving along with the system. The assumed system movement velocity is given by $U_{storm} = -15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $V_{storm} = 18 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (Section 4.4.1).

The wind hodograph (Figure 4.12) can be converted to the coordinates moving along with the convective system to obtain the relative wind hodograph (Figure 4.14). The system propagation is approximated from radar data (Section 4.4.1). In this frame of reference, winds at all levels up to 10 km altitude AMSL are slower than the system propagation speed so that one cannot determine the system steering level (Section 2.2.3, p. 32). This suggests that the system propagation speed could have been influenced by a RIJ and cold pool dynamics (Section 2.2.3, p. 32). It is also possible that the wind profile over the Masurian LD differed to some degree from the profile observed at Legionowo (see Section 5.5.5, p. 134).

4.3.3 Surface observations related to the crossing of the severe convective system over Masurian LD

The Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs provided records of the 10-m wind direction and magnitude, 2-m temperature, 2-m moisture content, surface pressure, precipitation, and timing related to the passage of the severe convective system.

The system approached the Mikołajki WST at 12:50, that is, at that time when the onset of precipitation was observed at the station. Violent rain showers were observed between 12:50 and 13:10, moderate rain showers were observed between 13:10 and 13:30, and weak rain was observed between 13:30 and 13:50. The hail was observed between 12:58 and 13:01. Decrease in the visibility down to around 100 m was observed in the area of violent showers. Total rainfall recorded at the station between 12:00 and 18:00 was 24.6 mm (only one system was observed in that time period). The system was first observed in a distance at 12:28 when approaching from the ESE direction

Figure 4.15: Hourly meteorological observations collected at the Mikolajki WST (red markers) and Ketrzyn WST (blue markers; 21 August). In case of the Ketrzyn WST an additional wind speed weather record from 13:10 was added.

(WST records). The average 10-m wind speed was 16 m s^{-1} between 12:51 and 13:00. Surface wind gusts up to 35 m s^{-1} were measured between 12:50 and 12:51, wind gusts up to 12 m s^{-1} were measured at 13:01, and wind gusts up to 7 m s^{-1} were measured at 13:21¹³ (WST records).

The increase of wind speed in Mikołajki was accompanied by the change of wind direction from 110° to 160° (Figure 4.15, upper panels). This change was likely a manifestation of the downward momentum transport from higher levels to the surface. The subsequent change in wind direction at 14:00, from 160° to 70° , is likely a result of the cold pool spreading.

According to the weather records from the Mikołajki WST, the system brought a significant change of thermal conditions in the surface layer. In particular, the 2-m temperature reduction from 27.6 to 16.0°C was observed between 12:00 and 13:00 (Figure 4.15) accompanied by the 2-m dewpoint temperature reduction from 20.2 to 15.5°C . For the pseudoequivalent potential temperature¹⁴ (Θ_{pseq}), these values correspond to a reduction from 345.1 K at 12:00 to 320.3 K at 13:00. Surface pressure at the station increased from 994.1 hPa at 12:00 to 997.2 hPa at 13:00 and decreased later to 995.8 hPa (14:00). That change in surface pressure likely indicated passing of the system meso-high.

At the Kętrzyn WST (about 35 km to the NNW from the Mikołajki WST), weak rain was observed between 13:10 and 13:13, between 13:25 and 14:00, and between 14:10 and 14:45. Moderate rain showers were observed between 13:20 and 13:25, and between 14:00 and 14:10. Violent rain showers were observed at the station between 13:13 and 13:20. In contrast to the Mikołajki WST, hail was not observed. Total rainfall recorded at the station between 12:00 and 18:00 was 3.6 mm (only one system was observed during that time period). The system was first observed in a distance at 12:55

¹³These and subsequent maximum wind gusts values were recorded as QNT values (ICAO Coding).

¹⁴ The pseudoequivalent potential temperature (Θ_{pseq}) represents the potential temperature that an air parcel would attain if all its water vapour was condensed during a pseudo-adiabatic ascent and the released heat was used to heat that parcel. The Bolton (1980) formula for Θ_{pseq} reads:

$$\Theta_{pseq} = T_K \left(\frac{p_0}{p} \right)^{R_d / (c_{pd} + q_t c_l)} \times \exp \left(\frac{L_h q_v}{(c_{pd} + q_t c_l) T_L} \right),$$

where the following parameters describe the parcel: $T_K = 273.15^\circ\text{C} + T$ is the absolute temperature, p is the pressure, q_v is the water vapour mixing ratio, $q_t = q_v + q_l$ is the total water mixing ratio, and T_L is the saturation temperature, and the following parameters characterize the thermodynamical system: p_0 is the reference pressure level, R_d is the dry air gas constant, c_{pd} is the specific heat capacity of the dry air at the constant pressure, c_l is the specific heat of liquid water at the constant pressure, and L_h is the latent heat of condensation.

The saturation temperature T_L is approximated as:

$$T_L = \frac{2840}{3.5 \ln T - \ln e - 4.805} + 55,$$

where e denotes the pressure exerted by parcel's water vapour.

Figure 4.16: The vertical cross section of radar reflectivity observations (left), the horizontal reflectivity map with the location of the cross section (center) and the radar reflectivity scale (right) (21 August, 13:00). Source: IMGW-PIB.

as approaching from the SE direction. The average 10-m wind speed was 16 m s^{-1} between 13:11 and 13:20. Surface wind gusts up to 30 m s^{-1} were measured between 13:10 and 13:11, decreasing to about 14 m s^{-1} at 13:21, and 9 m s^{-1} at 14:01 (WST records).

Weather records from the Kętrzyn WST show the 2-m temperature reduction from 26.6 to 17.7°C and dewpoint temperature reduction from 19.7 to 16.4°C between 13:00 and 14:00. These values correspond to Θ_{pseq} reduction from 342.3 K to 324.4 K .

4.4 Evolution of the system structure

4.4.1 Morphological observations obtained by the weather radar in Gdańsk

Due to the distance between Masurian LD and the weather radar in Gdańsk, the following analysis is focused on the system evolution starting from 12:00 and does not include the radial velocity fields. From that time, the system was sufficiently close to the weather radar in Gdańsk to obtain reflectivity images at and above 5 km altitude AMSL (Figures 4.13, 4.16, 4.17, 4.18, and 4.19). The part of the system below that height remained out of the radar line of sight (Figure 4.16).

The convective precipitation region was detected on the edge of the radar range at 12:00 (Figure 4.17). A few convective cells were advected into the radar range and a few others developed within that area between 12:00 and 13:00 (Figure 4.17). During that time, the maximum observed reflectivity values exceeded 50 dBZ (value representative for heavy rain) at 5 km altitude AMSL. The system passed over the Śniardwy Lake between 12:40 and 12:50, and it approached Mikołajki at 12:50, consistently with the WST record.

The convective core of the system at 13:00 consisted of a bow-shaped cluster of convective cells (Figure 4.18). Since the majority of convective cells were aligned in an arch, the system resembled the classical bow echo system developing from initially

Figure 4.17: Radar reflectivity at 5 km altitude AMSL measured by the weather radar in Gdańsk. The black circle marks an approximate weather radar coverage boundary. Dots denote the WSTs in Mikołajki (letter M) and in Kętrzyn (letter K). Gray lines mark terrain elevations of 0.2, 40 and 116 m (the surface elevation of Śniardwy Lake) AMSL. Source: IMGW-PIB.

rather weakly organized convective cells (Section 2.2.4). Formation of the bow echo system lasted 1.5 hour from the moment of the secondary CI which is rather short for a typical situation (Section 2.2.4, p. 39). The maximum observed reflectivity was around 60 dBZ (to the west of Śniardwy Lake, Figure 4.18). Several cells of the system reached the peak reflectivity of at least 45 dBZ¹⁵. System cloud tops were at least at 14 km altitude AMSL (Figure 4.16), that is, they significantly overshoot the tropopause height that was estimated at 11.5 km altitude AMSL by the 12:00 sounding from Legionowo. This implies that the system updrafts were sufficiently strong to break through tropopause and develop overshooting tops penetrating into the lower stratosphere.

The trailing stratiform precipitation region was rather narrow at 13:00 but grew significantly till 14:20 (Figure 4.18). Little is known about its small-scale structure because the relevant reflectivity data are ambiguous due to the radar beam blocking, detectable in Figure 4.18. The system featured also a well developed leading anvil cloud (Figure 4.19). Development of that anvil was likely supported by a moderate jet observed in the upper troposphere (Figure 4.5). At the WSTs, approach of the anvil cloud was not associated with surface-reaching precipitation. For example, the onset of precipitation at Śniardwy Lake occurred about half an hour after the anvil cloud approach (Wojciechowska and Wojciechowski, 2007).

Between 13:00 and 14:20, the convective system passed more than 100 km while moving in approximately the NNW direction (Figure 4.18, Section 4.3.3). The average system propagation speed at 5 km altitude AMSL between 13:00 and 14:20 was around 23 m s^{-1} ($U_{storm} \approx -15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $V_{storm} \approx 18 \text{ m s}^{-1}$; only observations starting from the 5 km altitude AMSL were entirely in the radar line of sight). The system preserved the characteristic bow echo shape during that time period.

The sequence of horizontal radar reflectivity cross sections, Figure 4.18, shows that the system had a few main features frequently encountered in quasi-linear MCS systems, that is, the quasi-linear shape of the highest reflectivities and distinct convective (leading) and stratiform (trailing) precipitation regions. The bow-like radar reflectivity echo of the convective region of the system suggests presence of a strong mid-to-low tropospheric RIJ, a dynamical phenomenon frequently associated with bow echo systems (Section 2.2.4, p. 40). Thus, starting from around 13:00 the system should be classified as a bow echo system.

Around 14:30 the system reached the Sambia Peninsula in the Kaliningrad Region and then it started to move into the Baltic Sea. Over the sea, the bowing segment of the system moved approximately in the NW direction between 15:00 and 16:00 (Figure 4.20). The bowing segment dissipated after 16:00 and some of the remaining convective cells continued moving in the northerly direction. Later, the remaining con-

¹⁵Radar reflectivity value equal 60 dBZ corresponds to moderate hail (precipitation rate of about 200 mm hour^{-1}), reflectivity value equal 45 dBZ corresponds to heavy rain (precipitation rate of about 30 mm hour^{-1}).

Figure 4.18: Radar reflectivity at 5 km altitude AMSL observed by the weather radar in Gdańsk. The black circle marks an approximate weather radar coverage boundary. The elongated reflectivity minima behind the arch of bow echo cells are artificial and result from the radar beam blockage effect. Dots denote the WSTs in Mikołajki (letter M) and in Kętrzyn (letter K). Gray lines mark terrain elevations of 0.2, 40 and 116 m (the surface elevation of Śniardwy Lake) AMSL. Black lines denote bow echo positions at 13:00, 13:20, 13:50 and 14:20. Source: IMGW-PIB.

Figure 4.19: Radar reflectivity at 6 km altitude AMSL observed by the weather radar in Gdańsk (colors) overlaid over satellite image acquired by MSG SEVIRI detector in $7.3 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength (grayscale). Gray lines terrain mark elevations of 40 m and 116 m (the surface elevation of Śniardwy Lake) AMSL. Black circle marks an approximate weather radar coverage boundary. The red crosses mark the approximate locations of the secondary CI around 11:15. Source: IMGW-PIB / EUMETSAT.

vective system acquired a vortical shape suggesting presence of a system-scale vortex. The system dissipated after 20:00 near the Swedish coast of the Baltic Sea.

4.4.2 The system propagation velocity

Based on the radar reflectivity at 5.0 km altitude AMSL (Figure 4.18) the estimated propagation velocities of the system were approximately 27 m s^{-1} between 13:00 and 13:20, 24 m s^{-1} between 13:20 and 13:50, and 21 m s^{-1} between 13:50 and 14:20. These values exceed the ambient winds measured by 12:00 Legionowo sounding at 5.0 and 6.0 km altitude AMSL (16 and 19 m s^{-1} , respectively). The difference of the system propagation speed from the ambient wind was already discussed in Section 4.3.2.

4.4.3 A comment on the convective mode of the system

The analyzed observations indicate that the system had the bow echo structure. Moreover, the radar reflectivity fields suggest absence of long-lived supercellular structures and BWER¹⁶; Figures 4.17 and 4.18), characteristic of supercells. The essential wind shear indices calculated from the Legionowo upper-air sounding (Figures 4.5 and 4.12) are as follows: $\overline{SH}_{0-6} \approx 16 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $\overline{SH}_{0-1} \approx 1.6 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, and the bulk Richardson number $\text{BRN} \approx 142$. According to Thompson et al. (2003) such indices mark an environment hardly supportive for supercells.

¹⁶The BWER is a distinctive supercell feature that is identified in low-to-mid tropospheric radar reflectivity cross sections, and persists over the most of supercell life time (Figure 2.15; Section 2.2.5).

Figure 4.20: Maps depicting maximum radar reflectivities of the system observed by the weather radar in Gdansk between 15:00 and 18:00. The radar reflectivity scale is as in Figure 4.13. Source: IMGW-PIB

4.5 Reconstruction of a likely sounding for Masurian LD

Characteristics of the thermal structure of the atmosphere from the 12:00 Legionowo sounding included a moderate CAPE value and a moderate-to-strong CIN barrier (Figure 4.5) suggesting a low likelihood of the warm season severe convection. In the face of events from 21 August, it is clear that the thermal structure of ML from the Legionowo sounding cannot be considered representative for Masurian LD at noon. It is possible, however, to make an attempt to reconstruct the most likely thermal structure of the pre-storm conditions over Masurian LD around 12:00. For this purpose, one can try merging the upper-air sounding from Legionowo with ML temperature and dewpoint temperature that can be estimated from 2-m measurement taken at 12:00 at the Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs.

A few significant assumptions have to be made to modify the sounding. First, it is assumed that the ABL over Masurian LD featured around 1 km thick ML at noon. Then, it is assumed that the morning growth of that ML, including the ratio of sensible to latent surface heat fluxes (the Bowen ratio), resulted in the vertical gradients of the thermal and moisture profiles across ML alike the ones observed in the 12:00 Legionowo sounding. Also, due to the lack of appropriate data, effects of horizontal advection have to be excluded.

To formulate the temperature and dewpoint temperature profiles for Masurian LD using the Legionowo sounding, that sounding data are first linearly interpolated to the vertical grid with 100 m grid spacing, and the resulting profile is referred to as the original profile. Next, intermediate profiles for ML (0 to 1000 m) are created on that grid. For the intermediate profiles, the surface temperature (dewpoint temperature) is set to the 2-m temperature (dewpoint temperature) measured at the WST. Within ML, the temperature and the dewpoint temperature at levels up to 1000 m of the intermediate profile are set to the values that preserve the temperature and the dewpoint temperature lapse rates of the original profiles. Then, the final temperature and dewpoint temperature profiles are created as a combination of the original profile and the intermediate profile. For the temperature, the final profile is set to the values of the intermediate profile in the 0 to 800 m layer, then as a weighted average of the original and the intermediate profile between 900 to 1000 m height, and the original profile above 1000 m height. For the dewpoint temperature, the weighted averaging of the original and intermediate profiles is applied for the 600 to 800 m layer to avoid overestimation of the total moisture content in ML. Finally, a small adjustment of the temperatures in the 800 to 1100 m layer is applied to ensure the neutral or stable conditions.

As a result of the above procedure, two moist thermodynamical profiles for Masurian LD at 12:00, one for Mikołajki (in the S of Masurian LD) and one for Kętrzyn (in

Figure 4.21: Skew-T diagrams showing composed soundings for Mikołajki (left) and for Kętrzyn (right) for 12:00 of 21 August. The values of several convective parameters are listed in the diagrams.

the N of Masurian LD), are created (Figure 4.21). The profiles indicate that the thermal structure of the atmosphere over Masurian LD could feature a significant convective instability. For example, the expected ML_CAPE for Kętrzyn is 2896 J kg^{-1} and for Mikołajki it is 2962 J kg^{-1} , which are values close to the upper-bound for the most typical conditions for weakly-forced bow echoes over the US (Section 2.2.4, p. 41). Then, the average water vapour mixing ratio for the ML is 12.5 g kg^{-1} for Kętrzyn and 12.7 g kg^{-1} for Mikołajki. The equilibrium level for a quasi-adiabatic parcel is located above the tropopause, consistent with observed development of the troposphere-overshooting tops on 21 August. According to the modified soundings, any immediate release of that energy is inhibited by a rather weak convection inhibition barrier, ML_CIN of about 18 J kg^{-1} for both profiles. To conclude, convective indices for the composed soundings suggest that the pre-storm environment over Masurian LD was vulnerable to the mechanical destabilization and was capable to host a severe bow echo system.

4.6 Summary

This chapter provides description of the severe convective system that passed over Masurian LD on 21 August 2007 and of the weather conditions preceding its initiation. Observational data from various sources were analyzed in order to understand the genesis and evolution of the system.

South to south-east upper-air flow was observed over the central and eastern Poland during more than 24 hours preceding the system development. That flow promoted a continuous inflow of the subtropical Mediterranean air mass to Poland. The ABL

was around 3 km thick and the altitude of tropopause was around 11.5 km AMSL. The S to SE flow on 21 August featured a relatively strong tropospheric winds having the velocity in the mid-troposphere up to 19 m s^{-1} and in the upper troposphere up to 26 m s^{-1} .

Higher 2-m temperatures and dewpoint temperatures were observed at noon of 21 August across Masurian LD than in other parts of NE Poland. A relatively narrow layer of a very warm and humid air was present in the surface layer over Masurian LD that was not observed at the WSTs to the E and W of that area. The surface daytime heating likely strengthened the convective instability. Because of the absence of a sufficient mechanical forcing over Masurian LD, that instability was not released in the late morning. The convective ABL over Masurian LD shortly before the initiation of the system likely was around 3 km thick and likely included the ERL. The combination of the ERL (observed at noon in Legionowo) with the surface temperatures and dewpoint temperatures (observed at noon over Masurian LD) indicated an environment featuring a significant convective instability.

The convective system started to develop around 11:15. Most likely, this was a result of the secondary CI driven by the cold pool outflows that lifted the well mixed layer air. Observations from the Siedlce WST confirmed presence of the cold pool to the S of the secondary CI area. The system structure was initially rather unorganized but it managed to form a bow echo system after around 1.5 hour. Favorable conditions allowing the development of a fast moving convective system were observed downwind from the area of CI, that is, the overlapping of the upper-air wind direction with the spatial distribution of very high dewpoint temperatures in the surface layer.

The system passed two WSTs in Masurian LD. That allowed collecting reliable meteorological data, including evolutions of 10-m wind, 2-m temperature, 2-m moisture, pressure, and precipitation. Direct effects of the downward momentum transfer within the system were observed at the Mikołajki WST, including a significant change in wind direction and a rapid increase of wind gusts magnitude during the system approach. Since the measured maximum 10-m wind gusts speed reached 35 m s^{-1} and the measured average wind speed reached 16 m s^{-1} , the storm provided a vital threat to the safety of people and property.

Analysis of radar reflectivity data shows that starting from around 13:00 the system can be classified as the classical meso- β scale bow echo. The movement velocity of the convective precipitation region was between 21 and 27 m s^{-1} . Most likely, the genesis of severe surface wind gusts observed at Masurian LD was associated with either straight-line or downburst winds. The radar reflectivity data indicated development of overshooting tops penetrating into the lower stratosphere.

Combination of the system nearest upper-air sounding with the WSTs data from Masurian LD allows obtaining likely profiles of temperature and moisture for the Ma-

surian LD at 12:00 of 21 August. They indicate presence of a significant convective instability in combination with a rather weak convection inhibition barrier. Thus, the reconstructed pre-storm environment certainly supported severe convection development and was vulnerable to the mechanical destabilization. Those profiles are also used for the assessment of the modeling setup developed throughout Sections 5.3 to 5.5.4.

Chapter 5

Setup of a modeling framework for studying the severe convective system from 21 August 2007

5.1 Introduction

The meteorological analysis carried out in Chapter 4 documented rapid development of convective cells and their subsequent organization into a bow echo system that passed over Masurian Lake District (Masurian LD) on 21 August 2007. The bow echo system acquired a moderate spatial extent, developed a relatively large anvil cloud, and was capable to generate significant surface wind gusts that caused property damage and loss of life. The NWP models then did not forecast its development in advance. Today, an analysis of that meteorological phenomenon with the help of the COSMO model may facilitate understanding of the key model and data elements that allow a successful forecast of the system. That analysis goes in pair with the statement of Lawson and Jr. (2016) who noted that warm-season bow echoes are rather poorly forecasted by convection-permitting systems in comparison to other types of convection. If successful, current study may widen understanding of genesis of bow echo systems development in the Central-Eastern Europe.

To realize this goal, a multi-step numerical modeling study of the weather situation from 21 August is performed and documented. First part of the study, presented in this chapter, covers the development of the appropriate modeling framework. That includes choice of the optimum initial and boundary conditions (ICs and BCs) for numerical simulations and modifications of ABL and free tropospheric model data (in accordance with available weather observations from 21 August). A few potential improvements for NWP forecasts over Poland during the warm-season convective weather come out from that study as well.

Throughout this study, numerical simulations are carried out with the COSMO model in a semi-operational setup. Numerical simulations utilize computational grids with the horizontal grid interval of either 7.0 km (C-7) or 2.2 km (C-2). Most of the experiments carried out apply the higher quality ICs than in Wójcik (2017) and Wójcik et al. (2019). Therefore, simpler model data modifications are applied here.

This study begins with a selection of the optimal ICs and BCs for the convection-permitting numerical simulations. The selection considers two C-7 convection-parameterizing simulations with ICs and BCs originating from either the GME global model or the ERA-5 reanalysis dataset (IFS global model). The superior simulation (ERA-5-based) is selected for further studies. Subsequent experiments (with ICs and BCs derived from the ERA-5 dataset) are aimed to improve model representation of environmental conditions in the area of the bow echo development. They can be divided into two main groups. The first group aims to ensure close-to-realistic profiles of moisture and temperature across the well-mixed convective boundary layer (ML) leading to the realistic CAPE and CIN representations (Sections 5.5.1, 5.5.2, 5.5.3, and 5.5.4). This is because warm-season bow echoes are known to develop in areas of a significant CAPE (Section 2.2.4). Those experiments include the assimilation of soil temperatures, switch from the coarser horizontal grid (C-7) to the finer one (C-2), nudging of SYNOP messages (10-m wind, surface pressure, and 2-m moisture), and modification of the surface heat fluxes and the Bowen ratio. The second group considers adjustments of the horizontal temperature gradients across the lower and middle troposphere (900-520 hPa) and aims to reconstruct a more realistic wind shear within these layers (Sections 5.5.3 and 5.5.5, Wójcik et al., 2019). This is because bow echoes frequently develop in environments with a moderate or large wind shear (Section 2.2.4). Those experiments include the nudging of surface pressure observations from SYNOP messages and an adjustment of the ICs for temperature. The experiments with the assimilation of soil temperatures and adjustment of the temperature IC are carried out using C-7 simulations. That allows assimilating soil temperatures measured before 00:00 UTC¹ 21 August and adjustment of the IC for temperature across areas located at lateral edges of the C-2 domain. The other experiments are carried out within the C-2 simulations.

This chapter includes 4 more sections. Section 5.2 describes models setups and computational domains. Section 5.3 presents main differences between convection-parameterizing simulations driven by the ERA-5 dataset and the GME model (E-7 and G-7 simulations, respectively). Section 5.4 describes weather evolution modelled in the E-7 simulation and discusses flaws of that simulation. Section 5.5 documents steps to improve model representation of environmental conditions in the area of the bow echo system development.

¹Time in this chapter is given in UTC as in the previous chapter. The acronym UTC is generally omitted throughout this thesis.

Figure 5.1: The C-7 and C-2 computational domains (the orographic map covers the C-7 domain; meters).

5.2 General setup of simulations

5.2.1 The COSMO-7 setup

The COSMO-7 (C-7) simulations start at 00:00 21 August, around 13 hours prior to the occurrence of the severe system. Model integration time step is 30 seconds. The essential parameterizations for that resolution are turned on (for references see Section 3.2, p. 60): the 1-M cloud microphysics (with cloud ice and precipitating snow), radiative transfer (updated every 15 minutes), operational COSMO turbulence scheme (with advection of TKE), multi-level soil model, and convection parameterization (shallow and deep). The soil model has 10 levels between 0.005 m and 14.58 m below the surface. The soil model initialization is based on either GME or ERA-5 data, and does not include data assimilation.

The C-7 domain covers a large fraction of Europe (Figure 5.1). The C-7 domain size is 310 x 310 grid points (2170 km x 2170 km; $dx=7.0$ km), with 12 points wide lateral absorbers. The computational grid employs 60 vertical levels (hybrid terrain-following coordinates) between the surface and 22.7 km height AMSL. Simulations in the C-7 domain use ICs and BCs interpolated from either GME model (G-7) or the ERA-5 reanalysis (E-7).

5.2.2 The COSMO-2 setup

The COSMO-2 (C-2) convection-permitting simulations start at 00:00 21 August as well. Model integration time step is 20 seconds. The essential physical parameterizations are the 1-M cloud microphysics (with cloud ice, precipitating snow and graupel), radiative transfer (updated every 6 minutes), operational COSMO turbulence scheme (with TKE advection), and multi-level soil model (10 levels; initialized from the C-7 simulation output). The shallow and deep convection parameterization are turned off.

The C-2 horizontal domain is 500 x 560 grid points (1100x1232 km; $dx=2.2$ km), with 18 points wide lateral absorber. That domain is centered over Central-Eastern Poland and covers entire Poland and some areas located upwind and downwind from Poland on that day (Figure 5.1). BCs for the C-2 simulations are updated every 30 minutes.

5.3 Review of the coarse-scale COSMO-7 semi-operational simulations

5.3.1 The G-7 simulation

The GME model provides ICs and BCs derived from global operational forecasts with the average horizontal grid length of 40 km (in 2007) and a rather basic data assimilation scheme (optimum interpolation; Majewski et al., 2002). Data from that model (provided by DWD) serve as the source of ICs and BCs for the COSMO-7 convection-parameterizing simulation. A short comparison of the G-7 simulation with key observational data is provided in this section to evaluate whether this simulation provides a sufficiently accurate and promising source of ICs and BCs for convection-permitting simulations.

Figure 5.2 depicts 500 hPa surface height, liquid and ice water path, and 850 hPa precipitation field between 00:00 and 15:00 of 21 August. The liquid and ice water path discriminates areas with little clouds (below 0.05 kg m^{-2}), with relatively shallow clouds (between 0.05 and 0.5 kg m^{-2}), and with relatively thick clouds or areas filled with significant precipitation (above 0.5 kg m^{-2}). This product is also used for qualitative comparisons of simulated cloud distributions with the satellite observations of the cloud cover (CC) from 21 August. The low-level precipitation is depicted by the pseudo-radar reflectivity contours for 850 hPa which allows documenting the instantaneous distribution of precipitation. The figure indicates that already at 00:00 the horizontal distribution of CC and precipitation differs from the satellite observations (Figure 4.8, Section 4.2.3). The G-7 forecast significantly overestimates the area of clear-sky conditions over Poland (for almost the entire country) and fails to represent

widespread convective activity occurring after midnight. In particular, the cloud cluster entering SE Poland from the S direction after midnight is completely missed in the G-7 forecast. At 06:00, the G-7 simulation develops significant CC and convection over NW and NE Poland which is not seen in the satellite observations. Furthermore, the convective clusters over SE and central Poland are absent in the G-7 forecast at 06:00.

Significant upper-air advection of spurious clouds and cloud dissipation after 06:00 in G-7 simulation reproduce quite well the almost clear-sky conditions over NE Poland around 09:00 (Figures 5.2 and 4.11). ML representation over NE Poland in the G-7 simulation remains noticeably biased for the morning (06:00-12:00) 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature, significant physical parameters characterizing moist thermal conditions near the bottom of ML. Figure 5.3 compares forecasted and observed 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature at the synoptic WSTs in Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olsztyn (Masurian LD) and at the WST in Siedlce (to the S from Masurian LD). The figure depicts negative morning-to-noon temperature biases for Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs, and negative dewpoint temperature biases for Siedlce, Mikołajki and Olsztyn WSTs. Those deficits of temperature and moisture in ML lead to the underestimation of the simulated CAPE around noon over Masurian LD. When compared to the observation-based estimation (Section 4.5), the deficit of ML_CAPE for the Mikołajki WST is found to be significant (around 1500 J kg^{-1} ; Figures 4.21 and 5.4).

Figure 5.5 compares upper-air temperatures and dewpoint temperatures in the G-7 simulation with the 12:00 Legionowo sounding (Figure 4.5, bottom left; located to the SW from Masurian LD) and shows the simulated upper-air horizontal wind profile as well. The simulated temperatures are overestimated across ML and the low-to-mid troposphere (below around 550 hPa), The simulated horizontal winds are weaker than observed across most of the troposphere (deficit of around 5 m s^{-1}). The simulated dewpoint temperatures are quite well represented between the surface and 850 hPa, but become strongly underestimated between 850 hPa and mid-troposphere.

5.3.2 The E-7 simulation

The ERA-5 reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) applies the IFS model configured for climate reanalysis. The reanalysis has the average horizontal grid length of 31 km, around two times finer vertical grid density than the GME data, and three times higher BCs update frequency (1 hour vs 3 hours). The data assimilation scheme for ERA-5 applies 4-Dimensional Variational Data Assimilation with ensemble-based background uncertainty estimation and covers a wide range of weather observations. Because ERA-5 provides very realistic reanalysis dataset, this section considers the COSMO-7 convection-parameterizing simulation with ICs and BCs originating from that dataset.

Figure 5.6 depicts 500 hPa surface height, liquid and ice water path, and 850 hPa precipitation field in the E-7 simulation between 00:00 and 15:00 of 21 August. At

Figure 5.2: Liquid and ice water path (blue-color scale; kg m^{-2}), height of 500 hPa (copper-color scale; meters), and radar reflectivity at 850 hPa (violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, and red 55 dBZ) in the G-7 simulation (compare Section 5.3.1 for description of these parameters). Capital letters denote locations of Legionowo (L), and Mikołajki (M).

Figure 5.3: Evolution of the 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature measured at selected WSTs (black) and simulated by G-7 (red). Horizontal averaging was applied over grid points remaining in the distance up to 10.0 km from each WST. Root mean square differences (RMSD) for the 00:00-12:00 and 00:00-17:00 periods are indicated for each plot (for the ideal forecast the RMSD would equal 0). The 00:00-12:00 RMSDs from the main simulations in this chapter are also collected in Table 5.1.

Figure 5.4: Map depicting ML_CAPE (left; J kg^{-1}) and ML_CIN (right; J kg^{-1}) at 12:00 in the G-7 simulation.

Figure 5.5: Skew-T diagram depicting upper-air conditions for Legionowo at 12:00 in the G-7 simulation (solid lines and wind arrows). Model data was obtained by horizontal averaging over grid points remaining in the distance up to 10.0 km from Legionowo. The reference (observed Legionowo sounding) is depicted with dashed lines.

00:00, the simulation reproduces the convective cloud cluster entering SE Poland after midnight from the S direction with a moderate shift in the N direction (up to 100 km) and with significantly underestimated intensity of convective precipitation. Over the central and NW Poland, the ICs underestimate CC and likely convective precipitation when compared to the satellite image in Figure 4.8. Despite of that, the ICs reproduce the initial 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature over central and NE Poland reasonably well (shown for selected NE Poland weather stations in Figure 5.7). In particular, this is a significant improvement over the ICs from the GME forecast because the latter features larger temperature and dewpoint temperature biases over the NE Poland (Figure 5.3).

At 06:00, the E-7 simulation overestimates CC over NE Poland and underestimates CC over SE Poland (Figure 5.6). No simulated precipitation is seen over NE Poland at that time, in agreement with satellite observation (Figure 4.8) and a noticeable advantage in comparison to the G-7 simulation. Between 06:00 and 09:00, the simulated CC over central and NE Poland decreases to the level similar to the one observed in the satellite images (Figure 4.11). Thus, the approximately clear-sky forecast for NE Poland around 09:00 can be considered as a quite accurate one. Nevertheless, the morning evolution of 2-m temperature over NE Poland features a negative bias (Figure 5.7) while the 2-m dewpoint temperature evolution features errors with varying sign. The maximum forecasted 2-m dewpoint temperatures reach 20°C (Siedlce and Kętrzyn) that is comparable to the pre-storm observations from the morning of 21 August (20.0°C for the Ostrołęka WST and 19.3°C for the Mikołajki WST; Section 4.2.4). In comparison to the G-7 simulation, the 2-m temperature root mean square differences (RMSD) for the period 00:00-12:00 (morning) are significantly reduced for the Siedlce and Olsztyn WSTs while they remain quite similar for the Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs. Also, the morning RMSD statistics for the 2-m dewpoint temperature indicate either a slight (Siedlce WST) or a significant improvement (Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olsztyn WSTs) with respect to the G-7 simulation. The better statistics of the E-7 simulation result in ML_CAPE forecast for Masurian LD ranging between 1600 and 2300 J kg⁻¹ (Figure 5.8), that is, the deficit of ML_CAPE is of around 1000 J kg⁻¹, significantly lower than in the G-7 simulation (see Section 4.5).

Figure 5.9 (bottom left) compares the upper-air temperatures and dewpoint temperatures in the E-7 simulation with the 12:00 Legionowo sounding and depicts the simulated upper-air horizontal wind profile. In comparison to the G-7 simulation, the dewpoint temperature error is slightly larger and the temperature error is similar, but it is lower within ML. The horizontal wind profile error is qualitatively similar.

Although both G-7 and E-7 simulations miss to represent the onset of severe convection over Masurian LD, the E-7 simulation seems better. The advantages of E-7 simulation include the higher quality of ICs (CC over Poland, initial 2-m temperature

Figure 5.6: Liquid and ice water path (blue-color scale; kg m^{-2}), height of 500 hPa (copper-color scale; meters), and radar reflectivity at 850 hPa (violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, and red 55 dBZ) in the E-7 simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Legionowo (L) and Mikołajki (M).

Figure 5.7: Like Figure 5.3 but for the E-7 simulation.

Figure 5.8: Map depicting ML_CAPE (left; $J kg^{-1}$) and ML_CIN (right; $J kg^{-1}$) at 12:00 in the E-7 simulation.

Figure 5.9: Skew-T diagrams depicting upper-air conditions in the E-7 simulation (solid lines and wind arrows) in Legionowo (12:00, left) and Mikołajki (right, 13:00). Model data was obtained by horizontal averaging over grid points data remaining in the distance up to 10.0 km from the each location. Dashed lines represent the observed sounding from Legionowo.

and dewpoint temperature over Masurian LD), and evolution of these parameters between 00:00 and 12:00 better approximating the observations. For that reason, the E-7 simulation is selected for the further study.

5.4 Characterization of the weather evolution modelled in the E-7 simulation

Spatial distributions of the air masses and geostrophic wind fields in the E-7 simulation (Figure 5.10, top and middle rows) reproduce quite accurately the synoptic situation from 21 August 2007 (discussed in Section 4.2.1). In particular, over the E and central Poland, the S to SSW mean mid-tropospheric winds prevail (isolines of 500 hPa surface height, Figure 5.6) and the inflowing air mass clearly represents the subtropical Mediterranean origin (Figure 5.9).

An important feature of the simulated flow is a convergence area (CA) within the upper flow reaching Masurian LD around 13:00 (shown by a trajectory analysis, Figure 5.12). In CA, the subtropical air flowing from the E Slovakia and NE Hungary (crossing the Carpathian Mountains) meets even warmer air flowing from the SW Ukraine, moving along the E side of the Carpathian Mountains. Presence of weak temperature gradients across CA is documented by the average temperatures of air parcels reaching Masurian LD (e.g., 850 and 650 hPa; Figure 5.12). Those gradients are also reproduced by the E-7 simulation-derived 00:00 Shepetivka sounding (that represents air mass on the E side of CA) and 12:00 Legionowo sounding (that

Figure 5.10: Map depicting thickness of the isobaric layer between 850 and 500 hPa at 00:00 and 13:00 (top row; meters), wind magnitude at the 850 (middle left) and 700 hPa (middle right) isosurfaces, and wind shear between 850 and 500 hPa isosurfaces (bottom left; colors and arrows) and between 950 and 700 hPa (bottom right) in the E-7 simulation. Capital letters in the thickness maps denote locations of Mikołajki (M), Legionowo (L), and Shepetivka (S).

Figure 5.11: Skew-T diagram showing upper-air conditions in Shepetivka derived from the ICs for E-7 simulation (00:00; solid lines and wind arrows). Dashed lines depict the observed sounding from that site.

represents air mass on the W side of CA). However, those soundings suggest that the simulation-derived gradients may not be as large as implied by the radiosonde observations (Figures 5.9 and 5.11, the solid and dashed lines denote the simulation-derived and radiosonde data, respectively). The convergence of the southerly flow occurs within 850 to 550 hPa. Above 500 hPa the air temperatures are similar across the air mass (Figures 5.9 and 5.11, skew-T diagrams for Shepetivka 00:00, Legionowo 12:00, and Mikołajki 12:00).

Severe moist convection is absent in E-7 over Masurian LD both at the time of the bow echo development (12:00-13:00) and in the afternoon (15:00; Figure 5.6). Despite that, after 13:00, a local increase of CC over Masurian LD is seen in the area of decreased CIN and increased CAPE (Figure 5.8), suggesting parameterized convective activity.

The lack of significant convective activity may be related to the apparent negative model biases in the representation of 2-m temperature and 2-m dewpoint temperature evolutions over Masurian LD and their impact on CAPE (Figure 5.7). Several factors can play role in the maintenance of those biases. For example: an underestimated insolation of NE Poland in the morning of 21 August, biased representation of soil temperatures in the E-7 simulation influencing the surface energy balance (Figure 5.14 depicts around 1.5-2°C negative soil temperature bias), advection of too cold and/or too dry air into the ML over Masurian LD (Figure 5.12, top row), and inaccurate distribution of the moist air plume over NE Poland (shifted eastwards at 12:00; Figures 5.13 and 4.10). These factors are discussed throughout Section 5.5.

Figure 5.12: Backward trajectories arriving at 13:00 to Masurian LD in the E-7 simulation. The pressure level defining location of each parcel at its arrival point is shown in the upper-right corner of each plot. Colouring of trajectories represents temperature evolution along parcels trajectories (color scale is located below each plot; °C). The map colouring represents orography (scale located to the right of each row). Capital letters denote Mikołajki (M) and the relevant sounding stations providing the 00:00 21 August soundings: Budapest (B), Cluj-Napoca (C), Legionowo (L), Lviv (Lv), Shepetivka (S), Poprad (P), Szeged (Sz), and Uzhhorod (U).

Figure 5.13: Map of NE Poland depicting evolution of the dewpoint temperature (colors; °C) and wind at 200 m height AMSL (arrows) in the E-7 simulation. Map for 09:00 shows localizations of the main WSTs mentioned in the chapter: Białystok (B), Elbląg (E), Kętrzyn (K), Legionowo (L), Mikołajki (M), Mława (Mi), Olsztyn (Ol), Ostrołęka (Os; provides data with 3 hour time step only), Siedlce (Si), Suwałki (Su), and Warszawa-Okęcie (W-O).

Figure 5.14: Comparison between soil temperatures at the 0.20 m (dots) and 0.50 m (crosses) levels measured at selected WSTs (black) and model-simulated (red; E-7 simulation).

5.5 Improvement of boundary layer and free tropospheric air characteristics

The E-7 simulation is unable to reproduce accurately the morning ML characteristics (2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature) observed over Masurian LD on 21 August 2007. Furthermore, the model-derived 00:00 Shepetivka sounding and 12:00 Legionowo sounding suggest that E-7 underestimates the magnitude of upper-air temperature gradients across the E Poland. Similarly, a counterpart convection-permitting COSMO-2 simulation (with ICs and BCs derived directly from the E-7 simulation) is unable to reproduce those weather conditions as well (not shown). Therefore, this section is intended to correct the ML and free tropospheric air characteristics, following the strategy described in the Introduction (Section 5.1). The improved setup will be incrementally built upon the E-7 setup.

5.5.1 Adjustment of the soil model temperatures and the lakes surface temperatures

The soil model temperatures adjustment aims to correct the surface energy balance to reduce the 2-m temperature bias observed over Masurian LD in the E-7 simulation (Figure 5.14). Implementation of the adjustment is based on the nudging of soil temperature observations within the topmost soil model levels, that is, the levels exhibiting the diurnal cycle of temperature (0.005 m, 0.0167 m, 0.05 m, 0.10 m, and 0.20 m deep) and the first level exhibiting the seasonal temperature dependence (0.50 m deep).

Relaxation of the model soil temperatures is carried out in a restricted area of the computational domain and the Cressman (1959) objective analysis method is utilized to derive the analysis field for the relaxation. That analysis method corrects the gridded model soil temperature fields towards the observations in the area limited by geographical distance to the observations locations. The analysis can have one or more iterations that subsequently differ by the decreasing radius of influence assigned to the observations. Magnitude of the radius reflects the maximum distance from the observation location at which that observation has an influence on the analyzed grid point value. If a grid point remains within one iteration under the influence of more than a one observation, a weighting function allows obtaining a balanced correction of that point value. The weighting function is defined as in the Cressman (1959).

The corrected analysis field is constructed using the soil temperature observations from the Polish WSTs. In practice, observations from 12 stations located in the NE and E Poland are used: Mikołajki, Siedlce, Olsztyn, Białystok, Terespol, Mława, Elbląg, Suwałki, Warszawa-Okęcie, Koziernice, Włodawa, and Lublin WST. Two Cressman's iterations are used with the radii of influence equal $R_1 = 160$ km in the first iteration and

Figure 5.15: Map depicting locations of WSTs providing soil temperature observations (black dots). The circles mark the inner circles of influence (radius equal 80 km) in the Cressman's objective analysis of soil temperatures.

$R_2 = 80$ km (Figure 5.15; localizations of the most of WSTs are marked in Figure 5.13) in the second iteration. Soil temperature observations at the 0.05 m below the ground (at 00:00, 06:00, 12:00, and 18:00) are used for the 0.005 m, 0.0167 m, and 0.05 m model levels. Soil temperature observations at the 0.10 m, 0.20 m, and 0.50 m levels (at 06:00, 12:00, and 18:00) are used for the corresponding model levels. The nudging window starts 3 hours before the standard soil temperature observation times and finishes 1 hour after that time, and the nudging time scale is 60 minutes.

The adjustment of the E-7 simulation is run in two steps. An auxiliary E-7 simulation is calculated in the first step with soil temperatures nudging starting at 00:00 20 August (i.e., one day earlier). That simulation provides improved soil temperature ICs for the main simulation that starts at 00:00 of 21 August (E-7-Soil). The E-7-Soil simulation also includes the surface temperature adjustment for the lakes (discussed in the next paragraph). In that simulation, the soil temperature nudging lasts till 13:00 of 21 August.

Lakes' surface temperature is adjusted for the lakes located between 19° and 25°E and 52° and 55°N. The temperature measured around 08:00 21 August at the Jezioro Mikołajskie Lake (21.6°C) defines the lakes surface temperature in that area during the entire E-7-Soil simulation time. High heat capacity of water justifies the constant temperature approach in short-term simulations.²

Figure 5.16 shows that soil temperatures evolution over NE Poland in the E-7-Soil simulation is improved when compared to E-7 (Figure 5.14). That improvement

²The COSMO lake parameterization scheme of Mironov (2008) is technically not applicable for this study because it requires a few weeks of simulation to spin-up.

Figure 5.16: Comparisons between soil temperatures at the 0.20 m (dots) and 0.50 m (crosses) levels observed at selected weather stations (black) and model-simulated (red; E-7-Soil simulation).

has a significant positive impact on the 2-m temperature evolution (decreased morning RMSD for the Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olsztyn WSTs) and a small positive impact on the 2-m dewpoint temperature evolution (decreased morning RMSD for the Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olsztyn WSTs; Figure 5.17). In the surface layer (bottom 10% of ML), a slight increase of dewpoint temperature is observed across the NE Poland compared to the E-7 simulation (Figures 5.18 and 5.13 respectively). That local increase is limited to around 0.5°C . The large-scale flow in the free troposphere remains virtually the same as in the E-7 simulation (not shown).

5.5.2 Switch to the convection-permitting setup

The first convection-permitting simulation, E-2-Soil, utilizes ICs and BCs derived from the E-7-Soil simulation and the appropriate model setup (Section 5.2.2). One expects that this change will allow more accurate modelling of convection initiation and subsequent convective evolution.

There are many similarities between flow fields in the E-2-Soil and E-7-Soil simulations. In particular, the low- and mid-tropospheric horizontal flow and temperature distributions remain quite similar in both simulations although the E-2-Soil simulation exhibits more small-scale features (compare Figures 5.10 and 5.19). Humidity across the surface layer is slightly higher as the E-2-Soil simulation produces rather higher humidity across the NE Poland in the morning and at noon (compare Figures 5.18 and 5.21). For the E-2-Soil simulation, the majority of the morning 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature RMSD slightly increases (compare Figures 5.17 and 5.20) although a noticeable decrease is still visible with respect to the E-7 simulation. Further improvement of the 2-m RMSDs and upper-air wind and temperature fields will be obtained through the nudging of surface observations (Section 5.5.3).

Figure 5.17: Like Figure 5.3 but for the E-7-Soil simulation.

Figure 5.18: Map of NE Poland depicting evolution of the dewpoint temperature (colors; °C) and wind field (arrows) at 200 m height AMSL in the E-7-Soil simulation. Typical surface elevations in that area range between 80 and 200 m height AMSL. Capital letters denote locations of Mikołajki (M) and Legionowo (L).

5.5.3 Nudging of surface observations

Application of surface data assimilation is intended to improve model representation of ABL thermodynamical characteristics, to correct model representation of tropospheric horizontal temperature gradients and wind shear magnitude, and to correct model representation of wind field within the ABL. Those potential benefits are associated with assimilation of the 2-m dewpoint temperature, surface pressure, and 10-m wind observations. The subsequent discussion of the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation focuses on improvements related to the ABL thermodynamical representation and to the low-to-mid tropospheric geostrophic wind representation.

The COSMO operational nudging scheme is used for the assimilation. The nudging utilizes observational data from the SYNOP messages collected between 00:00 and 08:00 of 21 August. That dataset covers messages from the main WSTs in Poland (77 stations, SYNOPs from majority of those stations are available every hour) and WSTs in other countries within the area of the C-2 domain (225 stations, SYNOPs from majority of those stations are available every 3 hours). Spatial distribution of the WSTs (Figure 5.22) is not uniform. In particular, a low WSTs density is present in E Poland, in the W Belarus, and in the NW Ukraine³. For operational applications, the horizontal spreading of observation increments follows an exponential function having the average horizontal scale equal to 70 km. The vertical spreading of observation increments is of a few tens of meters for the 2-m dewpoint temperature, a few hundreds of meters for

³The relatively low availability of surface weather reports from the Ukraine (under the auspices of WMO) is a known issue deteriorating quality of NWP modelling (ECMWF, 2018).

5.5 Improvement of boundary layer and free tropospheric air characteristics

Figure 5.19: Map depicting the thickness of the 850 to 500 hPa isobaric layer at 00:00 and 13:00 (top row, meters), wind magnitude at 850 (middle left) and 700 hPa isosurfaces (middle right), and wind shear between 850 and 500 hPa isosurfaces (bottom left) and between 950 and 700 hPa isosurfaces (bottom right) in the E-2-Soil simulation. Capital letters in the thickness maps denote locations of Mikołajki (M), Legionowo (L), and Shepetivka (S).

Figure 5.20: Like Figure 5.3 but for the E-2-Soil simulation.

Figure 5.21: Map of NE Poland depicting evolution of the dewpoint temperature (colors; °C) and horizontal wind (arrows) at 200 m height AMSL in the E-2-Soil simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Mikołajki (M) and Legionowo (L).

Figure 5.22: Orographic map (C-2 domain) depicting WSTs delivering SYNOP messages for data assimilation in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation (black dots).

the 10-m wind, and a few kilometers for the temperature (temperature increments are derived from pressure increments and applied between the surface and 400 hPa; Hess and Schraff, 2012).

Table 5.1 summarizes the morning (00:00-12:00) 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature RMSDs calculated for the forecasts (all the main simulations discussed in this Chapter) using the weather observations from the stations located within Masurian LD (Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olsztyn WSTs) and the Siedlce WST that registered the cold pool at 11:00 on 21 August. The table indicates that the nudging results in a systematic decrease of RMSDs for Siedlce, Mikołajki, and Kętrzyn (E-2-Soil-Ndg and E-2-Soil forecasts). A comparison of Figures 5.20 and 5.23 shows additionally that the

Table 5.1: Temperature and dewpoint temperature root mean square differences (RMSD) from observations in the period 00:00-12:00 (R_{0-12} ; left and right column for each WST respectively). The R_{0-12} compares the WSTs observations with forecasts given by the main simulations discussed in Chapter 5. For locations of WSTs refer to Figure 5.13.

Simulation	Siedlce		Mikołajki		Kętrzyn		Olsztyn	
G-7	2.92	1.30	1.47	1.41	2.47	1.33	1.98	1.96
E-7	1.74	1.21	1.66	0.97	2.60	1.01	1.46	1.16
E-7-Soil	1.77	1.20	1.11	0.87	2.18	0.96	0.95	1.13
E-2-Soil	2.00	1.31	1.16	0.74	2.06	1.25	1.12	1.11
E-2-Soil-Ndg	1.94	1.28	0.98	0.67	1.88	1.24	1.62	1.07
E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux	1.92	1.46	0.61	0.73	1.32	1.01	0.43	1.19
E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear	1.97	1.33	0.60	0.73	1.31	1.00	0.47	1.21

Figure 5.23: Like Figure 5.3 but for the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation.

morning time series of the 2-m dewpoint temperature evolution are weakly affected by the data assimilation. Nevertheless, the mesoscale changes of dewpoint temperatures distribution in the surface layer reach 0.5-1.0°C of magnitude and have a systematic character (Figure 5.24). That is, at 09:00 (1 hour after the end of nudging window) the moisture plume is slightly drier and shifted to the west, in agreement with observations (Figure 4.10, top right). Then, between 09:00 and 12:00 a significant moistening of simulated surface layer occurs and the dewpoint temperature maxima to the E/W from Mikołajki are slightly smaller/larger compared to the E-2-Soil simulation (Figure 5.21). Such a moistening of the order of 0.5°C was indeed locally observed on that day (Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs, Figure 4.15) although it was not characteristic for the almost entire NE Poland, as observed in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation.

The increments to the thickness of the 850-500 hPa isobaric layer (due to the nudging of surface pressure) are concentrated over E and NE Poland (13:00; Figure 5.25, top row). That is, the thickness increases over NE Poland by up to 7 meters and it decreases over SE Poland and SW Ukraine by up to 5 meters. Thus, the nudging intensifies

Figure 5.24: Map of NE Poland depicting evolution of the dewpoint temperature (colors; °C) and wind field (arrows) at 200 m height AMSL in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Mikołajki (M) and Legionowo (L).

the mid-tropospheric ridge over NE Poland together with the temperature and pressure gradients on its western edge. As a result, a slight increase of the wind magnitude at 700 hPa is observed to the N and E from Masurian LD. Then, a noticeable change of the wind magnitude at 850 hPa is observed to the E (around $+3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and to the W (around -3 m s^{-1}) from Masurian LD (Figure 5.25, middle and bottom rows).

The surface pressure nudging in the COSMO model also influences the average ABL temperature because around $2/3$ of the temperature increment for each column is distributed between the surface and 700 hPa (Hess and Schraff, 2012). In practice, Table 5.1 depicts that a noticeable improvement of the 2-m temperature RMSD is observed for the Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Siedlce WSTs. The ML over Masurian LD remains, however, too cold at noon at many locations (Figure 5.23).

In the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation, a significantly delayed development of precipitating convection is simulated (16:00, Figure 5.26).

5.5.4 Modification of surface heat flux magnitude and the Bowen ratio

The assessment of the 2-m surface layer characteristics in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation documents around 2°C temperature deficit at noon for the Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olstyn WSTs, and around 2°C dewpoint temperature deficit for the Kętrzyn WST (in the northern part of Masurian LD; Figure 5.23). Since convection intensity depends on pre-storm CAPE that in turn depends on ML thermodynamical characteristics, those biases call for a further improvement of the morning ML over Masurian LD. One way to include that improvement is to reduce impact of the morning (around 06:00-09:00)

Figure 5.25: Maps in the top row depict thickness of the 850-500 hPa isobaric layer (meters) at 13:00 in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation (left) and that thickness difference with respect to the E-2-Soil simulation (right). Maps in the middle row depict wind magnitude (m s^{-1}) at 850 (left) and 700 hPa isosurfaces (right). Maps in the bottom row depict wind change (m s^{-1}) in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation with respect to the E-2-Soil simulation (at the same isosurfaces; red/blue colors for the increased/decreased magnitude). Capital letters in the thickness maps denote locations of Mikołajki (M), Legionowo (L), and Shepetivka (S).

Figure 5.26: Liquid and ice water path (blue-color scale; kg m^{-2}), height of 500 hPa (copper-color scale; meters), and radar reflectivity at 850 hPa (violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, and red 55 dBZ) in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Legionowo (L), and Mikołajki (M).

excessive CC over NE Poland (discussed in Section 5.3.2 for the E-7 simulation) as well as to compensate the 06:00 temperature deficits for the Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs (Figure 5.23) and for the other stations (Ostroleka, Baranowicze, and Lida WSTs; not shown). This can be accomplished by increasing surface insolation (incoming short-wave radiation) up to the value characteristic for the cloudless sky. This modification is expected to modify the surface conditions and possibly increase the total surface heat flux. The altered heat flux is divided into sensible and latent components, and their ratio may be modified by increasing or decreasing moisture content of the topmost soil layers. The following paragraphs discuss the method in detail. Then, the improved simulation is discussed and it is referred to as E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux.

Figure 5.27 depicts the area where the insolation is set to the value characteristic for the cloudless sky (limited by the black solid contour). The area consists of 10 regions centered around WSTs and having the radius equal 70 km in the west, 90 km in the north-east, and 110 km in the south-east due to the lower density of stations and observations (Figure 5.22). Inside that area, the insolation is increased by reducing the cloud fraction, level by level, to 0 at the input of the radiative transfer parameterization. This allows increasing the incoming surface shortwave radiation to the maximum physically possible value on the 21 August. Outside that area, a 20 km wide transition zone defines partial adjustment where the instantaneous cloud fraction is multiplied by a factor linearly increasing from 0 % at the inner edge (black) to 100 % at the outer edge (red). If a surface grid point belongs to two transition zones, the cloud fraction adjustment giving the higher surface insolation is applied. The modification is active from 03:30 (approximate time of the sun rise for Masurian LD) until no later than 12:00 (depending on the station, see below). This is because more limited modifications provide insufficient correction of ML characteristics over NE Poland. The modification is switched off for a given station when the modified air flowing toward Masurian LD would reach and influence it after the convective initiation period. The following list groups the stations (regions) and times of switching off the modification:

1. Outside from Masurian LD: the Lida, Baranowicze, Grodno, Siedlce, and Terespol WSTs. The modification is switched off at 10:00.
2. Close to Masurian LD: the Białystok, and Ostrołęka WSTs. The modification is switched off at 11:00.
3. Within Masurian LD: the Mikołajki, Olsztyn, and Suwałki WSTs. The modification is switched off at 12:00.

Once the modification is switched off for any region, the shape of still active regions is recalculated.

To eliminate any significant interference between the modification and already developing convective activity in vicinity of Masurian LD after 10:00, the modification

Figure 5.27: Map depicting the areas of the full (black contour) and partial (in-between of the black and red contour) adjustment of the incoming shortwave radiation in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation (valid for 03:30-10:00). More detail is provided in Section 5.5.4.

is switched off for a grid column if the amount of precipitating hydrometers exceeds 1 g kg^{-1} for any model grid point located between the surface and 1.7 km height above ground level (AGL). Practically, this condition is not fulfilled in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation but occurs locally in most of simulations discussed in Chapter 6.

The increased surface heat flux is divided into the sensible and latent (the Bowen ratio) by modifying the soil moisture content of the model soil levels exhibiting a significant daily temperature cycle (0-0.2 m deep). The altered Bowen ratio influences the daily evolution of ML (Thomas et al., 2018).

Since the soil moisture observations were not performed at the Polish WSTs in 2007, the soil moisture IC modifications are chosen by the trial-and-error technique to minimize the 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature time-averaged biases (05:00-10:00). The initial relative correction of soil moisture is calculated for each station as proportional to the difference between the 2-m temperature bias (B_T) and the 2-m dewpoint temperature bias (B_{DT}) in an auxiliary simulation with the increased surface heat flux magnitude only. The proportionality constant equals $25\% (\text{°C})^{-1}$ (an experimentally selected value making influence on the surface flux). The corrections for the stations are distributed in their neighbourhoods using the Cressman objective analysis implemented to the INT2LM interpolator of COSMO (see Section 5.5.1 for description of the Cressman objective analysis). If beneficial, the proportionality constant is increased locally and stepwise by $10\% (\text{°C})^{-1}$, with the maximum magnitude equal $50\% (\text{°C})^{-1}$. Table 5.2 summarizes the trial-and-error procedure and its results by listing the

Table 5.2: Temperature and dewpoint temperature biases (05:00-10:00) in the procedure of the soil moisture IC modification. The 1st and 2nd columns list the stations and their Cressman's radii of influence. The 3rd and 4th columns depict biases for the auxiliary simulation with the increased surface heat flux magnitude only. The 5th column lists the final values of proportionality constant for soil moisture IC modification in the 0-0.2 m layer. The 6th and 7th columns list the minimized biases.

Station	Radius of influence	Bias B_T aux. sim.	Bias B_{DT} aux. sim.	Moisture increase	Bias B_T E-2-Soil- -Ndg-Flux	Bias B_{DT} E-2-Soil- -Ndg-Flux
	km	°C	°C	%/°C	°C	°C
Baranovici	110	-0.56	-1.25	17	-1.01	-0.62
Białystok	110	-0.44	1.41	-50	0.25	0.75
Elbląg	70	-1.21	0.97	-50	-0.74	0.58
Grodno	90	-0.36	1.88	-50	0.54	1.02
Kętrzyn	70	-2.06	0.63	-50	-1.65	0.28
Lida	90	-0.75	0.70	-46	-0.11	-0.06
Mikołajki	70	-0.84	-0.18	-17	-0.58	-0.41
Mława	70	-1.13	0.95	-50	-0.76	0.65
Olsztyn	70	0.30	-0.63	50	0.09	-0.45
Ostrołęka	70	-1.64	-0.72	-50	-1.16	-1.08
Siedlce	70	0.77	0.37	10	0.65	0.50
Suwałki	70	-1.39	0.91	-50	-0.81	0.26
Terespol	110	0.69	-1.18	50	0.22	-0.72

WSTs (1st column; note three additional stations with respect to Figure 5.27), their Cressman's radii of influence (2nd column), the biases in initial simulations (3rd and 4th columns), the final values of proportionality constant for soil moisture modification (5th column), and the biases in the optimized simulation (E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux; 6th and 7th column).

The modified soil moisture content tends to alter moisture distribution across the simulated atmospheric surface layer once the incoming shortwave radiation becomes high, that is, especially between 09:00 and 12:00 (Figure 5.29). During that period, the near-surface moisture to the N, S, E, and around Mikołajki is reduced (in comparison to the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation), and to the NW from Mikołajki is increased. That is, the modification corrects the initial surface layer moisture from the E-7 simulation (Figure 5.13) towards the observed structure of the low-level moist plume (Figure 5.29; Section 4.2.4).

Figure 5.28 and Table 5.1 show that the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation noticeably reduces the 2-m temperature RMSDs for Masurian LD (Mikołajki, Kętrzyn, and Olsztyn WSTs). Although the 2-m dewpoint temperature RMSD for 00:00-12:00 decreases only locally (Kętrzyn WST), the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation optimizes the 05:00-10:00 bias of that parameter, as shown in Table 5.2.

The surface heat flux and the Bowen ratio modifications increase the forecasted

5.5 Improvement of boundary layer and free tropospheric air characteristics

Figure 5.28: Like Figure 5.3 but for the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation.

Figure 5.29: Map of NE Poland depicting evolution of the dewpoint temperature (colours; °C) and wind (arrows) at 200 m height AMSL in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Mikołajki (M) and Legionowo (L).

Figure 5.30: Skew-T diagrams depicting upper-air conditions at noon in Legionowo and Mikołajki in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation (left and right, respectively). The simulation data was obtained by horizontal averaging over grid points data remaining in the distance up to 10.0 km from the each location.

CAPE for Masurian LD. Areas of the highest ML_CAPE forecast for NE Poland match areas with the highest dewpoint temperature forecast in the surface layer (12:00; Figures 5.29 and 5.31). The ML_CAPE forecast for Mikołajki, around 2860 J kg^{-1} at 12:00 (Figure 5.30, right), is close to the observation-based estimation from Section 4.5 (around 2960 J kg^{-1}). Also, the peak pseudoequivalent potential temperature (see the footnote on p. 81) forecast for the Mikołajki WST (344 K at 13:00) is close to the observations from the Mikołajki WST (345.1 K at 12:00, Section 4.3.3). It seems that all the corrections applied so far allow reconstructing quite a realistic model representation of ML over NE Poland.

Between around 12:00 and 13:30, the ML features a weak ML_CIN of around 5 J/kg (Figure 5.31, right). That barrier erodes and convection develops in vicinity of Mikołajki (14:00, Figure 5.32). That is around two hours earlier than in the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation but still more than one hour too late. The collective activity of convective cells results in the development of a mesoscale anvil cloud (15:00). The movement of convective cells is rather slow and does not resemble the bow echo system from 21 August 2007.

5.5.5 Direct adjustment of horizontal temperature gradients in the low-to-mid troposphere

In the E-2-Soil-Ndg simulation, the nudging of surface pressure observations increased the early afternoon wind speed around 850 hPa to the E from Masurian LD (Figure 5.25, bottom left) and slightly increased wind speed around 700 hPa to the S from Masurian

Figure 5.31: Maps depicting ML_CAPE (left; J kg^{-1}) and ML_CIN (right; J kg^{-1}) at 12:00 over NE Poland in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation.

LD and over the SW Lithuania and NW Belarus (Figure 5.25, bottom right). Nevertheless, all the so far discussed simulations underestimate the horizontal thermal gradient across the converging air masses inflowing to the NE Poland from the SSW and SE directions (backward trajectories in Figure 5.12, discussion of E-7 simulation in Section 5.4). In particular, the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation overestimates upper-air temperatures over central Poland at noon, within the air mass flowing on the western side of the convergence area (CA). The bias is around 1.5°C in 800-600 hPa layer (the model-simulated Legionowo sounding is shown with solid lines and observed sounding is shown with dashed lines in Figure 5.30). Furthermore, in that simulation, temperature of the air flowing around noon on the eastern side of CA is likely underestimated by around 1.5°C across 800-550 hPa layer. That assessment is based on the presence of such a bias in the IC across the central-western Ukraine (the IC-based Shepetivka sounding is shown with solid lines and observed sounding is shown with dashed lines in Figure 5.11). At noon, that bias zone reaches the central and W Lithuania (shown in Figure 5.35 for the simulation discussed in this section). Also, the low spatio-temporal availability of surface pressure observations from the central-western Ukraine and western Belarus raises doubts about the nudging capability to correct that bias (Figure 5.22 and Figure 5.25, top right). As a result of the two indicated opposite-signed temperature biases, the representation of low-tropospheric horizontal temperature gradients between the central Poland and central Lithuania is underestimated in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation. Since that gradient ultimately defines the vertical shear of the geostrophic wind over NE Poland (including Masurian LD) this section aims to reconstruct a more realistic temperature and wind distribution in the low-to-mid troposphere.

Figure 5.32: Liquid and ice water path (blue-color scale; kg m^{-2}), height of 500 hPa (copper-color scale; meters), and radar reflectivity at 850 hPa (violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, and red 55 dBZ) in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Legionowo (L), and Mikołajki (M).

Figure 5.33: Areas of the temperature IC modification on the western (A; left) and the eastern (B; right) sides of the convergence area. Red dots denote locations of pseudo-observations in the Cressman's analysis.

The outlined goal is reached by modifying the temperature IC in the two source areas (denoted as A and B in Figure 5.33) from which air flow converges over NE Poland around noon. The first area (A) is centered over the central Hungary and its location is approximated with help of a backward trajectory analysis for air parcels reaching vicinities of the Legionowo radiosonde station at noon (Figure 5.36). The second area (B) is located around and to the S from the Shepetivka radiosonde station. Horizontally uniform temperature distribution is assumed in both modified source areas. The two horizontally-uniform states are derived from the 00:00 Shepetivka sounding and from the 12:00 Legionowo sounding. The following paragraphs document implementation of that scheme utilizing the Cressman's objective analysis and the LAGRANTO software for trajectory calculation (Sprenger and Wernli, 2015). Finally, the derived environment for Masurian LD and the afternoon convection are discussed for the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation.

The temperature correction is performed within the IC for a dedicated 7 km grid size simulation (E-7-Soil-Shear) because the adjustment areas reach beyond the C-2 domain (Figures 5.1 and 5.33). The correction is followed by the recalculation of hydrostatic pressure profiles. The E-7-Soil-Shear simulation is not explicitly discussed in this study. It defines ICs and BCs for the convection-permitting E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation.

The Cressman's objective analysis utilizes a number of pseudo-observations (vertical profiles of temperature derived from the two soundings) defined on a regular grid with a horizontal interval of 21 km (grids points marked with red dots in Figure 5.33). The negative/positive corrections are applied only in the A/B areas, in accordance with

Figure 5.34: Skew-T diagram depicting the IC of the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation around the Shepetivka (solid lines) along with the Shepetivka midnight sounding (dashed lines). The simulation data was obtained by horizontal averaging over the 10.0 km distance from the station.

the structure of the low-tropospheric temperature biases. The radius of influence of each pseudo-observation is 40 km.

Pseudo-observations for the Cressman's analysis around Shepetivka are defined in the ellipse having foci located at 27.05°E , 50.18°N (location of Shepetivka) and 28.10°E , 47.25°N , and the semi-major axis equal 201 km (Figure 5.33, right). In the vertical, pseudo-observations extend between 900 and 520 hPa, and the temperature values between those levels are interpolated directly from the sounding. Initial testing also suggested a correction of the humidity field because otherwise a morning upper-air convection is triggered on the E-side of the CA, in conflict with satellite observations. The humidity correction decreases the amount of water vapour between 900 and 520 hPa and its setup follows the Cressman's analysis for the temperature. As a result of both corrections, the new ICs match quite well the 00:00 Shepetivka sounding (Figure 5.34). The temperature increments for the IC are depicted with grayscale in Figure 5.35. That figure also shows that forward trajectories starting from the area around Shepetivka reach central and NW Lithuania around 12:00.

For the configuration of the temperature correction on the W side of the CA, the backward trajectory analysis is used. Based on that analysis, documented in Figure 5.36 for the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation, the pseudo-observations for the Cressman's analysis are defined in the ellipse having foci located at 19.60°E , 48.95°N and 20.90°E , 45.85°N , and the semi-major axis equal 225 km (Figure 5.33). In the vertical, the Cressman's analysis area extends between 830 and 540 hPa. The corrected temperature values between those levels originate from the 12:00 Legionowo sounding (Figure 4.5, bottom left) modified by the adiabatic lifting by 15 hPa. That lifting

Figure 5.35: Forward trajectories for air parcels departing at 00:00 from the vicinities of the Shepetivka sounding station calculated using the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation data (00:00-12:00). The colouring of trajectories denotes evolution of parcels potential temperatures along their trajectories (K). The trajectories are shown for parcels departing from 550 hPa (top left), 650 hPa (top right), 750 hPa (bottom left), and 850 hPa (bottom right). The grayscale colouring denotes the temperature difference between the modified IC and the IC for the E-7-Soil simulation at the denoted isobaric surfaces (°C).

Figure 5.36: Backward trajectories for air parcels arriving at 12:00 to the vicinities of the sounding station in Legionowo as calculated from the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation. The colouring of trajectories denotes evolution of parcels instantaneous pressure level along their trajectories (hPa). The trajectories are shown for parcels arriving to 550 hPa (top left), 650 hPa (top right), 700 hPa (bottom left), and 800 hPa (bottom right). The grayscale colouring denotes the temperature difference between the modified IC and the IC for the E-7-Soil simulation at the denoted isobaric surfaces ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

at 00:00 is necessary as those air trajectories experience a descend by around 15 hPa along their paths over the Carpathian mountains (shown with colouring of trajectories in Figure 5.36). The temperature corrections calculated by the Cressman's analysis are shown in Figure 5.36 (selected isobaric levels).

Figures 5.37 and 5.38 depict 850-500 hPa thickness fields for the modified IC of E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation (left) and for that simulation at 13:00 (right). On the eastern side of the converging flow, the correction thickens the mesoscale ridge across the central-western Ukraine. During the simulation, that ridge is advected northwards and stretched over the Lithuania and NE Poland. On the western side of the converging flow, a shallow trough is created in the IC. The area of the largest correction within that trough roughly coincides with the midnight location of the observed night-time MCS

5.5 Improvement of boundary layer and free tropospheric air characteristics

Figure 5.37: Maps depicting thickness of the isobaric layer between 850 and 500 hPa at 00:00 (left; meters) and 13:00 (right; meters) in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Mikołajki (M), and Legionowo (L).

(Figures 4.8 and 5.36) that is poorly represented in the ICs (discussed for E-7 simulation, Section 5.3.2). In the course of the simulation that trough is advected and stretched across Poland (mostly in the latitudinal direction). Thickness of 850-500 hPa remains almost unchanged over Masurian LD but the horizontal temperature gradients increase across NE Poland. Correction of the model representation of the thermal profile for Legionowo at 12:00 (Figure 5.39, left) is smaller than for the Shepetivka (Figure 5.34).

The correction of upper-air temperatures impacts the distribution of geostrophic wind over NE Poland. At 13:00, 700 hPa wind strengthens (by up to 3.5 m s^{-1}) over the most of NE Poland (Figure 5.40, top right). Therefore, quite large areas of winds exceeding 18 m s^{-1} are observed in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation (Figure 5.40, middle right). An opposite situation occurs for 850 hPa wind, that is, that wind weakens over the most of NE Poland (Figure 5.40, top left). Strong winds at that level are observed only at the very edge of NE Poland, over the central-northern Lithuania, and over the NW Belarus (Figure 5.40, middle left). As a result, a stronger wind shear is observed between 950 and 700 hPa than between 850 and 500 hPa (Figure 5.40, bottom row). In particular, this simulation forecasts for the NE Poland the strongest wind shear between 950 and 700 hPa from all the simulations discussed so far. The SSE to SE wind at 700 hPa is also quite consistent with the NW alignment of the high ML_CAPE plume (Figure 5.41) that was likely characteristic for the weather situation on 21 August 2007 (Section 4.3.2).

The modification has a rather neutral influence on the noon ML_CAPE over Masurian LD although a noticeable ML_CAPE decrease is observed to the E and NE from Masurian LD (Figures 5.31 and 5.41). Consistently, the 00:00-12:00 evolution of 2-m

Figure 5.38: Maps depicting the thickness change of the isobaric layer between 850 and 500 hPa at 00:00 (left) and 13:00 (right; meters) in result of altering the distribution of low-to-mid tropospheric temperature gradients in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation. The E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation is the reference one. Note the different scales for both plots.

Figure 5.39: Skew-T diagrams depicting the model-simulated (E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear) upper-air conditions for Legionowo (left) and Mikołajki (right) at 12:00. The simulation data was obtained by horizontal averaging over grid points remaining in the distance up to 10.0 km from each location.

Figure 5.40: Maps in the top row depict the wind change (m s^{-1}) for the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation with respect to the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation at 850 hPa (left) and 700 hPa (right) isosurfaces (red/blue colors for the increased/decreased magnitude). Maps in the middle row depict the wind magnitude at those isosurfaces for the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation. Maps in the bottom row depict the wind shear between 850 and 500 hPa isosurfaces (left; colors and arrows) and between 950 and 700 hPa (right).

Figure 5.41: Map depicting the ML_CAPE (J kg^{-1}) over NE Poland at 12:00 in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation.

temperature and dewpoint temperature in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation is similar to the one observed in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux (minor differences observed after 12:00; Table 5.1 and Figure 5.42).

Convection developing in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation is delayed and significantly weaker in comparison to the observations from 21 August (Figure 5.43). It is also weaker than the one in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux simulation, but its location is a little closer to Masurian LD.

Figure 5.42: Like Figure 5.3 but for the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation.

Figure 5.43: Liquid and ice water path (blue-color scale; kg m^{-2}), height of 500 hPa (copper-color scale; meters), and radar reflectivity at 850 hPa (violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, and red 55 dBZ) in the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation. Capital letters denote locations of Legionowo (L), and Mikołajki (M).

Chapter 6

Modeling of the severe convective system development

6.1 Introduction

The reconfiguration of ambient atmospheric environment (Chapter 5) was successful in leading to a simulated development of pronounced convective instability over Masurian LD and a noticeable increase of upper-air wind shear (Section 5.5.5). In that setup, however, the developing convection was significantly delayed and weakly organized. That delay likely resulted from the lack of realistic convection initiation (CI) mechanisms in the environment with a weak synoptic-scale forcing (the secondary CI on 21 August 2007 was likely caused by the cold pool-driven mechanical lifting, Section 4.3.1). The situation when the model does not reproduce the primary convection and, consequently, cannot reproduce the related secondary convection or even the diurnal convective cycle is a rather natural problem in modeling of the weakly forced convection (e.g., Clark et al., 2016; Hirt et al., 2019; Lean et al., 2008).

To implement the missing secondary CI mechanisms, this chapter introduces two convection triggering schemes, one referred to as deterministic and one as stochastic, intended to initiate convection in the COSMO-2 simulations. The deterministic scheme induces convection by triggering development of a line of towering cumulus clouds around the place and time as observed on 21 August 2007 with intention to mimic the secondary CI on the leading edge of the spreading cold pool, as hypothesized in Chapter 4. The stochastic scheme populates the ML over NE Poland with many relatively weak thermals from which only a few located in areas with low CIN and large CAPE may have a chance to trigger convection. This scheme is intended to mimic the primary CI of the first generation of convective cells¹. Since the latter scheme is randomized, it allows obtaining an ensemble of simulations from which only one is shown.

¹The first generation of convective cells is defined in Section 4.3.1 on p. 75.

The simulated convective systems are analyzed considering their resemblance to the system from 21 August (Section 4.3). That includes the comparison of the near surface temperature and moisture evolution with the measurements, observation of the spatio-temporal distribution of wind gusts, and comparison of the system-scale flow field with the classical bow echo system and its mechanism of the downward momentum transport (Section 2.2.4). The first sensitivity test analyzes how the adjustment of the horizontal low-to-mid tropospheric temperature gradients (Section 5.5.5) influences evolution of the simulated convective system.

Since the structure of modelled convective systems is sensitive to the employed cloud microphysical parametrization scheme and to the number of hydrometeor classes and their typical number concentrations (Adams-Selin et al., 2013; Morrison et al., 2009), the basic set of simulations is extended to provide solutions obtained with the more realistic double-moment (2-M) microphysical scheme of Seifert and Beheng (2006). Although the 2-M microphysical schemes are rare in operational forecasting (due to increased computational costs), those schemes provide a more realistic description of in-cloud microphysical processes that, in turn, should improve the overall accuracy of the model representation of precipitation formation and associated flow dynamics (Section 3.1, p. 58).

The final tests investigate the influence of horizontal grid refinement on the representation of the main convective currents (updraft, downdraft, RIJ, cold pool, and precipitation shafts) that may remain under-resolved in simulations with the default 2.2 km horizontal grid length. In those tests, the 0.55 km horizontal grid length is employed (COSMO-05) giving four times more points in each horizontal direction to resolve the currents and related vertical momentum transport. Such grids are expected to enter operational NWP in about 5 to 10 years. For the initialization of the COSMO-05 simulation, the dynamical downscaling of already-developed initial convection is used, as proposed by Lebo and Morrison (2015).

6.2 Convective systems developing in simulations with additional convection triggering

The following three subsections document three simulations obtained with the help of the deterministic scheme (Section 6.2.1), the stochastic scheme (Section 6.2.2), and both of them (Section 6.2.3).

6.2.1 Simulation with the deterministic scheme

The deterministic scheme mimics the dynamic and organized lifting at the leading edge of the morning convection cold pool. The aim is to trigger the second generation of

Figure 6.1: Map depicting ML_CAPE (J kg^{-1}) in the REF+Det simulation (11:00). Black dashed line marks the thermal core. Red crosses mark observed locations of secondary CI on 21 August 2007 (11:15-11:30; show as well in Figures 4.10 and 4.11).

convection², that is, convective development around 11:30 UTC³ on 21 August that was likely forced by mechanical lifting of the cold pool (secondary IC; Figure 4.11). To reconstruct the lifting the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation is used (Section 5.5.5). That simulation is extended by adding a linear surface-based thermal in the location close to the secondary CI area on 21 August (Figure 4.11, middle and bottom rows). This simulation is referred to as REF+Det in the following discussion. The thermal core is located between 21.75°E and 22.95°E at the 53.15°N latitude and across the high ML_CAPE area in NE Poland (Figure 6.1). The thermal is located between the surface and 0.76 km height and its width is 20 km. The maximum temperature perturbation is 3°C at the core and it decreases to zero at the edges following the cosine function.

The thermal-driven CI becomes successful at the western flank of the thermal and leads to the formation of a towering cumulus cloud around 11:30 to the S from Mikołajki and surface precipitation around 12:00 (Figure 6.2). The larger CIN barrier inhibits CI at the eastern flank (presence of that barrier is documented in Figure 5.31, right). The system approaches Mikołajki at the right time but it misses to evolve into a potentially severe bow echo system during its lifetime (Figure 6.2). Consequently, rather weak surface wind gusts⁴ are simulated as the convection passes Mikołajki and NE Poland (Figure 6.3).

The vertical cross sections in Figure 6.4 depict distribution of liquid and ice clouds,

²The second generation of convective cells is defined on p. 75 in Section 4.3.1.

³Time in this chapter is given in UTC as in the previous chapters. The acronym UTC is generally omitted throughout this thesis.

⁴The COSMO model implementation of the Brasseur (2001) parameterization is used for calculation of the surface wind gusts magnitude.

Figure 6.2: Liquid and ice water path (blue-color scale; kg m^{-2}), height of 500 hPa (copper-color scale; meters), and radar reflectivity at 850 hPa (violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, and red 55 dBZ) in the REF+Det simulation. Figures for 12:00, 13:00, and 14:00 depict locations of vertical cross sections (dashed lines) with IDs (non-prime letters shown only), shown in Figure 6.4. The other capital letters denote locations of Legionowo (L), and Mikołajki (M).

Figure 6.3: Maps depicting the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts in the REF+Det simulation (m s^{-1}).

Figure 6.4: Vertical cross sections showing the convective cells developing in the REF+Det simulation. Arrows denote winds in the surface-related frame of reference. Blue contours denote hydrometeors (isolines of 0.2, 2.0, 5.0, and 10 g kg^{-1} are shown). Dark orange contours denote the pressure perturbation with respect to the E-7-Soil-Shear simulation (negative values dashed, contour interval 50 Pa starting from $\pm 75 \text{ Pa}$). Blue shading denotes the cloud condensate exceeding the 0.02 g kg^{-1} (light) and 0.5 g kg^{-1} (dark) thresholds. Gray shading denotes the negative potential temperature perturbations with respect to the E-7-Soil-Shear simulation (light for the 2°C and dark for the 5°C threshold).

and liquid and ice hydrometeors as well as the pressure and potential temperature perturbation fields with respect to the reference E-7-Soil-Shear simulation that provides ICs and BCs for this simulation. Such an analysis allows identification of mid-level meso-lows because convection development over NE Poland is absent in the E-7-Soil-Shear simulation. However, the analysis underestimates slightly the cold pool intensity (a bias of about 1°C) since the reference simulation does not include the modifications described in Sections 5.5.3 and 5.5.4.

The cross sections A-A' (12:00) and B-B' (13:00) in Figure 6.4 show that the initial cells tend to tilt downshear across the mid-to-upper troposphere (i.e., in the approximately NNW direction, parallel to the environmental winds). Those cells build the leading rather than the trailing anvils. The tilt of cells is consistent with a weak cold pool and a moderate wind shear over Masurian LD (Figure 6.5). The two cross sections also reveal absence of a significant mid-level meso-low. Therefore, little horizontal momentum can be generated in the pressure gradient field (PGF) of the meso-lows. Thus, the potential downward momentum transport within the system is limited by the ambient mid-tropospheric winds (Figure 6.3).

Between 14:00 and 15:00 (Figure 6.2, bottom row), there is too little organization in the system and, consequently, the simulated cold pool is rather shallow and weak (Figure 6.6, bottom row; cross section C-C', Figure 6.4). Although the cold pool circulation is rather weak, slightly upshear tilted cells are simulated at 14:00, as shown by the cell in the cross section C-C' (the one close to the path of the original system, Figure 4.18). In the cross section C-C', a weak meso-low is also simulated (amplitude

Figure 6.5: Maps depicting evolution of the wind magnitude (m s^{-1}) at 700 hPa (top row; around 3160 m AMSL over NE Poland), 850 hPa (middle row; around 1500 m AMSL), and 950 hPa (bottom row; around 550 m AMSL) in the REF+Det simulation.

Figure 6.6: Map depicting the temperature evolution at 200 m height AMSL in the REF+Det simulation ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Figure 6.7: Horizontal cross section at 3.0 km height AMSL depicting the horizontal wind (arrows) and the negative pressure perturbation (colormap; contour interval 50 Pa starting from -75 Pa) in the REF+Det simulation. The perturbation is calculated with respect to the E-7-Soil-Shear simulation.

of around -75 Pa, Figure 6.7) as well as a weak RIJ that descends in the area of convective precipitation and influences the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts (around $18\text{--}21\text{ m s}^{-1}$; Figure 6.3, bottom right).

Figure 6.8 shows a noticeable decrease of the 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature RMSDs for the period 13:00-17:00 in comparison to the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation (Figure 5.42). This is a consequence of the successful CI and subsequent cold pool formation. The 00:00-12:00 RMSDs and the RMSD for Siedlce WST are practically unchanged (not shown).

6.2.2 Simulation with the stochastic scheme

The stochastic scheme is intended to represent activity of grid point-scale realistic thermals developing under the influence of the daytime heating. The ascent and mixing of those thermals erodes the weak CIN barrier and ultimately facilitates development of initial convective updrafts. The scheme stops once the initial convective cells develop. The activity area of the scheme covers the NE Poland (Figure 6.9, left) so that it imposes no strict conditions on the location of the successful CI as in the deterministic scheme.

The scheme is active between 9:30 and 11:30. The thermals have a cylindrical shape with the horizontal radius of 2.33 km, that is, the warm core is located in a one grid column while the temperature in the four neighbouring columns is increased only slightly. The thermals are between the surface and 0.76 km height AGL. Both location and amplitude of the thermals are randomized. The probability of choosing a grid column to host a warm thermal is 4% in a single draw. Every 20 minutes, a set of such grid columns is drawn from all grid columns located in the area shown in Figure 6.9 (left). Then, all the drawn thermals are randomly released at those locations during

Figure 6.8: Evolution of the 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature measured at WSTs around the Masurian LD (black) and simulated by REF+Det (red). Horizontal averaging was applied over grid points remaining in the distance up to 10.0 km from each WST. RMSDs for the 00:00-12:00 and 00:00-17:00 periods are indicated for each plot.

Figure 6.9: The ML_CAPE (left) and ML_CIN (right) in the REF+Stoch simulation (11:00, J kg^{-1}). The black solid frame marks the area with the activated stochastic scheme.

the subsequent 10 minutes period. If surface temperature at the release point is lower than 23°C (a subjective threshold indicating a possible presence of a weak cold pool), release of the thermal is omitted (totally, only about 2% of thermals are not released). The amplitude of each thermal is drawn from the Gaussian distribution with mean of 1.25°C and standard deviation of 0.5°C . The amplitude decreases to zero along the radius following the cosine function. In total, six draws are carried out and around 23.5% of grid columns becomes activated in the area.

All 10 simulations generated by the stochastic scheme-based ensemble extend the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear setup by application of the different chains of random numbers in the stochastic scheme realization. While an organized convection develops in each ensemble member, time required for that organization differs by more than one hour between the members (not shown). The documented stochastic simulation is one out of the ensemble chosen as a result of a two-stage selection. First, three simulations are chosen from the ensemble as those capable in generating significant surface wind gusts in a possibly short time (i.e., gusts exceeding 25 m s^{-1} at 13:30). Out of them, the one with the most intensive cold pool (i.e., suggesting the most active gust front) in analyzed below.

The shown and analyzed ensemble member is referred to as the REF+Stoch simulation in the following discussion. The convection activation scheme in the REF+Stoch simulation results in the appearance of first convective cells around Masurian LD even before 11:00 (Figure 6.10, top left). For example, the cross section A-A' (Figure 6.11, top left) depicts such a cell that ultimately dissipates half an hour later. Between 11:00

and 12:00 around 10 precipitating cells develop around Masurian LD, with majority of them initiated by the stochastic scheme and having the spatial distribution consistent with the low pre-storm CIN areas (see Figures 6.9 and 5.31, both right). Those cells develop moderate precipitation shafts but their cold pools are relatively weak at 12:00 (Figure 6.12, top row). The example cross section B-B' (Figure 6.11) shows that at 12:00 updrafts are rather downshear tilted. The meso-lows remain weak and despite of moderate intensity of precipitation, no significant convective downdrafts are observed. Therefore, little horizontal momentum is generated by meso-lows, downward momentum transport is almost negligible, and very weak surface wind gusts are observed at 11:00 and 12:00 (Figure 6.13, top row).

A significant organization of convection occurs during the period 12:00-13:00 over Masurian LD. A common (i.e., originating from individual convective clouds) cold pool develops featuring a noticeable vertical thickness (around 0.5 km; cross section C-C', Figure 6.11) and covering approximately the southern part of the Masurian LD (Figure 6.12, middle left). Thus, cells located to the rear of the cold pool tend to dissipate, while cells near the gust front start to organize along that line. The convective updrafts above the gust front get more upright (cross section C-C', Figure 6.11) suggesting that the increasing cold pool circulation promotes development of the low-level vorticity balance as in the RKW theory (Section 2.2.3, p. 35).

A distinct common region of convective precipitation is present at 13:00 (Figure 6.10, middle left) covering Mikołajki at that time (as observed on 21 August). The total induced surface precipitation exceeds locally 20 mm (Figure 6.14, top left) indicating that a significant amount of latent heat is released across the troposphere. Consistently, two noticeable meso-lows are present with the amplitude exceeding locally -2.25 hPa (Figure 6.15, top left). The horizontal momentum generation in the PGF field of the meso-lows is significantly larger than at 12:00 and leads to the development of RIJ (cross section C-C', Figure 6.11). The combination of more intensive convective downdrafts and increased horizontal momentum generation result in the development of more significant surface wind gusts (up to around 24 m s^{-1} ; Figure 6.13, middle left). These suggest that the system at 13:00 resembles the developing bow echo system at the stage B of Fujita (1978) (see Figure 2.11, p. 39).

The convective precipitation region is noticeably larger at 14:00 than at 13:00 (Figure 6.10, middle row) and its shape strongly resembles the shape of the bow with the bulge (Stage C of Fujita (1978); see Figure 2.11, p. 39). The vertical cross section of that bulge (D-D', Figure 6.11) shows the cold pool with a vertical thickness that exceeds 2.5 km at its head, horizontal momentum generation in the PGF field of the meso-low (amplitude of around -2.75 hPa), and downward momentum transfer (including the RIJ descending in the convective precipitation area). The bow-shaped meso-low is approximately perpendicular to the ambient wind at 700 hPa (Figure 6.15) so that both sources

Figure 6.10: Like Figure 6.2 but for the REF+Stoch simulation. The vertical cross sections are shown in Figure 6.11.

Figure 6.11: Like Figure 6.4 but for the REF+Stoch simulation. Locations of the cross sections are shown in Figure 6.10.

Figure 6.12: Maps depicting the temperature evolution at 200 m height AMSL in the REF+Stoch simulation.

Figure 6.13: Maps depicting the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts in the REF+Stoch simulation (m s^{-1}).

Figure 6.14: Maps depicting the total surface precipitation since 11:00 in the REF+Stoch simulation (mm of precipitation).

Figure 6.15: Like Figure 6.7 but for the REF+Stoch simulation.

of descending momentum add up and then focus over a relatively limited area at the surface (Figure 6.13; see also Figure 2.6 in Section 2.2.3 and discussion therein). Since a deposition of a significant surface precipitation is simulated to the N from Mikołajki between 13:00 and 14:00 (Figure 6.14, middle row), that suggests that the cross section D-D' depicts a situation shortly after development of a strong wet downburst. Consistently, the most severe surface wind gusts develop (magnitude up to $30\text{--}36\text{ m s}^{-1}$ ⁵; Figure 6.13, middle right), the near-surface winds have the diverging structure, and the cold pool is bow-shaped (Figure 6.12, middle right). The system propagation velocity becomes the highest and equals 19 m s^{-1} for the period 13:00-14:00.

Morphological structure of the simulated system (Figure 6.10) continues to resemble the stage C of Fujita (1978) between 14:00 and 15:00. Subsequently, between 15:00 and 16:00, the precipitation weakens and there are no clear signs of an ongoing transition to the stage D (bow echo system with a rotating head). This is likely related to the positioning of the system. That is, by 16:00, the western half of the system is offshore and the cooler ABL over the sea (Figure 6.12) limits CAPE available to the system. Between 14:00 and 16:00, two pressure minima in the mid-level meso-low field are seen in the cross sections of the system (E-E' and F-F' in Figure 6.11). They are associated with buoyancy deficits due to the latent heat release across updrafts (Section 2.2.3, p. 33). The primary minimum (i.e., with the larger amplitude) is related to the updraft

⁵The nowadays 3 level gradation of severe convective weather in IMGW-PIB classifies such gusts as related to the 2nd ($25\text{--}32\text{ m s}^{-1}$) and 3rd (above 32 m s^{-1}) level warnings.

Figure 6.16: Maps depicting wind magnitude (m s^{-1}) at 700 hPa (around 3160 m AMSL over NE Poland) in the REF+Stoch simulation.

located above the most active part of the gust front (i.e., in the bowing segment). The secondary minimum is related to the updrafts of other cells that flank the bowing segment (see also 6.15, bottom row). The area of meso-lows tends to enlarge between 14:00 and 16:00 and the maximum simulated amplitude is of around -3.25 hPa (15:00; Figure 6.15). As a result, the magnitude of RIJ is high and the simulated surface wind gusts remain quite severe and cover moderate surface area, with magnitude exceeding 30 m s^{-1} at 15:00 and 27 m s^{-1} at 16:00 (Figure 6.13, bottom row). Furthermore, the locations of maximum surface wind gusts at 14:00, 15:00, and 16:00 seem to be aligned. The most thick head of the cold pool (up to 3 km) is seen at 16:00 (cross section F-F' in Figure 6.11, and Figure 6.12, bottom right). As a consequence of such cold pool thickness, upshear-tilt of updrafts becomes noticeable (e.g., cross section F-F', Figure 6.11). Such a cold pool thickness remains in agreement with many idealized and semi-realistic studies (e.g., Badlan et al., 2017; Mahoney et al., 2009). The propagation velocity of the system is around 17 m s^{-1} for the period 14:00-15:00 and around 19 m s^{-1} for the period 15:00-16:00.

The system simulated in the REF+Stoch simulation depicts the classical evolution of a small squall line from the development stage (downshear-tilted updrafts), through the mature stage (upright updrafts), up to the stage of the overwhelming cold pool circulation (upshear-tilted updrafts). The mature system features pronounced RIJ, which is associated with the horizontal momentum generation in the PGF field of meso-lows and with the relatively strong ambient wind around 700 hPa (Figure 6.16). An assessment of the ambient wind influence on the system organization is considered in Section 6.3.

The stochastic CI leads to a quite realistic development of convection, including the location and timing, and features the average RMSD scores for the 2-m temperature and dewpoint temperature even better than ones in the simulation with the deterministic CI (Figures 6.17 and 6.8). The main RMSD improvements concern the 00:00-17:00 2-m dewpoint temperature evolution for the Mikołajki and Kętrzyn WSTs, and the 00:00-

Figure 6.17: Like Figure 6.8 but for the REF+Stoch simulation.

17:00 2-m temperature for the Kętrzyn WST. The largest contribution to the 00:00-17:00 2-m remaining temperature RMSD comes from too shallow 2-m temperature reduction as the simulated cold pool approaches the stations.

Although the stochastic CI leads to quite realistic development of convection, there are several differences in morphology and characteristics of the simulated and observed systems. First, the simulated system represents primarily the heavy convective rain showers without secondary high reflectivity areas associated with dissipating cells or stratiform precipitation (Figure 6.18). This is in contrast with the 21 August 2007 system structure since around 14:20 (Figures 4.18 and 4.20). Following Morrison et al. (2009), a simulation with the double-moment microphysical parameterization is included in this study in anticipation of an additional improvement (Section 6.4). Second, the path of the simulated system is more to the east in comparison to the observations from 21 August (Figure 4.20). This suggests that too little easterly momentum is transferred to the cold pool (Mahoney et al., 2009). One possible reason is an inexact model representation of the geopotential field over central and NE Poland and the related underestimation of the easterly component of the ambient wind around 700 hPa and above. Such explanation is suggested by the Legionowo model-derived sounding at noon of 21 August, shown in Figure 5.39 (left), compared to the reference radiosonde observation, shown in Figure 4.5 (bottom left). That is, the average simulated wind direction between 700 and 500 hPa is 168° while the observed wind direction in that

Figure 6.18: Vertical cross sections showing the radar reflectivity field (gray 5 dBZ, violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, red 55 dBZ), wind field (arrows), and regions of specific rain mass above 0.2 g kg^{-1} (gray colour) in the REF+Stoch simulation. The gray colour reflects the rain droplet number concentration parameter of the 1-M microphysical scheme in agreement with the colour scale from Figure 6.32. The green dashed line depicts the isoline of 0°C . Locations of the cross sections are the same as in Figure 6.11.

layer was 148° . Third, while the simulated system reaches the highest movement velocity between 13:00 and 14:00 (similarly to the observed system; Section 4.4.1) its propagation velocity is around 4 m s^{-1} slower than for the observed system during the period between 13:00 and 14:20.

6.2.3 Simulation with the concurrent stochastic and deterministic schemes

The extension of the E2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation with the concurrent application of the stochastic and deterministic schemes is referred to as REF+Det+Stoch in the following discussion. This experiment is intended to test whether such a setup provides an even more realistic realization of convection. The two schemes are configured exactly as described in Sections 6.2.1 and 6.2.2 (including the same chain of random numbers) and they act independently.

Figure 6.19 indicates that the simulated system resembles the one in the REF+Stoch simulation (Figure 6.10). In particular, the path of the simulated system remains almost unchanged and changes in the system morphology are limited. Those changes include a slightly increased cross-line width of the system (13:00-16:00) and a more pronounced vortex structure embedded in the system at 16:00. The latter results in the system resemblance to the D stage bow echo system with the rotating head (see Figure 2.11). The simulated head features, however, a rather weak radar reflectivity (16:00; Figure 6.19). The key dynamical currents in the REF+Det+Stoch and REF+Stoch systems have quite similar structures (e.g., upright updrafts, diverging upper-tropospheric winds, meso-lows, RIJ, thickness of the cold pool), as shown in Figure 6.20 (14:00;

Figure 6.19: Like Figure 6.2 but for the REF+Det+Stoch simulation. The vertical cross sections are shown in Figure 6.20.

Figure 6.20: Like Figure 6.4 but for the REF+Det+Stoch simulation. Location of the cross section is shown in Figure 6.19.

A-A') to compare with 6.11 (14:00; D-D').

The results of this simulation, together with REF+Det and REF+Stoch, indicate that the stochastic triggering of the first-generation of convective cells outperforms the deterministic triggering of the second generation. This is because the simulations with the stochastic triggering develop a squall line or a bow echo that is long-lived, located in vicinity of the Masurian LD, and propagates down the wind. Therefore, the stochastic CI scheme will be applied in the subsequent sensitivity simulation.

6.3 Impact of the low-tropospheric ambient wind on the system movement velocity

This section investigates the influence of environmental wind shear on the system propagation and structure using the stochastic CI (Section 6.2.2) within the E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux setup. That is, the modification of tropospheric horizontal temperature gradients, introduced in Section 5.5.5, is switched off. As a result, the simulation referred to as REF-Shear+Stoch features a noticeable weaker wind around 700 hPa across NE Poland at noon and in the afternoon when compared to the REF+Stoch simulation (Figures 6.21 and 6.16, respectively). At the same time, the temperature distribution in the low-to-mid troposphere (850-500 hPa layer) over Masurian LD changes little because the modification from Section 5.5.5 affected primarily conditions over the central Poland and the Lithuania (Figure 5.38, right). This is important because the similar low-tropospheric temperature distribution ensures quite similar CIN distribution (shown for CIN fields modified already by stochastic CI in Figures 6.22 and 6.9, both right). Also, the pre-noon ML_CAPE remains similar over the NE Poland (Figures 6.22 and 6.9, both left).

6.3 Impact of the low-tropospheric ambient wind on the system movement velocity

Figure 6.21: Maps depicting the wind magnitude evolution (m s^{-1}) at 700 hPa (around 3160 m AMSL over NE Poland) in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation.

Figure 6.22: Maps depicting ML_CAPE (left) and ML_CIN (right) in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation (11:00, J kg^{-1}). The black solid frame marks the area with the activated stochastic scheme.

The convection developing in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation during the period 11:00-12:00 has a lot in common with the REF+Stoch simulation. That is, the liquid and ice water path distributions over NE Poland are similar (11:00-12:00; Figures 6.23 and 6.10, both top row), well-developed updrafts are present and they reach similar heights (12:00), and cold pools and meso-lows are weak at 12:00 (Figures 6.24 and 6.11). A few differences can also be seen at 12:00, for instance, the precipitation shafts seem to be slightly less widespread (Figures 6.23 and 6.10, both upper right) and the convective updrafts tend to be slightly less downshear tilted in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation (Figures 6.24 and 6.11).

The convective system in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation becomes noticeably different from the one in the REF+Stoch simulation around 13:00. While the convective rain shower areas are of similar size (Figures 6.23 and 6.10, both middle left), the cold pools are a little smaller, and the gust front is around 12 km less advanced to the N (Figures 6.25 and 6.12). The surface wind gusts are also slightly weaker (Figures 6.26 and 6.13). Furthermore, the smaller surface precipitation amounts (Figures 6.27 and 6.14) and the around 0.5 hPa weaker meso-low (Figures 6.28 and 6.15) suggest that the total amount of ABL air lifted during the period 11:00-13:00 is smaller than in the REF+Stoch simulation. The simplest explanation is that the slower cold pool movement, the lower precipitation rates (12:00-13:00), and the weaker meso-low in the REF-Shear+Stoch are associated with the lower rates of the environmental momentum deposition into the cold pool. Such decreased momentum transfer would result in a lower efficiency of ABL air lifting by the system and would be consistent with the above symptoms including the decreased condensation and precipitation rates.

The REF-Shear+Stoch system remains weaker between 13:00 and 14:00 as well. It passes around 52 km during that period (movement velocity of around 14.5 m s^{-1}) while the other system passes around 70 km (19 m s^{-1}). At 14:00, the REF-Shear+Stoch system has a noticeably smaller convective precipitation area (Figures 6.23 and 6.10), the horizontal cold pool extent (Figures 6.25 and 6.12), and the total precipitation is noticeably smaller as well (Figures 6.27 and 6.14). Also, the difference in the meso-low amplitude remains at least 0.5 hPa (Figures 6.28 and 6.15). As a result, the RIJ is slightly weaker (Figures 6.21 and 6.16) and the simulated magnitude of surface wind gusts is of the order of $24\text{-}30 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (compared to $27\text{-}36 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for the REF+Stoch simulation; Figures 6.26 and 6.13). Many of these features hold also for the period 14:00-15:00.

To conclude, the weaker environmental vertical wind shear over the NE Poland translates into a noticeably lower amount of lifted ABL air between around 12:00 and 14:00, the lower precipitation, slower propagation velocity of the system, and noticeably weaker magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts. Therefore, evolution of that system is less similar to the system observed on 21 August 2007 than the one in the

6.3 Impact of the low-tropospheric ambient wind on the system movement velocity

Figure 6.23: Like Figure 6.2 but for the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation. The vertical cross sections are shown in Figure 6.24.

Figure 6.24: Like Figure 6.4 but for the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation. Locations of the cross sections are shown in Figure 6.23.

Figure 6.25: Map depicting the temperature evolution at 200 m height AMSL in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation.

6.3 Impact of the low-tropospheric ambient wind on the system movement velocity

Figure 6.26: Maps depicting the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation (m s^{-1}).

Figure 6.27: Map depicting the total precipitation since 11:00 in the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation (mm of precipitation).

Figure 6.28: Like Figure 6.7 but for the REF-Shear+Stoch simulation.

REF+Stoch simulation.

6.4 Impact of the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme on the model representation of the system

6.4.1 The REF+Stoch+2M simulation

This section tests the sensitivity of the simulation reproducing the bow echo system to the complexity of the microphysical scheme. The E-2-Soil-Ndg-Flux-Shear simulation with the stochastic CI scheme and the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme of Seifert and Beheng (2006, see also Section 3.1, p. 58) is referred to as REF+Stoch+2M. All the other setup details are configured as in the REF+Stoch simulation, including the same chain of random numbers used in the stochastic scheme. The 2-M cloud microphysical scheme includes both graupel and hail hydrometeors⁶. The following analysis focuses on the impact of that scheme on the timing of CI and morphological structure of the convective system. Then, Section 6.4.2 compares the magnitude of surface wind gusts and the rear-inflow characteristics in the REF+Stoch+2M and REF+Stoch simulations.

The pre-storm ML_CAPE, ML_CIN, and 500 hPa height distributions over NE Poland are practically identical for the REF+Stoch+2M and REF+Stoch simulations (Figures 6.29 and 6.9; Figures 6.30 and 6.10, top row). As one could expect, the most significant change in the pre-storm environment is the liquid and ice water paths of the morning clouds and the first-generation convective clouds⁷ (Figures 6.30 and 6.10, top row). The stochastically-induced cells develop narrower anvils and tend to produce rather precipitation instead liquid or ice clouds that would remain suspended in the mid-to-upper troposphere (for example, cells shown in the cross sections A-A' and B-B', Figures 6.31 and 6.11). In particular, the ratio of vertically integrated precipitation and cloud condensate present over the cold pool area (Figure 6.37, top left) shows that the 2-M microphysical scheme features a more efficient conversion of cloud condensate to precipitation.

The CI area and timing as well as the spatial distribution of convective cells are similar in both simulations till around 13:00 (Figures 6.30 and 6.10, top row). The vertical cross sections, Figures 6.31 and 6.11, show both similarities and differences of the systems in both simulations. The similarities include the transition of initially downshear-tilted updrafts at 12:00 to the upright ones at 13:00 and finally to the upshear-tilted ones (15:00-16:00). The simulated anvil tops reach similar heights, from around 12.5 km AMSL at 12:00 to 14.0 km AMSL (13:00 and later). The differences include

⁶An experiment with the graupel only provides qualitatively similar results to the one discussed in this section.

⁷See p. 75.

Figure 6.29: Maps depicting ML_CAPE (left) and ML_CIN (right) in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (11:00, J kg^{-1}). The black solid frame marks the area with the activated stochastic scheme.

less widespread anvils because of the increased amount of precipitation (mentioned in the previous paragraph) and a smaller magnitude of mid-to-upper tropospheric updraft vertical velocities (as indicated in the study of Morrison et al., 2009). The rain droplet number concentrations in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figure 6.32, top right) is not constant in space and time, as assumed in the 1-M scheme ($N_{0r} = 8 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^{-4}$). In the 2-M scheme its values locally exceed $10^6 - 10^7 \text{ m}^{-4}$ (low-to-mid tropospheric updrafts) but are reduced to around $10^2 - 10^3 \text{ m}^{-4}$ for precipitation that falls out of less vigorous (dissipating) cells and anvils.

A distinct cold pool develops at the surface within Masurian LD by 13:00, and it covers Mikołajki indicating the right timing of the system in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figure 6.33, middle left). The cold pool after 13:00 is deeper than in the REF+Stoch simulation (cross sections C-C' to F-F' in Figures 6.31 and 6.11; Figures 6.33 and 6.12). After 14:00, it also becomes noticeably larger. Morphologies of the two systems differ significantly during the 13:00-14:00 period (Figures 6.30 and 6.10) so that the systems hardly resemble one another at 14:00. Also, the system in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation does not take the bow shape.

Figure 6.34 shows that the REF+Stoch+2M simulation features less surface precipitation (data for REF+Stoch simulation shown in Figure 6.14). That is consistent with the lower instantaneous radar reflectivities simulated at 850 hPa (Figures 6.30 and 6.10). The 2-M microphysical scheme features more efficient upper-air conversion of cloud condensate to precipitation (p. 167) suggesting that evaporation of convective precipitation is significantly larger in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (consistently with con-

Figure 6.30: Like Figure 6.2 but for the REF+Stoch+2M simulation. The vertical cross sections are shown in Figure 6.31.

Figure 6.31: Like Figure 6.4 but for the REF+Stoch+2M simulation. Locations of the cross sections are shown in Figure 6.30.

Figure 6.32: Vertical cross sections showing the radar reflectivity field (gray 5 dBZ, violet 15 dBZ, blue 25 dBZ, yellow 35 dBZ, orange 45 dBZ, red 55 dBZ), wind field (arrows), and rain droplet number concentration (gray colour scale) in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation. The isoline of 0 °C is marked using a green dashed line. Locations of the cross sections are shown in Figure 6.30.

6.4 Impact of the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme

Figure 6.33: Map depicting the temperature evolution at 200 m height AMSL in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation.

Figure 6.34: Map depicting the total precipitation since 11:00 in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (mm of precipitation).

clusions of Morrison et al., 2009). The more intense cold pool in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation since around 14:00 also confirms that hypothesis.

Since around 15:00, the system in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation becomes noticeably larger in the direction perpendicular to the gust front (cross sections D-D' and F-F', Figure 6.32). In the rear, weaker or dissipating cells are present with the highest radar reflectivities exceeding 45 dBZ at and below the melting level (e.g., cross section E-D', Figures 6.32 and 6.31). Such structures are hardly present in the REF+Stoch simulation (Figures 6.18 and 6.11). As a result of the altered distribution of precipitation and precipitation-driven downdrafts, the RIJ locally descends to the surface farther behind the gust front compared to the REF+Stoch simulation and, consequently, the surface area affected by significant wind gusts is larger (Figures 6.35 and 6.13).

The average temperature and dewpoint temperature RMSDs for the Masurian LD (Figure 6.36) remain similar to the REF+Stoch simulation RMSDs.

Figure 6.35: Maps depicting the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (m s^{-1}).

Figure 6.36: Like Figure 6.8 but for the REF+Stoch+2M simulation.

6.4.2 Evolution of surface wind gusts compared to the REF+Stoch simulation

It is useful to compare the representation and evolution of strong surface winds resulting from application of different microphysics schemes, as shown in Figure 6.37. Two metrics of surface winds are chosen to measure how severe are the simulated wind gusts in each simulation. That are the maximum magnitude of surface wind gusts and the surface coverage area. The magnitude of surface gusts clearly impacts the level of potential damage at the surface. Figure 6.37 (top right) depicts the time evolution of that metric⁸ for the cold pool area (identified using the 23°C threshold for the 2-m temperature). Then, the coverage area measures the spatial expansion of potentially hazardous weather conditions at the surface and, indirectly, may also inform about the duration of the gustiness period at the surface. Therefore, Figure 6.37 (middle left) shows the significant gusts area, that is, the surface area in the cold pool featuring surface wind gusts exceeding 25 m s⁻¹ (a threshold for the 2nd level warning of severe convective weather in Poland, see also the footnote on p. 150).

Three additional metrics of the simulated convective systems are considered because phenomena they measure potentially influence the magnitude of surface wind

⁸The COSMO model implementation of the Brasseur (2001) parameterization is used for calculation of the surface wind gusts magnitude.

gusts. As the gusts magnitude depends on the strength of RIJ (via the transport of horizontal momentum in downdrafts), the analysis involves the maximum RIJ wind speed at 3 km height AMSL above the cold pool area (Figure 6.37, middle right). Because the transport of horizontal momentum is realized by downdrafts, the analysis involves also the maximum downdraft speed (bottom right) at 1 km height AMSL above the cold pool area and the area of downdrafts (bottom left) over the cold pool featuring at least -0.5 m s^{-1} downdraft speed at 1 km height AMSL. The two metrics may provide a relative information about the intensity of the downward mass flux and about the kinetic energy of downdrafts.

Data is presented for the period 12:30 till 16:00, with 15 minutes time resolution. As shown above, both simulations lead to quite a similar development and evolution of the system. Between 12:30 and around 13:30, the systems are developing over Masurian LD and feature relatively small cold pools. Between 13:30 and around 15:00, the matured systems propagate over the land where ABL features significant convective instabilities. After 15:00, the systems propagate also offshore where ABL conditions are less supportive than previously.

The maximum surface wind gusts (Figure 6.37, top right) tend to be weaker in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation except of a short period when both systems develop (13:00-13:30) and a period when both systems are partly offshore (15:30-16:00; the REF+Stoch system weakens at that time). The maximum surface wind gusts are simulated close to the gust front in both simulations (Figures 6.35 and 6.13). In particular, the peak gust values (33 m s^{-1} for REF+Stoch+2M; 38 m s^{-1} for REF+Stoch) are simulated over the land in both simulations, but noticeably later in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (15:00-15:30 vs. 13:45-14:00). The application of a more sophisticated microphysical scheme did not bring a notable intensification of surface wind gusts in the afternoon which could result from the upper-tropospheric momentum transfer down to the surface, as may occur in mature squall lines (Mahoney et al., 2009).

The significant gusts area (Figure 6.37, middle left) is similar in both simulations till 14:45. Later, it remains quite steady in the REF+Stoch simulation but grows significantly in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation, and becomes at least 5 times larger at 16:00.

The RIJ at about 3 km AMSL develops in the ambient flow featuring winds exceeding locally 18 m s^{-1} (e.g., Figure 6.38). Therefore, already at 12:30, the maximum RIJ magnitude in both simulations exceeds 23 m s^{-1} (Figure 6.37, middle right) although the meso-lows are rather shallow even at 13:00 (Figures 6.39 and 6.15). In the development phase, the maximum RIJ magnitudes increase at a faster rate and are generally larger in the REF+Stoch simulation (than in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation). During that time, those larger RIJ magnitudes do not go in pair with larger maximum surface gusts. In the mature phase, however, the REF+Stoch simulation features the strongest RIJ in pair with the stronger surface wind gusts. Both metrics are weaker in

Figure 6.37: Time evolution of parameters characterizing flow in convective systems in the four simulations: REF+Stoch (violet), REF+Stoch+2M (blue), REF+Stoch+HR (orange), and REF+Stoch+2M+HR (green). The parameters are described in Sections 6.4, p. 167), and 6.4.2, p. 175. The simulations are described in Sections 6.2.2, 6.4, 6.5.2, and 6.5.3, respectively.

Figure 6.38: Maps depicting the wind magnitude (m s^{-1}) at 700 hPa (around 3160 m AMSL over NE Poland) in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation.

the REF+Stoch+2M simulation during that period. In the offshore phase, the maximum RIJ magnitudes tend to decrease in both simulations. The generally larger maximum RIJ magnitudes in the REF+Stoch simulation contrast with the rather higher amplitude of meso-lows in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (around -2.25 hPa at 13:00, -3.25 hPa at 14:00, -3.75 hPa at 15:00, and -2.75 hPa at 16:00) than in the REF+Stoch simulation (around -2.25 hPa at 13:00, -2.75 hPa at 14:00, -3.25 hPa at 15:00, and -2.75 hPa at 16:00). It follows that meso-low amplitudes are not the only factor driving the strength of RIJ, which depends also on other factors like spatial distribution of pressure perturbations and their gradients.

The evolution of maximum RIJ magnitude in the REF+Stoch simulation in the period 12:30-13:45 clearly coincides with the evolution of maximum surface wind gusts, as could be expected from the idealized model of convective momentum transport in bow echoes (Mahoney et al., 2009). Afterwards, there exists a noticeably weaker coincidence as the RIJ magnitude features an another peak in period 14:45-15:30 and the corresponding peak of surface wind gusts is simulated in period 15:00-15:30. In the REF+Stoch+2M simulation, a noticeable coincidence is detected primarily between 14:00 and 15:45. It follows that the coincidence between the maximum RIJ and surface wind gusts magnitude is rather detected on the time scale of around hour than as an immediate relation.

The maximum magnitudes of downdraft speeds at 1 km AMSL (Figure 6.37, bottom right) are quite similar in both simulations. Their time average is slightly higher in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (-4.7 m s^{-1}) than in the REF+Stoch simulation (-4.3 m s^{-1}). In case of the REF+Stoch+2M simulation, the maximum magnitude of downdraft speeds at 1 km AMSL seem to be hardly connected with the maximum surface wind gusts magnitude. However, in case of the REF+Stoch simulation, there exists a coincidence with the time scale of around one hour when the maximum magnitude of downdraft speeds in that simulation reaches two maxima in periods 13:00-14:00 and

Figure 6.39: Like Figure 6.7 but for the REF+Stoch+2M simulation.

14:30-15:30.

The area covered by downdrafts (Figure 6.37, bottom left) grows similarly in the REF+Stoch and REF+Stoch+2M simulations during the development phase. Subsequently, it features a faster growth in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation and a slower in REF+Stoch till around 15:00. Later, between 15:00 and 16:00, the area covered by downdrafts features a net growth in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation but a net fall in the REF+Stoch simulation. Ultimately, the area of downdrafts in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation becomes almost twice as large as in the REF+Stoch simulation. As a result, the cold pool area becomes around two times larger in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figures 6.33 and 6.12) and the maximum surface wind gusts are more steady and do not fall below 30 m s^{-1} by the end of simulation.

The metrics do not allow for an unequivocal recognition of the more severe system from the two investigated. The convective system in the REF+Stoch simulation is more severe in terms of the maximum magnitude of surface wind gusts. In turn, the convective system in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation is more severe in terms of the surface area affected by significant wind gusts.

6.5 Impact of a refined horizontal grid length

As noticed in Section 3.1 (p. 58), the present-day operational regional models utilize too coarse horizontal grid lengths (1-3 km) to resolve turbulent eddies, entrainment

of convective updrafts, or to reproduce the natural vertical velocity energy spectrum (Bryan et al., 2003; Lebo and Morrison, 2015; Weisman et al., 1997). Grids with the horizontal length of at least 250 m are required for such applications (Bryan et al., 2003; Lebo and Morrison, 2015). Such grids are rather prohibitively expensive for the operational NWP.

The dynamical downscaling of the REF+Stoch and REF+Stoch+2M simulations (Sections 6.5.2 and 6.5.3) is intended to investigate impact of the increased horizontal grid length ($dx=0.55$ km) on the representation of convective processes. The down-scaled simulations start after the stochastic CI when 10 or more convective cells are present around the Masurian LD (Figures 6.10 and 6.30, both top right). Such an approach alleviates the impact of differences in the CI on the subsequent system evolution and, in that sense, follows the Lebo and Morrison (2015) downscaling method for simulating idealized squall lines.

6.5.1 The COSMO-05 setup

The two COSMO-05 (C-05) simulations start at 12:00 of 21 August from the ICs interpolated from the REF+Stoch or REF+Stoch+2M simulations (including the soil model). The model integration time step is 7.5 seconds. The setup of physical parameterizations for the C-05 simulations follows the C-2 setup (Section 5.2.2). Data assimilation is turned off in the C-05 setup except for the soil temperature nudging in the period 12:00-13:00 (Section 5.5.1).

The horizontal domain size is 1320 x 1320 grid points (726 x 726 km; $dx=0.55$ km; Figure 6.40), with a 72 points wide lateral absorber. The domain is centered over the NE Poland to cover the area of convection development at noon and in the afternoon of 21 August. The surface characteristics (roughness, plant cover, surface albedo, soil type) for the C-05 simulations come from the same dataset as for the C-2 simulations but they include more fine-scale features. For that reason, no noise is added to the ICs. The BCs are updated every 15 minutes. The ICs and BCs include the 3D velocity field. The ICs and BCs also include all moist variables except for the hail and the droplet number concentrations in the simulation with the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme (due to the technical limitations of the COSMO model).

6.5.2 The high-resolution simulation with the 1-M cloud microphysical scheme

The C-05 downscaled version of the REF+Stoch simulation is referred to as the REF+Stoch+HR simulation. The initial 500 hPa heights, total liquid and ice water paths, and 850-hPa precipitation rates at 12:00 in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation follow accurately the reference REF+Stoch simulation (Figures 6.41 and 6.10). A significant

Figure 6.40: The C-2 and C-05 computational domains (the orographic map covers the C-2 domain; meters).

change in the convection representation is seen already at 12:30 (Figure 6.41; not shown for REF+Stoch) when the new convective cells tend to be narrower than the ones in REF+Stoch. Such a quick model response is consistent with the conclusion of Lebo and Morrison (2015) that the vertical velocity field adjustment (that is, shift of the peak vertical velocity within the energy spectrum) can be realized in around 1 hour.

The overall structure of the convective system and its evolution between 12:00 and 16:00 in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation is strikingly similar to the one in REF+Stoch. It concerns the location of the system development and its path (Figures 6.41 and 6.10), process of the B-stage bow echo development and its transition to the C-stage of Fujita (1978), distribution of the liquid and ice water paths including the anvils shape, an underrepresentation of secondary high reflectivity areas associated with dissipating cells (Figure 6.42), the ratio of vertically integrated precipitation and cloud condensate over the cold pool area (Figure 6.37, top left), near-surface cold pool temperature distributions (Figures 6.43 and 6.12), general structure of precipitation accumulated at the surface (Figures 6.44 and 6.14⁹, and ambient wind and RIJ structure around 700 hPa (Figures 6.45 and 6.16; Figures 6.46 and 6.15). The convective system in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation differs from the one in REF+Stoch because of the grid refinement and related flow viscosity reduction (Bryan and Morrison, 2011; Clark et al., 2016; Lebo and Morrison, 2015). The convective system in REF+Stoch+HR simulation is built out of narrower cells (Figures 6.47 and 6.11), some of those cells develop ahead

⁹In the REF+Stoch+HR simulation the total precipitation over Masurian LD is accumulated since 12:00 while in the REF+Stoch it is accumulated since 11:00. Those data are compared in the text above because the precipitation accumulated in the REF+Stoch simulation between 11:00 and 12:00 is an order of magnitude smaller than the one accumulated between 12:00 and 13:00

Figure 6.41: Like Figure 6.2 but for the REF+Stoch+HR simulation. The vertical cross sections are shown in Figure 6.47.

Figure 6.42: Like 6.18 but for the REF+Stoch+HR simulation. Locations of the cross sections are the same as in Figure 6.47.

Figure 6.43: Maps depicting the temperature evolution at 200 m height AMSL in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation.

of the main system as initially isolated ones (Figures 6.41 and 6.10; similar cells were observed on 21 August, Figure 4.17), anvils and precipitation shafts have larger surface areas and more hydrometeors are exposed to evaporation (Figures 6.47 and 6.11), and less precipitation is accumulated at the surface (Figures 6.44 and 6.14).

The developing (B-stage) bow echo system in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation initiates stronger surface wind gusts than in REF+Stoch up to around 13:30 (Figures 6.48 and 6.13). In that period, the maximum magnitude of downdraft speeds and the maximum RIJ magnitude are larger in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation than in REF+Stoch (Figure 6.37, bottom and middle right); Then, the maximum magnitudes of surface wind gusts become similar for a half an hour (Figure 6.37, top right). On average, in the period 13:00-14:00, the mean system propagation velocity in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation is of around 20 m s^{-1} (19 m s^{-1} for REF+Stoch) and the gust front position at 14:00 is advanced between 5 and 10 km farther to the north.

As the C-stage bow echo forms and moves over the land (approximately 14:00-15:00), the maximum magnitude of downdraft speeds remains systematically larger in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation and the area of downdrafts over the cold pool tends to be larger by up to 15% as well (Figure 6.37, bottom). Those suggest that the downward

Figure 6.44: Maps depicting the total surface precipitation since 12:00 in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation (mm of precipitation).

Figure 6.45: Maps depicting wind magnitude (m s^{-1}) at 700 hPa (around 3160 m AMSL over NE Poland) in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation.

Figure 6.46: Like Figure 6.7 but for the REF+Stoch+HR simulation.

mass flux is noticeably larger than in the REF+Stoch simulation. At the same time, the area of the cold pool with significant wind gusts becomes around two-times larger at 15:00 in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation (Figure 6.37, middle left; see also Figures 6.48 and 6.13) although the areas were approximately the same at 14:00. Also, the stronger maximum surface wind gusts are simulated in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation during that period.

The gust front of the C-stage bow-echo system in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation reaches the Curonian Bay around 14:45 and the open sea shortly after 15:00 (Figure 6.41). Over the sea, REF+Stoch features weakening of the maximum RIJ speeds, decreasing maximum magnitude of downdraft speeds, and, consequently, a fall in the magnitude of simulated surface wind gusts. In contrast, the REF+Stoch+HR simulation features slightly increasing magnitude of maximum downdraft speeds after 15:15, steady maximum RIJ speeds, and quite steady surface wind gusts of around 33 m s^{-1} or more. Ultimately, the system in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation passes a slightly longer distance between 12:00 and 16:00 (Figures 6.41 and 6.10).

Compared to the REF+Stoch simulation, the REF+Stoch+HR simulation approximately preserves the convective system path and timing, alters only slightly the system's overall structure, and increases gusts intensity and area. A one significant advantage of the refined simulation is the more realistic representation of individual convective cells, for example, cells that initially develop ahead of the main system.

Figure 6.47: Like Figure 6.4 but for the REF+Stoch+HR simulation. Locations of the cross sections are shown in Figure 6.41.

Figure 6.48: Maps depicting the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts in the REF+Stoch+HR simulation (m s^{-1}).

6.5.3 The high-resolution simulation with the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme

The C-05 downscaled version of the REF+Stoch+2M simulation is referred to as the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation. In that setup, as described in Section 6.5.1, complete information on some water species is not available in the ICs for the 2-M simulation. As a result, the initial simulated radar reflectivities are weaker than in the driving (REF+Stoch+2M) simulation (12:00; Figures 6.49 and 6.30). However, the model spins-up quickly and there are no significant reflectivity differences already at 13:00.

The convective system structure in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation resembles the one in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figures 6.49 and 6.30). The systems in the two simulations share the same path, have similarly evolving liquid and ice water paths (including extent of anvils), similar distributions of both violent and moderate convective rain shafts in 850 hPa simulated radar reflectivity field (12:30-16:00), and similar shapes of the cold pools (Figures 6.50 and 6.33). The systems feature, however, slightly different total amounts of accumulated surface precipitation (lower values in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation) but with alike spatial distribution (16:00; Figures 6.51 and 6.34). Then, the ratio of vertically integrated precipitation and cloud condensate over the cold pool area is usually slightly lower in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation but it remains significantly higher than the values observed in the simulations with the 1-M cloud microphysical scheme (Figure 6.37, top left). As precipitation forms, the rain droplet number concentrations in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation vary between $10^6 - 10^7 \text{ m}^{-4}$ within low-to-mid tropospheric updrafts and $10^2 - 10^3 \text{ m}^{-4}$ for precipitation that falls out of dissipating cells, as simulated in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figures 6.52 and 6.32). Of course, updrafts tend to be narrower and more numerous in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation. Since the anvil clouds are rather similar but the accumulated surface precipitation and the ratio of vertically integrated precipitation and cloud condensate are in average lower in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation, one may expect that the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation features an even higher efficiency of convective precipitation evaporation.

The REF+Stoch+2M+HR resembles to some extent the REF+Stoch+HR simulation as well. That is, the convective cells developing in both simulations are narrower than the ones in the lower-resolution simulations (Figures 6.49 and 6.41, Figure 6.53). In parallel, the magnitude of maximum downdraft speeds in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation is similar to the ones in the REF+Stoch+HR and larger than in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figure 6.37, bottom right).

The meso-lows in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation feature the spatial distribution and orientation with respect to the ambient wind alike in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figures 6.54 and 6.39). That similarity goes in pair with the similar distributions of the simulated liquid and ice water paths (Figures 6.49 and 6.30) since both

Figure 6.49: Like Figure 6.2 but for the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation. The vertical cross sections are shown in Figure 6.53.

Figure 6.50: Maps depicting the temperature evolution at 200 m height AMSL in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation.

Figure 6.51: Maps depicting the total surface precipitation since 12:00 in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation (mm of precipitation).

Figure 6.52: Like 6.32 but for the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation. Locations of the cross sections are the same as in Figure 6.53.

Figure 6.53: Like Figure 6.4 but for the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation. Locations of the cross sections are shown in Figure 6.49.

Figure 6.54: Like Figure 6.7 but for the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation.

meso-lows and clouds come from the water vapour condensation and latent heat release. The amplitudes of meso-lows in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation tend to be noticeably weaker than in the REF+Stoch+HR but stronger than in the REF+Stoch+2M (Figures 6.54, 6.46, and 6.39; respectively). At 3 km AMSL, those amplitudes range between -2.25 at 13:00, -3.75 at 14:00, -4.25 at 15:00, and -3.25 at 16:00. There is no obvious coincidence between those amplitudes and the evolution of maximum RIJ wind speeds at 3 km AMSL after 14:00 (Figure 6.37, middle right). It suggests that the strength of RIJ depends not only on meso-low amplitudes but also on the spatial distribution of related pressure perturbations and their gradients.

The surface wind gusts generated by the mature system have spatial distributions similar to the ones in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation (Figures 6.55 and 6.35). Their maximum magnitude is noticeably larger during the most of time by 2 to 6 m s^{-1} (Figure 6.37, top right). The area covered by significant gusts in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation is larger than in the REF+Stoch+2M and other simulations since around 13:30 (Figures 6.55 and 6.35, Figure 6.37, middle left). For a while, it exceeds the one in the REF+Stoch+2M simulation by more than 100%. These characteristics of surface wind gusts are possibly related to the increased downward mass flux in comparison to the REF+Stoch+2M simulation. That is, both downdraft areas and maximum magnitude of downdraft speeds tend to be larger in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation (Figure 6.37, bottom).

This high-resolution simulation preserves the path and the cold pool extent of the

Figure 6.55: Maps depicting the magnitude of forecasted surface wind gusts in the REF+Stoch+2M+HR simulation (m s^{-1}).

convective system from the coarse-scale simulation while increasing the system propagation velocity, significant gusts area, and maximum magnitude of surface wind gusts. This simulation also preserves the more realistic representation of individual convective cells. Similar effects of increased horizontal resolution are observed for the simulations employing 1-M cloud microphysical scheme. It follows that in the context of the possibly realistic 21 August 2007 bow echo system reproduction the high-resolution simulations provide a perceptible gain.

6.6 Summary

In this chapter, the ambient atmospheric environment reconstructed in Chapter 5 was initially applied to search for the optimum convection triggering scheme capable in simulating the bow echo system development. Two CI schemes were tried: deterministic and stochastic. The deterministic scheme used a linear thermal placed at the surface. The stochastic scheme populated the well mixed layer over NE Poland with many relatively weak thermals. Subsequently, the simulation with the stochastic scheme was applied to assess the wind shear influence on the system propagation and to investigate impacts of the grid length refinement and 2-M cloud microphysical parameterization on the representation of convective flow and precipitation.

For the analyzed case, the stochastic convection triggering scheme is shown to be superior to the deterministic scheme because it provides a more realistic realization of convection, including organization of cells into a C-stage bow echo system. For that reason, the system initiated with the stochastic scheme is analyzed in detail and serves as base for subsequent sensitivity tests. The system develops within the Masurian LD and passes the Mikołaki at the right time, gains a bow shape, induces severe wind gusts reaching 37 m s^{-1} . Later, its organization into the C-stage bow echo is delayed by less than one hour while its propagation velocity is lower by around 4 m s^{-1} only. For the most of the area affected by severe convection, the total induced surface precipitation is between 15 and 30 mm. The system features the classical evolution of convective updrafts, from the initially downshear-tilted, through upright, up to the upshear-tilted updrafts. Such an evolution indicates formation of the overwhelming cold pool circulation (Rotunno et al., 1988).

The first sensitivity test investigates importance of the low-to-mid tropospheric (around 700 hPa) wind shear magnitude on the convective system evolution. The decreased wind shear gives a convective system that propagates slower and generates weaker surface wind gusts. That shows that the low-to-mid tropospheric wind shear played a significant role in the 21 August bow echo system development.

Three additional sensitivity tests investigate the role of the 2-M cloud microphysical scheme, the impact of the grid refinement, and the application of both. The ap-

plication of the 2-M microphysics significantly alters the systems morphology in both C-2 and C-05 setups, including elimination of the leading bow shaped segment. Moreover, in the 2-M simulations, larger convective precipitation areas develop and feature secondary high reflectivity areas associated with dissipating cells. That shifts the RIJ descent areas farther to the rear of the systems and increase areas affected by the severe surface wind gusts. For the analyzed case, the extended convective precipitation areas and the increased (more realistic) propagation velocities of simulated systems provide the main gain from the application of 2-M microphysics.

The refined-grid simulations apply four times denser horizontal grid (C-05) and are based on the dynamical downscaling of already-developed initial convection at 12:00. The grid refinement results in the flow viscosity reduction, independently whether 1-M or 2-M microphysical scheme is used. In particular, narrower cells start to develop almost immediately in the refined simulations and feature higher maximum downdraft speeds. Those isolated cells, some developing initially ahead of the main system, represent the convective mode observed on the 21 August. Regarding the dynamics, the increased magnitude of maximum downdraft speeds likely contributes to the development of stronger surface wind gusts and their area. The main identified advantages associated with the downscaled simulations are the isolated cells (indicated above) and the increased (more realistic) propagation velocities of systems.

Chapter 7

Summary

The research chapters of this dissertation begin with the investigation of environment of the 21 August 2007 SCS from Masurian LD. That investigation provides a detailed analysis and improved understanding of a plausible genesis of the SCS and explains how the pre-storm conditions on that day over Masurian LD resulted in the SCS development.

The SCS formed within the subtropical air mass of the Mediterranean origin. The routine Legionowo sounding, about 200 km away from Masurian LD, released around the time of convection initiation (CI), showed that the subtropical air mass featured around 1 km thick well-mixed convective boundary layer and the tropopause around 11.5 km AMSL. The sounding featured an elevated residual layer between 1.4 and 3.2 km AMSL that favored development of strong updrafts and thus more intense convection once it is initiated. The sounding also showed presence of a relatively strong mid-tropospheric SE winds with speeds up to 19 m s^{-1} , and upper-tropospheric SSE winds up to 26 m s^{-1} . In addition, the further modeling study indicates that a relatively strong low-to-mid tropospheric horizontal winds ($18\text{-}20 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) were likely present over Masurian LD at the time of SCS development.

Analysis of the available weather station data over NE Poland suggests that a relatively narrow plume of warm and humid air was present in the morning and at noon of 21 August in the surface layer, with dewpoint temperatures exceeding 20°C . Such conditions indicate presence of a significant convective instability aided by high soil temperatures resulting from low cloud cover and high insolation. A combination of surface observations from Masurian LD and the Legionowo sounding suggests that the atmosphere over Masurian LD featured a significant convective instability, ML_CAPE of around 2900 J kg^{-1} , and a rather weak convection inhibition, ML_CIN of about 18 J kg^{-1} . Horizontal extension of the humid surface layer likely matched the direction of low- to mid-tropospheric winds, creating favorable conditions for SCS development and its fast propagation. However, development of deep convection over Masurian LD was suppressed because of the absence of a sufficient mechanical forcing. Convection

initiation leading to SCS development occurred around 11:15 and was driven by a cold pool outflow from an outbreak of earlier scattered non-severe deep convection to the south of Masurian LD. Within one and a half hour, the initially unorganized deep convection evolved into a meso-beta scale bow echo system. It propagated over Masurian LD with speeds between 21 and 27 m s⁻¹ and surface wind gusts up to 35 m s⁻¹. The bowing segment left the area around 14:30, moved offshore around 15:00, and the entire system dissipated around 20:00, after crossing the Baltic Sea.

The subsequent part of this dissertation documents development of an experimental NWP modeling setup that aims to obtain a possibly realistic model representation of the weather situation and to reproduce the bow echo system development. That part is also intended to facilitate understanding what meteorological factors encapsulated in the COSMO NWP model initial conditions are the necessary conditions that let the model forecast the severe convective system and its leading convective mode. Two global datasets provide the large-scale environment for limited-area convection-permitting COSMO model simulations over Poland. The ERA-5 reanalysis is assessed superior and it is used as source of initial and boundary conditions. Initial NWP simulations indicate that several modifications are necessary to obtain a reliable representation of the pre-storm conditions over Masurian LD. Those modifications include adjustments of the soil and lakes surface temperatures, nudging of surface observations, modification of the surface sensible and latent heat fluxes and the Bowen ratio, and an adjustment of the horizontal temperature gradients in the low-to-mid troposphere that affect the simulated tropospheric winds. The surface layer modifications reconstruct the warm and humid air plume over Masurian LD, in agreement with observations. The adjustment of the low-to-mid tropospheric temperature gradients increases wind shear within these layers. It is based on the limited upper-air observations from the 21 August and a simulation-based flow trajectory analysis. The trajectory analysis also suggests presence of a low-to-mid tropospheric convergence area over north-eastern Poland. Within that area, the sub-tropical Mediterranean air flowing across the eastern Slovakia and north-eastern Hungary (crossing the Carpathian Mountains) meets the warmer and drier air originating from the south-western Ukraine and moving along the eastern edge of the Carpathian Mountains. Overall, the need for such adjustments highlights the lack of high-resolution weather observations across the eastern Poland, western Belarus, and western Ukraine. Such observations would be required to improve regional NWP simulations in conditions with prevailing E and SE flow situations.

Applying the adjusted modeling setup in convection-permitting (2.2 km horizontal grid length) COSMO simulations, CI is still delayed, and the developing convection remains unorganized. Therefore, two idealized convection triggering schemes are added to help the bow echo system development by triggering different generations of convective cells in place of the observed (but absent in simulations) mechanism of CI. The first

scheme, referred to as the deterministic triggering scheme, uses an E-W oriented linear thermal placed at the surface in the proximity of the observed bow echo initiation. That scheme aims to trigger an organized line of convective cells around the place of severe convection development. The second scheme, referred to as the stochastic triggering scheme, populates the well-mixed layer over NE Poland with thousands of relatively weak small-scale thermals. Those thermals are supposed to provide an initial burst of deep convection that subsequently organizes itself and propagates along with its cold pool. Based on a set of simulations, it is assessed that the stochastic scheme is superior. This is because it provides a more realistic realization of convection, including organization of cells into a C-stage bow-echo system.

The intense C-stage bow echo system that develops in the adjusted 2.2 km modeling setup with the stochastic convection triggering scheme features the right location (Masurian LD) and a delay of only 30-45 minutes. That simulation paves a way for the analysis of the system structure and environmental and dynamical factors causing formation of severe wind gusts. Moreover, the simulation confirms that the COSMO NWP model is capable to reconstruct the development of the bow echo system under the condition that the model data are realistic and the model is fitted with an effective convection initiation scheme. The final sections of this dissertation discuss 4 additional test simulations, two with 2.2 km and two with 0.55 km horizontal grid length, that stem from the above described simulation. The first 2.2 km sensitivity test investigates the impact of the low-to-mid tropospheric wind shear on the convective system development and evolution. The reduced wind shear in the test results in a convective system that propagates slower and generates weaker surface wind gusts. This shows that the low-to-mid tropospheric wind shear plays a significant role in the 21 August bow echo system development. That, in turn, highlights complexity of the weather situation leading to the bow echo system development since it developed as a consequence of the rather transient favorable surface conditions, low-to-mid tropospheric winds, and a small-scale mechanical destabilization. The second sensitivity test investigates the role of double-moment (2-M) cloud microphysics parameterization in SCS' development, organization, and propagation. Simulated impacts include noticeable differences in the partitioning between cloud and precipitation species (less cloud water and ice, more rain, snow, and graupel), an enhanced rain evaporation and thus stronger and faster-propagating cold pool, a more realistic evolution of convective cells building the SCS, and the rear-inflow jet (RIJ) descending to the surface farther behind the gust front and thus leading to a larger area affected by severe wind gusts. However, the simulated convective systems is not bow-shaped.

The two 0.55 km horizontal grid length tests are initiated at noon from the 2.2 km simulation with the stochastic triggering scheme. The first 0.55 km simulation documents expected impacts resulting from increased horizontal resolution, such as nar-

rower and more realistic convective cells, and stronger convective downdrafts leading to enhanced surface wind gusts. Besides that, the overall structure of the simulated bow echo system remains unchanged, and its propagation speed increases slightly. The second 0.55 km simulation applies 2-M microphysics scheme as in the second 2.2 km test above. That simulation shows features seen in both 2.2 km 2-M simulation and 0.55 km 1-M simulation above. Overall, the high-resolution simulations approximately preserve the general systems structure while increasing the systems propagation speed and the magnitude of generated surface wind gusts.

In summary, the main scientific objectives of this dissertation have been successfully realized. The developed NWP modeling setup and the related simulation results have potential implications for future optimization of operational model setups, including testing of convection triggering schemes, turbulence parameterizations, grid resolutions, cloud microphysics, and data assimilation. Moreover, as the key elements leading to the SCS formation appear to be located in the low-to-mid troposphere, the necessity to collect observations across that layer for operational purposes is highlighted. The synoptic analysis draws also attention to the collection and studying of mid-latitude convective events developing at internal convergence zones within subtropical air masses.

Acronyms

1-M Single-moment.

2-M Double-moment.

3D Three-dimensional.

ABL Atmospheric Boundary Layer.

AGL Above Ground Level.

ALADIN Aire Limitée Adaptation dynamique Développement InterNational (fr.).

AMSL Above Mean Sea Level.

BC Boundary Condition.

BRN Bulk Richardson Number.

BWER Bounded Weak Echo Region.

C-05 COSMO-05.

C-2 COSMO-2.

C-7 COSMO-7.

CA Convergence Area.

CAPE Convection Available Potential Energy.

CC Cloud Cover.

CEST Central European Summer Time.

CI Convection Initiation.

CIN Convective Inhibition.

COSMO The Consortium for Small-scale Modeling.

CPM Convection-permitting Model.

DWD Deutscher Wetterdienst (ger.).

E East.

E-2 COSMO-2 model driven by ICs and BCs from E-7 simulation.

E-7 COSMO-7 model driven by ICs and BCs from ERA-5 data.

EL Equilibrium Level.

ERA-5 Fifth Generation ECMWF Atmospheric Reanalysis.

ERL Elevated Residual Layer.

FFD Forward-flank Downdraft.

G-7 COSMO-7 model driven by ICs and BCs from GME model.

GME Globales Modell (ger.).

IC Initial Condition.

IFS Integrated Forecasting System.

IMGW-PIB Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - National Research Institute.

LCL Lifting Condensation Level.

LFC Level of Free Convection.

Masurian LD Masurian Lake District.

MCS Mesoscale Convective System.

ML Well-Mixed Convective Boundary Layer.

MSG Meteosat Second Generation.

N North.

NWP Numerical Weather Prediction.

PDE Partial Differential Equation.

PGF Pressure Gradient Field.

RFD Rear-flank Downdraft.

RH Relative Humidity.

RIJ Rear-inflow Jet.

RKW theory Rotunno et al. (1988) Theory.

RMSD Root Mean Square Difference.

S South.

SAFIR Surveillance et Alerte Foudre par Interférométrie Radioélectrique (fr.).

SB Surface-based.

SCS Severe Convective System.

SEVIRI Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager.

SH Vertical Wind Shear.

SR Severe Right-Moving.

SYNOP Surface Synoptic Observation.

TKE Turbulent Kinetic Energy.

UTC Universal Time Coordinated.

WMO World Meteorological Organization.

WST Synoptic Weather Station.

Bibliography

- Adams-Selin, R. D., S. C. van den Heever, and R. H. Johnson, 2013: Impact of Graupel Parameterization Schemes on Idealized Bow Echo Simulations. *Monthly Weather Review*, **141**, 1241–1262.
- Arakawa, A., 2004: The Cumulus Parameterization Problem: Past, Present, and Future. *Journal of Climate*, **17** (13), 2493–2525, doi:doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2004)017<2493:RATCPP>2.0.CO;2.
- Arakawa, A. and W. H. Schubert, 1974: Interaction of a cumulus cloud ensemble with the large-scale environment, part i. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **31** (3), 674 – 701, doi:10.1175/1520-0469(1974)031<0674:IOACCE>2.0.CO;2.
- Atkins, N. T., C. S. Bouchard, R. W. Przybylinski, R. J. Trapp, and G. Schmocker, 2005: Damaging Surface Wind Mechanisms within the 10 June 2003 Saint Louis Bow Echo during BAMEX. *Monthly Weather Review*, **133** (8), 2275–2296, doi:10.1175/MWR2973.1.
- Bachmann, K., C. Keil, G. C. Craig, M. Weissmann, and C. A. Welzbacher, 2020: Predictability of Deep Convection in Idealized and Operational Forecasts: Effects of Radar Data Assimilation, Orography, and Synoptic Weather Regime. *Monthly Weather Review*, **148** (1), 63–81, doi:doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-19-0045.1.
- Badlan, R. L., T. P. Lane, M. W. Moncrieff, and C. Jakob, 2017: Insights into convective momentum transport and its parametrization from idealized simulations of organized convection. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **143**, 2687–2702.
- Baik, J. J., Y. H. Kim, and H. Y. Chun, 2001: Dry and Moist Convection Forced by an Urban Heat Island. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **40** (8), 1462–1475, doi:doi.org/10.1175/1520-0450(2001)040<1462:DAMCFB>2.0.CO;2.
- Baldauf, M., A. Seifert, J. Förstner, D. Majewski, M. Raschendorfer, and T. Reinhardt, 2011: Operational Convective-Scale Numerical Weather Prediction with the COSMO Model: Description and Sensitivities. *Monthly Weather Review*, **139**, 3887–3905.

- Baldauf, M., et al., 2013: The COSMO Priority Project Conservative Dynamical Core Final Report. *COSMO Technical Report*, **23**, doi:10.5676/DWD_pub/nwv/cosmo-tr_23.
- Baldauf, M., et al., 2021: The COSMO Priority Project CDIC: Comparison of the dynamical cores of ICON and COSMO, Final Report. *COSMO Technical Report*, **44**, doi:10.5676/DWD_pub/nwv/cosmo-tr_44.
- Barlow, J., et al., 2017: Developing a Research Strategy to Better Understand, Observe, and Simulate Urban Atmospheric Processes at Kilometer to Subkilometer Scales. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **98 (10)**, 261–264, doi:doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-17-0106.1.
- Bauer, P., A. Thorpe, and G. Brunet, 2015: The quiet revolution of numerical weather prediction. *Nature*, **525**, 47.
- Bjerknes, V., 1904: Das Problem der Wettervorhersage, betrachtet vom Standpunkte der Mechanik und der Physik. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, **21**, 1–7, doi:10.1127/0941-2948/2009/416.
- Bluestein, H. B. and M. H. Jain, 1985: Formation of mesoscale lines of precipitation: severe squall lines in Oklahoma during the spring. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **42**, 1711–1732.
- Bolton, D., 1980: The Computation of Equivalent Potential Temperature. *Monthly Weather Review*, **108**, 1046–1053.
- Boucher, O., et al., 2013: *Clouds and Aerosols*, book section 7, 571–658. Cambridge University Press, doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324.016, URL www.climatechange2013.org.
- Brasseur, O., 2001: Development and Application of a Physical Approach to Estimating Wind Gusts. *Monthly Weather Review*, **129**, 5–25.
- Browning, K., 1964: Airflow and precipitation trajectories within severe local storms which travel to the right of the winds. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **21**, 634–639.
- Brunet, G., S. Jones, and P. M. Ruti, (Eds.) , 2015: *Seamless prediction: from minutes to months*. WMO.
- Bryan, G. H. and H. Morrison, 2011: Sensitivity of a Simulated Squall Line to Horizontal Resolution and Parameterization of Microphysics. *Monthly Weather Review*, **140**, 202–225.

- Bryan, G. H. and M. D. Parker, 2010: Observations of a Squall Line and Its Near Environment Using High-Frequency Rawinsonde Launches during VORTEX2. *Monthly Weather Review*, **138**, 4076–4097.
- Bryan, G. H., J. C. Wyngaard, and J. M. Fritsch, 2003: Resolution Requirements for the Simulation of Deep Moist Convection. *Monthly Weather Review*, **131**, 2394–2416.
- Byers, H. R. and R. R. Braham, 1948: Thunderstorm Structure and Circulation. *Journal of Meteorology*, **5** (3), 71–86.
- Chappell, C. F., 1986: Quasi-stationary convective events. American Meteorological Society, 289–310 pp.
- Charba, J., 1972: Application of Gravity Current Model to Analysis of Squall-Line Gust Front. *Monthly Weather Review*, **102**, 140–156.
- Charney, J. G., R. Fjørtoft, and J. Von Neumann, 1950: Numerical integration of the barotropic vorticity equation. *Tellus*, **2** (4), 237–254, doi:doi.org/10.1111/j.2153-3490.1950.tb00336.x.
- Clark, P. A., N. M. Roberts, H. W. Lean, S. P. Ballard, and C. Charlton-Perez, 2016: Review Convection-permitting models: a step-change in rainfall forecasting. *Meteorological Applications*, **23**, 165–181.
- Clark, T. L., 1977: A small-scale dynamic model using a terrain-following coordinate transformation. *Journal of Computational Physics*, **24**, 186–214.
- Clark, T. L., 1979: Numerical Simulations with a Three-Dimensional Cloud Model: Lateral Boundary Condition Experiments and Multicellular Severe Storm Simulations. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **36** (11), 2191–2215, doi:10.1175/1520-0469(1979)036.
- Committee of Environmental Engineering, 2021: Stanowisko Komitetu Inżynierii Środowiska Polskiej Akademii Nauk w sprawie zmian klimatu. URL kis.pan.pl/images/stories/pliki/pdf/dokumenty/stanowisko20210616.pdf, accessed October 31, 2021.
- Coniglio, M. C., S. F. Corfidi, and J. S. Kain, 2012: Views on Applying RKW Theory: An Illustration Using the 8 May 2009 Derecho-Producing Convective System. *Monthly Weather Review*, **140**, 1023–1043.
- Cressman, G. P., 1959: An Operational Objective Analysis System. *Monthly Weather Review*, **87**, 367–374.

- Davies, J. M. and R. H. Johns, 1993: *Some Wind and Instability Parameters Associated With Strong And Violent Tornadoes: 1. Wind Shear And Helicity*, 573–582. American Geophysical Union.
- Davis, C., et al., 2004: The Bow Echo and MCV Experiment: Observations and Opportunities. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **85** (8), 1075–1093, doi:10.1175/BAMS-85-8-1075.
- Dawson, D. T., E. R. Mansell, and M. R. Kumjian, 2015: Does Wind Shear Cause Hydrometeor Size Sorting? *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **72** (1), 340–348, doi:10.1175/JAS-D-14-0084.1.
- Doms, G. and M. Baldauf, 2015: *A Description of the Nonhydrostatic Regional COSMO-Model Part I: Dynamics and Numerics*. Deutscher Wetterdienst.
- Doms, G., et al., 2011: *A Description of the Nonhydrostatic Regional COSMO-Model Part II: Physical Parametrization*. Deutscher Wetterdienst.
- Done, J., C. A. Davis, and M. Weisman, 2004: The next generation of NWP: explicit forecasts of convection using the weather research and forecasting (WRF) model. *Atmospheric Science Letters*, **5** (6), 110–117, doi:10.1002/asl.72.
- Doswell, C. A., 2007: Historical Overview of Severe Convective Storms Research. *Electronic Journal of Severe Storms Meteorology*, **2** (1), 1–25.
- Doswell, C. A. and L. F. Bosart, 2001: Extratropical synoptic-scale processes and severe convection. *Meteorological Monographs*, **50**, 27–70, doi:10.1175/0065-9401-28.50.27.
- Droegemeier, K. K. and R. B. Wilhelmson, 1985: Three-Dimensional Numerical Modeling of Convection Produced by Interacting Thunderstorm Outflows. Part I: Control Simulation and Low-Level Moisture Variations. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **42** (33), 2381–2403.
- Droegemeier, K. K. and R. B. Wilhelmson, 1987: Numerical Simulation of Thunderstorm Outflow Dynamics. Part I: Outflow Sensitivity Experiments and Turbulence Dynamics. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **44** (8), 1180–1210.
- Dz.U. poz. 1219, 2020: Prawo ochrony środowiska (ustawa). URL isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20200001219/0/D20201219.pdf, accessed October 31, 2021.
- ECMWF, 2018: *Extra weather station data improve ECMWF's forecasts*. URL www.ecmwf.int/en/about/media-centre/news/2018/extra-weather-station-data-improve-ecmwfs-forecasts, accessed May 20, 2020.

- Emanuel, K. A., 1991: A scheme for representing cumulus convection in large-scale models. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **48** (21), 2313 – 2329, doi:10.1175/1520-0469(1991)048<2313:ASFRCC>2.0.CO;2.
- Emanuel, K. A., 1994: *Atmospheric Convection*. Oxford University Press, 580 pp.
- Evans, J. S. and C. A. Doswell, 2001: Examination of Derecho Environments Using Proximity Soundings. *Weather and Forecasting*, **16**, 329–342.
- Foroutan, H. and J. E. Pleim, 2017: Improving the simulation of convective dust storms in regional-to-global models. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, **9**, 2046–2060, doi:doi.org/10.1002/2017MS000953.
- Frank, W. M., 1978: The life cycles of GATE convective systems. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **35**, 1256–1164.
- Fritsch, J. M. and R. A. Maddox, 1981: Convectively Driven Mesoscale Weather Systems Aloft. Part I: OBServations. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **20**, 9–19.
- Fujita, T. T., 1957: Three-Dimensional Mesoanalysis of a Squall Line.
- Fujita, T. T., 1978: Manual of downburst identification for project NIMROD.
- Gatzen, C., 2004: A Derecho in Europe: Berlin, 10 July 2002. *Weather and Forecasting*, **19**, 639–645.
- Grabowski, W. W. and M. M. Moncrieff, 2001: Large-scale organization of tropical convection in two-dimensional explicit numerical simulations. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **127**, 445–468.
- Haertel, P. T. and R. H. Johnson, 2000: The Linear Dynamics of Squall Line Mesohighs and Wake Lows. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **57**, 93–107.
- Hamilton, R. E., 1970: A review of the use if radar in detection of tornadoes and hail. *ESSA Tech. Memo. WBTM-ER-34*.
- Heise, W., M. Lange, B. Ritter, and R. Schrodin, 2003: Improvement and validation of the multi-layer soil model. *COSMO Newsletter, Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany*, **3**, 198–203.
- Hersbach, H., et al., 2020: The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **146** (730), 1999–2049, doi:10.1002/qj.3803.
- Hess, R. and C. Schraff, 2012: *A Description of the Nonhydrostatic Regional COSMO-Model Part III: Data Assimilation*. Deutscher Wetterdienst.

- Hirt, M., S. Rasp, U. Blahak, and G. C. Craig, 2019: Stochastic parameterization of processes leading to convective initiation in kilometer-scale models. *Monthly Weather Review*, **147**, 3917–3934.
- Hohenegger, C. and C. Schaer, 2007: Atmospheric Predictability at Synoptic Versus Cloud-Resolving Scales. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **88** (11), 1783–1794, doi:doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-88-11-1783.
- Houze, R. A., 1989: Observed structure of mesoscale convective systems and implications for large-scale heating. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **115**, 425–461.
- Houze, R. A., 1997: Stratiform Precipitation in Regions of Convection: A Meteorological Paradox? *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **78** (10), 2179–2196.
- Houze, R. A. and A. K. Betts, 1981: Convection in GATE. *Rev. Geophys.*, **19** (4), 541–576.
- Houze, R. A., S. A. Rutledge, M. I. Biggerstaff, and B. F. Smull, 1989: Interpretation of Doppler Weather Radar Displays in Midlatitude Mesoscale Convective Systems. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **70** (6), 608–619.
- Houze, R. A. J., 2004: Mesoscale Convective Systems. *Reviews of Geophysics*, **42**, 1–43.
- IMGW-PIB, 2007: Komunikat dotyczący wydarzeń z 21 sierpnia 2007.
- Johns, R. H. and W. D. Hirt, 1987: Derechos: Widespread convectively induced windstorms. *Weather and Forecasting*, **2**, 32–49.
- Kain, J. S., 2004: The Kain-Fritsch Convective Parameterization: An Update. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **43** (1), 170 – 181, doi:10.1175/1520-0450(2004)043<0170:TKCPAU>2.0.CO;2.
- Kessler, E., 1969: On the distribution and continuity of water substance in the atmospheric circulations. *Meteorological Monographs*, **10** (32).
- Kirtman, B., et al., 2013: *Near-term Climate Change: Projections and Predictability*, book section 11, 953–1028. Cambridge University Press, doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324.023, URL www.climatechange2013.org.
- Klemp, J., 1987: Dynamics of Tornadic Thunderstorms. *Ann. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, **19**, 1–33.
- Klemp, J. and R. Wilhelmson, 1978: The simulation of three-dimensional convective storm dynamics. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **35**, 1070–1096.

- Klimowski, B. A., M. R. Hjelmfelt, and M. J. Bunkres, 2004: Radar Observation of the Early Evolution of Bow Echoes. *Weather and Forecasting*, **19**, 727–734.
- Kolendowicz, L., 2006: The influence of synoptic situations on the occurrence of days with thunderstorms during a year in the territory of Poland. *International Journal of Climatology*, **26**, 1803–1820.
- Kolendowicz, L., 2012: Synoptic patterns associated with thunderstorms in Poland. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*, **21** (2), 145–156.
- Krikpatrick, C., E. W. M. Jr., and C. Cohen, 2011: Sensitivities of Simulated Convective Storms to Environmental CAPE. *Monthly Weather Review*, **139**, 3514–3532.
- Kundzewicz, Z., et al., 2013: Floods at the northern foothills of the Tatra Mountains – A Polish-Swiss research project. *Acta Geophysica*, **62**, 620–641, doi:10.2478/s11600-013-0192-3.
- Kurowski, M. J., D. K. Wójcik, M. Z. Ziemiański, B. Rosa, and Z. P. Piotrowski, 2016: Convection-permitting regional weather modeling with COSMO-EULAG: Compressible and anelastic solutions for a typical westerly flow over the Alps. *Monthly Weather Review*, 1961–1982, doi:10.1175/MWR-D-15-0264.1.
- Kusaka, H., K. Nawata, A. Suzuki-Parker, Y. Takane, and N. Furuhashi, 2014: Mechanism of Precipitation Increase with Urbanization in Tokyo as Revealed by Ensemble Climate Simulations. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology*, **53** (4), 824–839, doi:doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-13-065.1.
- Lafore, J.-P. and M. W. Moncreff, 1989: A Numerical Investigation of the Organization and Interaction of the Convective and Stratiform Regions of Tropical Squall Lines. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **46** (4), 521–544.
- Langhans, W., J. Schmidli, and B. Szintai, 2013: A Smagorinsky-Lilly turbulence closure for COSMO-LES: Implementation and comparison to ARPS. *COSMO Newsletter*, *Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany*, **No. 12**, 20–31.
- Lawson, J. and W. A. G. Jr., 2016: On Contrasting Ensemble Simulations of Two Great Plains Bow Echoes. *Weather and Forecasting*, **31**, 787–810.
- Lean, H. W., P. A. Clark, M. Dixon, N. M. Roberts, A. Fitch, R. Forbes, and C. Halliwell, 2008: Characteristics of High-Resolution Versions of the Met Office Unified Model for Forecasting Convection over the United Kingdom. *Monthly Weather Review*, **136** (9), 3408–3424, doi:10.1175/2008MWR2332.1.

-
- Leary, C. A. and R. A. Houze, 1979: Melting and Evaporation of Hydrometeors in Precipitation from the Anvil Clouds in Deep Tropical Convection. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **36**, 669–679.
- Lebo, Z. J. and H. Morrison, 2015: Effects of Horizontal and Vertical Grid Spacing on Mixing in Simulated Squall Lines and Implications for Convective Strength and Structure. *Monthly Weather Review*, **143**, 4355–4375.
- Lemon, L. R. and C. A. Doswell, 1979: Severe Thunderstorm Evolution and Mesocyclone Structure as Related to Tornadogenesis. *Monthly Weather Review*, **107** (9), 1184–1197.
- Lilly, D. K., 1979: The Dynamical Structure and Evolution of Thunderstorms and Squall Lines. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences*, **7**, 117–161.
- Lynch, P., 2008: The origins of computer weather prediction and climate modeling. *Journal of Computational Physics*, **227**, 3431–3444.
- Mahoney, K. M., G. M. Lackmann, and M. D. Parker, 2009: The Role of Momentum Transport in the Motion of a Quasi-Idealized Mesoscale Convective System. *Monthly Weather Review*, **137**, 3316–3338.
- Majewski, D., et al., 2002: The Operational Global Icosahedral–Hexagonal Grid-point Model GME: Description and High-Resolution Tests. *Monthly Weather Review*, **130** (2), 319–338.
- Majumdar, S. J., et al., 2021: Multiscale Forecasting of High-Impact Weather: Current Status and Future Challenges. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **102** (3), 635–659, doi:doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0111.1.
- Manabe, S., J. Smagorinsky, and R. F. Strickler, 1965: Simulated Climatology Of a General Circulation Model With a Hydrologic Cycle. *Monthly Weather Review*, **93** (12), 769 – 798, doi:10.1175/1520-0493(1965)093<0769:SCOAGC>2.3.CO;2.
- Markowski, P. and Y. Richardson, 2010: *Mesoscale Meteorology in Midlatitudes*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Marwitz, J. D., 1973: Trajectories Within the Weak Echo Region. *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, **12**, 1174–1182.
- Mathias, L., V. Ermert, F. Kelemen, P. Ludwig, and J. Pinto, 2017: Synoptic analysis and hindcast of an intense bow echo in Western Europe: The 09 June 2014 storm. *Weather and Forecasting*, **32**, 1121–1141.

- Mironov, D. V., 2008: Parameterization of lakes in numerical weather prediction. Description of a lake model. *COSMO Technical Report*, **11**.
- Moncrieff, M. W. and J. S. A. Green, 1972: The propagation and transfer properties of steady convective overturning in shear. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **98 (416)**, 336–352.
- Moncrieff, M. W. and M. J. Miller, 1976: The dynamics and simulation of tropical cumulonimbus and squall lines. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **102**, 373–394.
- Morris, R., 1986: The Spanish Plume - Testing the forecaster's nerve. *Meteor. Mag.*, **115**, 349–357.
- Morrison, H., G. Thompson, and V. Tatarskii, 2009: Impact of Cloud Microphysics on the Development of Trailing Stratiform Precipitation in a Simulated Squall Line: Comparison of One- and Two-Moment Schemes. *Monthly Weather Review*, **137**, 991–1007.
- Newton, C. W., 1950: Structure and Mechanism of the Prefrontal Squall Line. *Journal of Meteorology*, **7**, 210–222.
- Newton, C. W. and S. Katz, 1958: Movement of large convective rainstorms in relation to winds aloft. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **39**, 129–136.
- Nieckarz, Z. and S. Zięba, 2013: Variability of daily thunderstorm surface in Poland and Europe in years 1980-2010. *Atmospheric Research*, **127**, 77–89.
- Nolen, R. H., 1959: A radar pattern associated with tornadoes. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **40**, 277–279.
- Orlanski, I., 1975: A rational subdivision of scales for atmospheric processes. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **56**, 527–530.
- Palmén, E. and C. W. Newton, 1969: *Atmospheric Circulation Systems. Their Structural and Physical Interpretation*. Academic Press.
- Parker, M. D. and R. H. Johnson, 2000: Organizational Modes of Midlatitude Mesoscale Convective Systems. *Monthly Weather Review*, **128**, 3413–3436.
- Persson, A., 2005: Early operational numerical weather prediction outside the usa: an historical introduction. part 1: Internationalism and engineering nwp in sweden, 1952-69. *Meteorological Applications*, **12 (2)**, 135–159, doi:doi.org/10.1017/S1350482705001593.

- Pielke, R. A., 2001: Influence of the spatial distribution of vegetation and soils on the prediction of cumulus Convective rainfall. *Reviews of Geophysics*, **39** (2), 151–177.
- Prein, A. F., et al., 2015: A review on regional convection-permitting climate modeling: Demonstrations, prospects, and challenges. *Reviews of Geophysics*, **53** (2), 323–361, doi:10.1002/2014RG000475, URL agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/2014RG000475.
- Punkka, A.-J., J. Teittinen, and R. H. Johns, 2006: Synoptic and mesoscale analysis of a high-latitude derecho-severe thunderstorm outbreak in Finland on 5 July 2002. *Weather and Forecasting*, **21**, 752–763.
- Raschendorfer, M., 2001: The new turbulence parameterization of LM. *COSMO Newsletter, Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany*, **No. 1**, 89–97.
- Raymond, C., T. Matthews, and R. M. Horton, 2020: The emergence of heat and humidity too severe for human tolerance. *Science Advances*, **6** (19).
- Reinhardt, T. and A. Seifert, 2006: A three-category ice scheme for LMK. *COSMO Newsletter, Deutscher Wetterdienst, Offenbach, Germany*, **6**, 115–120.
- Ritter, M. and J. F. Geleyn, 1992: A comprehensive radiation scheme for numerical weather prediction models with potential applications in climate simulations. *Monthly Weather Review*, **120**, 303–325.
- Rojek, A., et al., 2015: Adaptation of fluid model EULAG to graphics processing unit architecture. *Concurrency and Computation-Practice & Experience*, **27**, 937–957, doi:10.7763/IJAPM.2014.V4.281.
- Rosik-Dulewska, C., 2010: Inżynieria środowiska. URL kis.pan.pl/images/stories/pliki/pdf/inzynieria_srodowiska_stan_obecny_i_perpektywy_rozwoju.pdf, accessed November 12, 2021.
- Rotunno, R., 1981: On the Evolution of Thunderstorm Rotation. *Monthly Weather Review*, **109**, 577–586.
- Rotunno, R. and J. Klemp, 1981: The Influence of the Shear-Induced Pressure Gradient on Thunderstorm Motion. *Monthly Weather Review*, **110**, 136–151.
- Rotunno, R. and J. Klemp, 1985: On the Rotation and Propagation of Simulated Supercell Motion. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **42**, 271–292.
- Rotunno, R., J. Klemp, and M. Weisman, 1988: A Theory for Strong, Long-Lived Squall Lines. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **45** (3), 463–485.

- Saito, K., 2012: *The JMA Nonhydrostatic Model and Its Applications to Operation and Research*, 85–110. doi:10.5772/35368.
- Satoh, M., T. Matsuno, H. Tomita, H. Miura, T. Nasuno, and S. Iga, 2008: Nonhydrostatic icosahedral atmospheric model (nicam) for global cloud resolving simulations. *Journal of Computational Physics*, **227** (7), 3486–3514, doi:doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2007.02.006, URL www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0021999107000654, predicting weather, climate and extreme events.
- Schlesinger, R., 1973: A Numerical Model of Deep Moist Convection: Part I. Comparative Experiments for Variable Ambient Moisture and Wind Shear. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **30**, 835–856.
- Schlesinger, R., 1975: A Three-Dimensional Numerical Model of an Isolated Deep Convective Cloud: Preliminary Results. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **32**, 934–957.
- Schlesinger, R., 1978: A Three-Dimensional Numerical Model of an Isolated Thunderstorm: Part I. Comparative Experiments for Variable Ambient Wind Shear. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **35**, 690–713.
- Schmid, W., H.-H. Schiesser, M. Furger, and M. Jenni, 2000: The Origin of Severe Winds in a Tornadic Bow-Echo Storm over Northern Switzerland. *Monthly Weather Review*, **128**, 192–207.
- Schumacher, R. S. and R. H. Johnson, 2005: Organization and Environmental Properties of Extreme-Rain-Producing Mesoscale Convective Systems. *Monthly Weather Review*, **133** (4), 961–976, doi:doi.org/10.1175/MWR2899.1.
- Seifert, A. and K. D. Beheng, 2006: A two-moment cloud microphysics parameterization for mixed-phase clouds. part 1: Model description. *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, **92** (1-2), 45–66, doi:10.1007/s00703-005-0112-4.
- Skamarock, W., M. Weisman, and J. Klemp, 1994: Three-Dimensional evolution of simulated long-lived squall lines. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **51**, 2563–2584.
- Smull, B. F. and R. A. Houze, 1987: Rear Inflow in Squall Lines with Trailing Stratiform Precipitation. *Monthly Weather Review*, **115** (12), 2869–2889.
- Sprenger, M. and H. Wernli, 2015: The LAGRANTO Lagrangian analysis tool - version 2.0. *Geosci. Model Dev.*, **8**, 2569–2586.
- Srivastava, R. C., 1985: A Simple Model of Evaporatively Driven Downdraft: Application to Microburst Downdraft. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **42** (10), 1004–1023.

- Stevens, B., et al., 2019: DYAMOND: the DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains. *Progress in Earth and Planetary Science*, **6** (1), 61, doi:10.1186/s40645-019-0304-z.
- Stuhl, R., 2017: *Practical Meteorology: An Algebra-based Survey of Atmospheric Science*. Univ. of British Columbia, 940 pp.
- Taszarek, M. and L. Kolendowicz, 2013: Sounding-derived parameters associated with tornado occurrence in Poland and Universal Tornadic Index. *Atmospheric Research*, **134**, 186–197.
- Taszarek, M., et al., 2019: Derecho Evolving from a Mesocyclone—A Study of 11 August 2017 Severe Weather Outbreak in Poland: Event Analysis and High-Resolution Simulation. *Monthly Weather Review*, **147** (6), 2283–2306, doi:doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-18-0330.1.
- Thomas, L., N. Malap, W. W. Grabowski, K. Dani, and T. V. Prabha, 2018: Convective environment in pre-monsoon and monsoon conditions over the Indian subcontinent: The impact of surface forcing. *Atmospheric Chemistry And Physics*, **18**, 7473–7488.
- Thompson, R. L., R. Edwards, J. A. Hart, K. L. Elmore, and P. Markowski, 2003: Close Proximity Soundings within Supercell Environments Obtained from the Rapid Update Cycle. *Weather and Forecasting*, **18** (6), 1243–1261.
- Thompson, R. L., C. M. Mead, and R. Edwards, 2007: Effective Storm-Relative Helicity and Bulk Shear in Supercell Thunderstorm Environments. *Weather and Forecasting*, **22** (1), 102–115.
- Thunis, P. and R. Bornstein, 1996: Hierarchy of Mesoscale Flow Assumptions and Equations. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **53** (5), 380–397.
- Tiedtke, M., 1989: A Comprehensive Mass Flux Scheme for Cumulus Parameterization in Large-Scale Models. *Monthly Weather Review*, **117** (8), 1779–1800.
- Trapp, R. J., 2013: *Mesoscale-Convective Processes in the Atmosphere*. Cambridge University Press.
- Trapp, R. J. and M. L. Weisman, 2003: Low Level Mesovortices within Squall Lines and Bow Echoes. Part II: Their Genesis and Implications. *Monthly Weather Review*, **131**, 2804–2823.
- Tsonis, A. A., 2007: *Introduction to Atmospheric Thermodynamics*. Cambridge.
- Ustrnul, Z. and D. Czekierda, 2009: *Atlas ekstremalnych zjawisk meteorologicznych oraz sytuacji synoptycznych w Polsce*. Instytut Meteorologii i Gospodarki Wodnej.

- von Kármán, T., 1940: The engineer grapples with nonlinear problems. *Bull. Amer. Math. Soc.*, **46**, 615–685.
- Wakimoto, R. M., H. V. Murphey, C. A. Davis, and N. T. Atkins, 2006: High Winds Generated by Bow Echoes. Part II: The Relationship between the Mesovortices and Damaging Straight-Line Winds. *Monthly Weather Review*, **134** (10), 2813–2829, doi: 10.1175/MWR3216.1.
- Weisman, M. and R. Rotunno, 2003: "A Theory for Strong, Long-Lived Squall Lines" Revisited. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **61** (4), 361–382.
- Weisman, M. L., 1992: The Role of Convectively Generated Rear-Inflow Jets in the Evolution of Long-Lived Mesoconvective Systems. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **49** (19), 1826–1847.
- Weisman, M. L., 1993: The Genesis of Severe, Long-Lived Bow Echoes. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **50** (4), 645–670.
- Weisman, M. L. and C. A. Davis, 1998: Mechanisms for the Generation of Mesoscale Vortices within Quasi-Linear Convective Systems. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **55**, 2603–2622.
- Weisman, M. L. and J. Klemp, 1982: The Dependence of Numerically Simulated Convective Storms on Vertical Wind Shear and Buoyancy. *Monthly Weather Review*, **110** (6), 504–520.
- Weisman, M. L., W. C. Skamarock, and J. Klemp, 1997: The Resolution Dependence of Explicitly Modeled Convective Systems. *Monthly Weather Review*, **125**, 527–548.
- Weusthoff, T., F. Ament, M. Arpagaus, and M. W. Rotach, 2010: Assessing the Benefits of Convection-Permitting Models by Neighborhood Verification: Examples from MAP D-PHASE. *Monthly Weather Review*, **138** (9), 3418–3433, doi: 10.1175/2010MWR3380.1.
- Wicker, L. J. and W. C. Skamarock, 2002: Time-Splitting Methods for Elastic Models Using Forward Time Schemes. *Monthly Weather Review*, **130**, 2088–2097.
- Wilhelmson, R., 1974: The Life Cycle of a Thunderstorm in Three Dimensions. *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences*, **31**, 1629–1651.
- Wojciechowska, J. and M. Wojciechowski, 2007: Biały szkwał: czegoś takiego jeszcze nie było. *Gazeta Wyborcza*.

- Wójcik, D. K., 2017: Numerical modeling of a downwind-developing mesoscale convective system over the Masurian Lake District. *E3S Web Conf.*, **17**, 00 099, doi: doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/20171700099.
- Wójcik, D. K., M. J. Kurowski, B. Rosa, and M. Ziemiański, 2012: A Study on Parallel Performance of the EULAG F90/95 Code. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, **7204**, 419–428.
- Wójcik, D. K., Z. P. Piotrowski, B. Rosa, and M. Ziemiański, 2015: Realistic weather simulations and forecast verification with COSMO-EULAG, URL www.egu2015.eu, European Geosciences Union General Assembly.
- Wójcik, D. K., B. Rosa, and M. Z. Ziemiański, 2017: Anelastic and compressible EULAG solvers for limited-area numerical Alpine weather prediction in the COSMO consortium., URL vedur.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/oral-abstractsbook.pdf, XXXIVth International Conference on Alpine Meteorology.
- Wójcik, D. K., M. Z. Ziemiański, and W. W. Grabowski, 2019: Numerical Modeling of a Masurian Lake District Severe Convective System from 21 August 2007, URL www.essl.org/cms/european-conferences-on-severe-storms/ecss-2019/, 10th European Conference on Severe Storms.
- Yano, J.-I., M. Z. Ziemiański, M. Cullen, P. Termonia, J. Onvlee, L. Bengtsson, A. Carrasi, and et. al., 2018: Scientific Challenges of Convective-Scale Numerical Weather Prediction. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.*, **99** (4), 699–710.
- Ziemiański, M. Z., D. K. Wójcik, B. Rosa, and Z. P. Piotrowski, 2021: Compressible EULAG dynamical core in COSMO: convective-scale Alpine weather forecasts. *Monthly Weather Review*, doi:10.1175/MWR-D-20-0317.1.
- Zipser, E. J., 1977: Mesoscale and Convective-Scale Downdrafts as Distinct Components of Squall-Line Structure. *Monthly Weather Review*, **105** (12), 1568–1589.